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The impact of Basel III on Bangladeshi commercial banks and their lending towards SMEs.

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ABSTRACT

Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, commonly known as BCBS, introduced Basel III for internationally active banks to directly respond to the last global financial crisis. Basel III addresses the shortcomings of the pre-crisis regulatory framework Basel II. Basel III introduced several essential changes in banks' capital structure, risk management framework, and leverage ratio framework to provide a foundation for a resilient banking system. Although banking regulation may minimise the possibility of a future financial crisis, it may also detain future economic growth. Research suggests that an increase in capital requirement negatively affects banks lending and credit provision to those who deemed a high risk to banks. This study seeks to: (1) examine the effects of Basel III on Bangladeshi commercial banks capital structure; (2) the impact of Basel III on Bangladeshi commercial banks risk-management system and its potential impact on SME lending; and (3) examine the financial implications of Basel III on different generations of Bangladeshi commercial banks.

This study adopted a mixed-method research design to facilitate the use of both quantitative and qualitative data. The researcher used the interview technique, two sampling methods, purposeful sampling and snowball sampling, to collect qualitative data. The quantitative data was collected from 36 Bangladeshi commercial banks' annual reports using a convenience sampling method. The primary data were analysed using NVivo 11 software, while secondary data was analysed using Excel software. The result shows that most BCBs are performing well in maintaining Basel III capital requirements. Still, the majority of the state banks are struggling to raise money to maintain the required capital. Although Basel III improved Bangladeshi commercial banks risk management system, the higher risk-weighted capital requirement for SME lending may influence banks to lend to high credit-rated SMEs compared to low credit-rated SMEs. SME owners believe risk-weights and SME credit rating made SME lending challenging for low credit-rated SMEs compared to Basel II's fixed risk weight. Furthermore, the result indicates that Basel III can reduce non-performing loans (NPL) in the long-term if risk-management principles are followed as per guidelines. The ratio analysis suggests that the second and third generations banks are better than third-generation banks in implementing Basel standard, which positively impacts both generation banks financially.

CERTIFICATION OF THESIS

I certify that the work presented in this dissertation is entirely my effort, except where otherwise acknowledged. This thesis represents my original work and has not previously been submitted for a degree in any other university.

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DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to my wife, Dr Muhtasima Nur-A Tasnim.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ADB	Asian Development Bank
AIRB	Advance Internal Rating Based
AMA	Advanced Measurement Approaches
BB	Bangladesh Bank
BCB	Bangladeshi Commercial Banks
BCBS	Basel Committee on Banking Supervision
BIS	Bank for International Settlement
CAPM	Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM)
CCB	Capital Conservation Buffer
CET1	Common Equity Tier
CSA	Chittagong Stock Exchange
CVAR	Credit Value Adjustment Risk
DSA	Dhaka Stock Exchange
FCB	Foreign Commercial Bank
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
IIF	Institute of International Finance
IRB	Internal Ratings Based
LCR	Liquidity Coverage Ratio
LDC	Least Developed Countries
MAG	Macroeconomic Assessment Group
MFI	Microfinance Institutions
MRA	Micro-credit Regulatory Authorities
NBFI	Nonbank financial
NGO	Non-Government funded organisation
NPL	Non-performing Loans
NSFR	Net Stable Funding Ratio (NSFR)

OECD	The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PCB	Public Commercial Bank
RAROR	Risk-adjusted Rate of Return
RMD	Risk Management Department
ROA	Return on Asset
RWA	Risk-weighted Asset
SB	Shonali Bank
SCB	State Commercial Bank

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Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction

The recent global financial crisis has resulted in a complete transformation of worldwide financial regulation. The global financial industry has witnessed the arrival of regulatory adjustments and the introduction of the new regulatory framework by regulatory authorities, aiming to reduce the possibility and potential negative impact of future financial crises (Izquierdo et al., 2017). These regulatory burdens are also geographically fragmented. Although the banking regulatory reforms introduced due to the last financial crisis, regulators also initiated various national legislation, which compromised the banking industry's consistency and predominantly affected banks globally. Therefore, any financial regulation needs to ensure a balance between stability and efficiency. Izquierdo et al., (2017) suggest that regulatory bodies should estimate the qualitative and quantitative impact of new regulation on other industries associated with the banking industry so that new law reduces future financial uncertainty without adversely impacting other industries' growth.

Historically, banking regulators have seen capital regulation as one of the significant components of regulatory reform. The banking industry regulators consider banks' financial solvency as the main element of their resilience. As a result, banks' base capital need and capital need during adverse scenarios, known as stress testing, have become a popular supervisory and market discipline tool for regulators in recent days. The tightening of banks' capital using regulatory capital automatically limits banks' ability to finance businesses directly, pushing enterprises to use the capital market for their finance needs. However, companies that cannot use the capital market to raise their capital must rely upon banks' finance. Thus, as mentioned earlier, capital requirement limits banks' direct finance capability; businesses that depend on banks' finance suffer the most due to tightening the regulatory capital requirement.

SME's worldwide have played a vital role in advancing economic and industrial development by providing the necessary foundation for increasing incomes in less developed economies to reduce poverty (Akterujjaman, 2012). Flexible financing source has been considered a crucial factor in developing the SME sector in the

emerging economies. Research suggests that the SME sector notably lacks an innovative financial model which could go beyond the traditional banking finance source and provide timely credits to SME's (ADB, 2016). In the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) area, SME's are the primary employment source and provide 70% of jobs and generate 50% to 60% value-added (OECD, 2014). In emerging economies, SME's contribute 45% of total employment and 33% of GDP (OECD, 2014). If the informal source's contribution was taken into account, SME's contribute more than 50% of employment and GDP in most countries regardless of income level (IFC, 2010).

Although the primary focus of this study is to analyse Basel III's impact on Bangladeshi banks' capital structure and their lending to SME's, the current Basel version is the evolution of Basel I and Basel II. Therefore, to understand Basel III's effect on banks and its potential impact on a country's economic situation, it is necessary to compare Basel III with its origin. Bank for International Settlement (BIS) was established in 1930 to function as an international financial institution and to provide co-operation between the world's central banks (BCBS, 2016). Since the collapse of the Bretton Woods System, the world's first monetary management which organised financial relations among independent nation-states, followed by several economic casualties, the central bank governors from G10 countries formed a committee on banking regulation and supervisory practice. It was later changed to Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS) (BCBS, 2016). BCBS's first regulation was the Basel Capital Accord, commonly known as Basel I (1988), followed by Basel II (2004) and Basel III (2010).

Basel II's progression to Basel III has intensely affected the banking industry's performances and behaviour, which seriously affected banks' capability to serve the SME sector (Izquierdo et al., 2017). Because of the size, SME's tend to be very reliant on banks' credit. Therefore, the availability of credit to SME's plays a critical role in the current economic environment. SME's have a high contribution to total employment and GDP in both developed and emerging economies (Izquierdo et al., 2017). Basel III has represented a regulatory overhaul for banks which has significantly increased the quality and minimum mandatory regulatory capital. New liquidity ratio requirement and high regulatory capital requirement in Basel III have directed banks towards less risky assets. One of the significant concerns among

central banks since the Basel Committee announced Basel III had been the impact of new Basel regulation on SME loans. A valid concern has been raised by the national supervisor and the central banks that more strict law and other additional regulatory requirements would reduce banks' willingness to finance the SME sector. The BCBS argued that Basel III had assigned lower risk weight for SME lending based on SME's credit rating and credit rating should facilitate SME's access to finance. However, SME's credit rating directly influence banks capital requirement. This study investigates whether changes in capital requirement based on risk-weighted asset (RWA) would facilitate SME lending and influence Bangladeshi commercial banks' (BCBs) lending decisions to Bangladeshi SMEs.

1.2 Background

1.2.1 Bangladesh

Bangladesh, officially known as the Peoples Republic of Bangladesh, is the world's 8th most populated country (Guhathakurta, 2013). Although Bangladesh has a higher population than Russia, and the Bengali language is ranked 6th globally, Bangladesh remains unknown to many people (Guhathakurta, 2013). Bangladesh rarely attracts global media, but it is either a natural disaster or political turbulence. However, it does not highlight the rich historical background, bravery, and patriotism of Bangladeshis, giving birth to modern Bangladesh. Bangladeshis are the only nation that sacrificed their lives to protect their mother tongue on 21 February 1952, which is currently celebrated as International Mother Language Day worldwide.

1.2.2 History

Although Bangladesh has existed as an independent country for 46 years, its linguistic and cultural roots can be traced back in history to as early as the 7th century (Schendel, 2009). According to Schendel (2009), Bengali, the national language of Bangladesh, existed in the 7th century and the first literature in the Bengali language emerged in the 11th century. Until the 12th century, Hinduism and Buddhism were the dominant religions in this area until Muslims invaded in the 13th century (Schendel, 2009). Eventually, conversion to Islam and settlement in this area was begun primarily by Arab and Persian traders and preachers. Since then, the land was ruled by Turks, Afghan, North Indians, Arakanese, Ethiopians and British (Schendel, 2009). Although the Portuguese established the first European

settlement in the 15th century, the land remained mostly independent until 1757 when the British East India Company defeated local ruler Nawab Shiraj-uddoula by which then declared itself as *de facto* ruler of Bangladesh (Schendel, 2009). Since then, Bengalis resisted against British rulers from time to time(Heitzman and Worden, 1989). In1946, the Muslim League won the general election and British rule ended through India and Pakistan's partition. East Bengal (Bangladesh) became a part of Pakistan and was named East Pakistan(Heitzman and Worden, 1989).

Bangladesh was born out of two vicious detachments. The first partition was in 1947 from the Indian sub-continent was based on the religious belief of the Bengal population (Schendel, 2009). The sizeable Muslim area of East Bengal became East Pakistan and the Hindu majority area in the west became West Bengal in India. Although East Pakistan was part of Pakistan (former West Pakistan), they failed to meet the political objectives of Bangladeshi (former East Pakistan) elites which led to a second violent partition in 1971(Heitzman and Worden, 1989). After nine months of violent bloodshed between the West Pakistan army and Bangladeshi freedom fighters, known as "Mukti Bahini", backed up by the Indian military, Bangladesh earned independence from West Pakistan by winning a battle against one of the largest armies of that time (Heitzman and Worden, 1989).

Figure 1.1: Bengal's detachment of 1947 and Pakistan's detachment of 1971. (Source: National Maritime Museum 2017)

1.2.3 Demography and population

Bangladesh is an ethnically homogeneous country and the name of the country originated from the Bengali ethno linguistic group. Several dialects are spoken

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throughout the country. The dialects spoken in the Chittagong and Sylhet division are unique compared to other parts of the country. Although the official language is Bengali, several Bengali dialects are spoken throughout the country, such as Chittagonian, Sylethi, Chakma, etc. On top of dialect, several Indic languages such as Manipuri, Assamese, Bihari, Rohingya are spoken in some parts of the country. Bangladesh has situated in South Asia and shares north, east and west land borders with India and the south-east border with Myanmar. The south side border lies with The Bay of Bengal which is approximately equal to Bangladesh's land size.

Figure1.2: The map of Bangladesh (Source: National Maritime Museum 2017)

Other surrounding countries are Nepal, Bhutan, and China, with which Bangladesh does not share any border. The total land area is estimated to 147,570 Square KM approximately. (CIA, 2016). The country's capital is known as Dhaka, one of the fastest-growing capital cities globally (ADB, 2015). The second-largest town in the country is Chittagong.

Bangladesh is a highly populated country. However, Bangladesh is ranked 8th in terms of population and 95th in land area. According to the last government census in 2011, Bangladesh's population was estimated at 142 million (World Bank, 2013). However, based on the statistical yearly increase, the population was estimated to become 156.20 million in 2016, approximately 2.19% of the total world population

(CIA, 2017). The population density is 3,279 per square mile, equivalent to 1266 per square kilometre(United Nation, 2015). The population growth rate was estimated to be approximately 1.05% as of July 2016 (CIA, 2017)

Figure 1.3: Bangladesh Population Pyramid (Source: CIA, 2016)

1.2.4 Religion

In 1972, the first constitution of Bangladesh recognised secularism as one of the four basic principles. However, secularism was withdrawn from the constitution in 1977. However, it was restored in 2010 by the Bangladesh Supreme Court, and Islam remained a state religion(Albinson, 2016). In terms of faith, 88.9% of Bangladeshis are Muslim, 9.8% Hindu and the remainder are Buddhist, Christian, and Atheist (CIA, 2016). Although religious belief is a significant part of Bengali culture, there are no boundaries among Bangladeshis when it is time to celebrate religious festivals.

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Figure 1.4: Religious belief in Bangladesh by population. Source: CIA (2016)

1.2.5 Ethnicity

Approximately 98% of Bangladeshis are Bengali ethnolinguistic group which extends to West Bengal of India (Albinson, 2016). The minority ethnic group comprises several tribal communities, including Chakma, Mog, Murong, Khashia, Garo, Shawtal, Bihari, Rohingyas etc. Although *Cultural Institution for Small Anthropological Groups Act 2010* recognises 27 ethnic groups throughout the country; other sources claim there are at least 75 ethnic groups in Bangladesh (CIA, 2017). According to the census in 1981, the tribal population was estimated to 897,828 (Heitzman and Worden, 1989).

Most of these tribal ethnic communities live in Chittagong Hill Tracks, Rajshahi and Sylhet division. These ethnic groups are different from the general population in terms of culture, Religion, and language. Many of these ethnic groups have their social boundaries and most of them follow Buddhism or Hinduism. Apart from tribal ethnic groups, other ethnic groups belong to the refugee category.

Biharis are an Urdu speaking ethnic group who came from West Bengal during the partition in 1947. During the Bangladesh liberation war in 1971, most of Bihari supported Pakistan and helped the Pakistan Army commit mass murder (Farzana, 2009). Many Biharis migrated to Pakistan after Bangladesh achieved its independence in 1971. However, the Pakistan government refused to take them back and the Bangladesh government recognised them as Bihari refugees. There are approximately one million Bihari refugees in Bangladesh (Farzana, 2009).

Many Rohingya refugees in Bangladesh migrated from neighbouring country Myanmar through the southeast border of Bangladesh. Rohingyas are a Muslim ethnic group that fled persecution in the Rakhine state of Myanmar due to the mass murder and violence conducted against them by Buddhist Monks and the Myanmar army because of their religious beliefs (Ganguly and Miliate, 2015). Approximately 250,000 Rohingyas migrated to Bangladesh between 1991 and 2010 and the migration continues (Ganguly and Miliate, 2015).

1.2.6 Economic Overview

Bangladesh has made extraordinary progress in the fight against poverty, supported by sustainable economic growth. According to the World Bank (2018), Bangladesh has reduced its poverty from 44.2% in 1991 to 13.8% in 2016/2017. Bangladesh GDP growth has been constant at over 6% for the last few years, reaching 7.3% in 2016/17 (World Bank, 2018). Bangladesh reached lower-middle-income

Figure 1.5: Bangladesh GDP per capita (World Bank, 2018)

country status in 2015 and rapid economic growth enabled Bangladesh to achieve the UN's Least Developed Countries (LDC) list for the first time in 2018. Bangladesh is expected to move out of this list by 2024 (World Bank, 2018). World Bank (2018) stated that creating new jobs should be a top development priority for Bangladesh, given that two million youth enter the job market every year. World Bank (2018) also suggested that Bangladesh needs to remove barriers to high growth posed by poor transporting infrastructure, low access to energy, complex business regulations, among others.

1.3 Basel III and SME's

Basel's objective is to eliminate the probability of bank failure and reduce the risk associated with banking operations (BCBS, 2011). The Basel accord is designed to strengthen the global banking system's stability and eliminate any competitive inequalities between banks from different countries by applying one uniform standard (BCBS, 2011). Basel III brought four significant changes to the existing Basel II regulation. Firstly, Basel III significantly increased both the quality and quantity of banks' mandatory capital so that banks can absorb future losses (BCBS, 2016). Secondly, Basel III introduces leverage ratios for risk-based measure (BCBS, 2016). The risk-based standard has been critical to perform sanity checks and understand the risk-based framework results. Thirdly, Basel III introduces two capital buffers. Conservation buffer directs banks' to build a strong capital base while the countercyclical buffer works as a safeguard for banks' against rapid credit growth (BCBS, 2016). Lastly, Basel III's liquidity risk management framework and global liquidity standard ensure that banks efficiently handle their risks and maintain sufficient liquidity buffers (BCBS, 2016).

Research suggests that higher liquidity ratio and tight regulatory capital requirements influence banks to concentrate more on less risky assets such as sovereign bonds (Admati et al., 2010). Under Basel II, banks' minimum regulatory capital requirement was 8% of total Risk-weighted Asset (RWA). RWA is defined as banks' assets exposed to risk and calculated by assigning a risk exposure to banks' assets to find banks' total real-world risk exposure (Financial Times, 2018). Basel II set a fixed 75% of risk weight to SME lending, given that lending to one borrower doesn't exceed over BDT 10 million (approximately \$130K) (Financial Times, 2018). However, banks can reduce SME loan RWA exposure by considering collateral value given that supplied collateral meets eligible criteria (Bangladesh Bank, 2010).

However, Basel III assigned variable risk-weight ranging from 20% to 150% to SME's and variable risk-weight depends on SME's credit rating (Bangladesh Bank, 2010). For example, SME 1 credit rating attracts 20% risk-weight, whereas SME 6 attracts 150% risk-weight (see table 2.8). Banks' can also take account of collateral value while calculating Risk-Weighted Asset (RWA) exposure. According to Basel III, banks' minimum capital requirement increases to 10% of RWA, of which 6% must be

Tier 1 capital (see table 2.3)(BCBS, 2011). Furthermore, Basel III introduced 2.5% of RWA as Capital Conservation Buffer (CCB) which banks need to rise year by year. An increase in the minimum capital requirement and CCB establish an automatic limiting factor in banks' lending capability. High-risk lending generates higher RWA capital for banks and banks either need to raise their money or reduce RWA to maintain required capital levels, as Basel III guideline stated. As banks tend to shift from high-risk investment, when capital requirement increases, it is assumed that banks are most likely to prefer to reduce high-risk investment rather than raising capital to back high-risk investment. Loans to SME's are considered high risk because of their size and uncertainty; the increase in capital requirement most likely will cause a reduction in SME lending if loans are not backed up by high-value collateral (Admati et al., 2010). Furthermore, suppose banks are struggling to raise capital to maintain minimum capital requirement. In that case, it is assumed that banks are most likely to shift from high-risk investment to low-risk activities that generate less RWA capital for them (Admati et al., 2010).

Research suggests that Basel III's capital restrictions can negatively impact banks' lending behaviours to SME's (Admati et al., 2010; Miles, Yang and Marcheggiano, 2012). Firstly, the capital requirement can work as a bottleneck to SME lending because banks can't lend to SME's without increasing their capital under Basel III, limiting their lending scopes to SME's (Admati et al., 2010). Secondly, strict regulatory capital increases most likely will increase financing costs for banks that are likely to be paid by borrowers, in this case, SME owners (Miles, Yang, and Marcheggiano, 2012). SME's are already neglected by banks in developing countries because of their inability to provide high-value collateral. Therefore, introducing new regulatory policies, which increase banks' capital requirement in line with their lending to SME's, may constrain SME's access to finance. This situation may adversely impact SMEs' future growth as well as the overall economic development of Bangladesh.

1.4 Research aim and objectives

This research aims to identify how the bank managers and SME owners experience Basel III's impact on BCBS ability to lend to SME's. Considering the recent banking reform introduced by BCBS, this research aims to provide a detailed analysis of

Basel III's effects on BCBs and their lending capability towards SME's. This research also aims to analyse Basel III's effect on BCBs' capital structure and existing risk management system and whether together they have any impact on BCBs' risk appetite level and risk-taking. Based on the above research aim, this research has the following objectives:

- 1- To investigate the microeconomic implications of Basel III on BCBs.
- 2- To investigate Basel III's potential impact on BCBs capital structure, risk management system, and non-performing loans (NPL).
- 3- To investigate the impact of Basel III on BCBs' lending towards SME's.

1.5 Research questions

Research questions should be unambiguous, brief, and focused and should provide an open statement of what the researcher wants to investigate (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

This study aims to investigate the impact of Basel III on BCBs and whether Basel III influences BCBs' lending behaviour and restricts SME's access to finance. To analyse and comprehensively answer the above primary research question, the researcher expands on the preliminary question using the following sub-questions.

RQ 1 – How does Basel III affect the capital structure of Bangladeshi commercial banks?

RQ 2 - How does Basel III improve banks risk management systems and how it impacts banks' lending?

RQ 3- Does Basel III influence Bangladeshi commercial banks' lending decision to SME's? Does Basel III affect Bangladeshi SME's accessibility to credits?

RQ 4 – Whether a different generation of banks who implemented Basel III standard have better financial performance?

The researcher adopted a mixed-method research design to facilitate quantitative and qualitative data to answer the above question. The researcher used the interview technique and two sampling methods, purposeful sampling and snowball sampling, to collect qualitative data. Moreover, quantitative data was collected from

the BCBs annual report using a convenience sampling method. Primary data collected using the interview method was analysed using NVivo 11 software, while secondary data was used to perform ratio analysis using Microsoft excel software.

1.6 Research motivation and contribution

It was argued that the higher capital requirement introduced in Basel III should make the banking system more robust and reduce the probability of a future financial crisis. Although the Global Financial Crisis revealed weaknesses in many western banks, both Asian economies and Asian banks coped well with the situation. None of the major Asian banks needed bailouts from their government (Park, Ramayandi and Shin, 2013). All internationally active banks adopted Basel III regardless of their situation during the last financial stress, even though studies suggest that many Asian countries remained mostly unaffected by the recent financial crisis (Park, Ramayandi and Shin, 2013). When regulatory capital requirement rises, banks naturally reduce lending to reduce RWA capital requirement (Heuvel 2004; Gambacorta and Mistrulli, 2004). Reduction in banks' lending is specifically bad news for Bangladeshi SME's because Bangladeshi SME's heavily rely upon traditional banking sources for finance rather than the capital market (ADB, 2014). Moreover, when banks reduce their lending, they are most likely to mitigate high-risk lending first (Altman and Sabato, 2005) and SME's are considered high risk because of the high mortality rate (ADB, 2014). Therefore, Basel III is expected to have some adverse effect on Bangladeshi SME's given that the SME sector is heavily dependent on banks' for their financial need.

According to Basel III, BCBs need to keep more assets tied to capital by 2019 to maintain the required capital level. Furthermore, increasing and sustaining a higher capital ratio is costly for banks and leads to a downward shift of credit and loan supply (Altman and Sabato, 2005). Many economists suggested that reducing credit and loan supply negatively affects banks' micro-economic activities, affecting their lending behaviours towards borrowers, particularly high-risk borrowers (Bliss and Kaufman 2002; Heuvel 2004; Gambacorta and Mistrulli, 2004). Like many least developed countries, SME's are the backbone of the Bangladeshi economy and play an essential role in developing the rural economy and reducing poverty by providing employment. Furthermore, SME's account for 90% of private enterprises in

Bangladesh and this figure most likely would go up if informal and micro-enterprises are taken in to account (ADB, 2015). It was estimated that SME's contributed 25% to Bangladesh's total GDP and 40% to total manufacturing outputs (ADB, 2015). So, it is clear that SMEs employ a large proportion of the Bangladeshi workforce

Many studies regarding Basel III's impact have focused on Basel regulation's effect on banks' capital structure and possible shortcoming on banks' capital (Allen et al., 2012; Cardone-Riportella, Trujillo-Ponce and Briozzo, 2011; Altman and Sabato, 2005). They studied the potential impact of Basel II and Basel III regulation on banks' lending behaviour towards SME's in developed countries which the researcher considers a western phenomenon. The motivation for using the Bangladeshi context is that Bangladesh belongs to the developing country's category and remained largely unaffected during the last financial crisis. Bangladesh's GDP growth rate remained over 6% for the previous few years and recently, in 2017, it grew to 7.3% (World Bank, 2018). As SME's are considered the backbone of the economy and contributed an impressive 25% to the GDP since 2014, a possible reduction in SME finance means a reduction in their contribution to Bangladesh GDP (ADB, 2015; The independent, 2018). As the world bank predicted that Bangladesh would attain the developed country's status by 2024, a reduction in GDP contribution from Bangladeshi SME's most likely to harm Bangladesh's journey towards the developed country status. Although BCBs' started to implement Basel III in 2015, Basel III's potential impact on BCBs' lending behaviours towards SME's is somewhat unclear. Since implementing Basel III regulation is mandatory for all BCBs, this research is driven by a desire to determine how Basel III has affected BCBs and whether Basel III has influenced BCBs lending behaviour towards SME's.

A few studies in the existing literature have focused on the importance of banks' finance to SME development in Bangladesh (Alam and Ullah 2006; Ahmed and Chowdhury, 2009; Chowdhury, Azam Islam, 2013). However, none of these investigated Basel III's impact on banks' capital and how an increase in capital requirement may affect banks' lending towards SME's. Alam and Ullah (2006) examined the major obstacle to SME financing in Bangladesh. They concluded that commercial banks lack the motivation to invest in SME's because of low profit and higher operating cost. Ahmed and Chowdhury (2009) studied problems relating to SME development in Bangladesh. They found several issues that contribute to the

Bangladeshi SME industry's low development rate, including lack of finance, necessary government support, essential skills, etc. Chowdhury, Azam, and Islam (2013) researched the problems faced by Bangladeshi SME's while seeking finance. Their research found that lack of high-quality collateral assets, excessive paperwork demanded by commercial banks, inadequate government support, etc., work as a barrier for SME's to access bank finance.

There have been several research studies carried out on the impact of Basel III regulation on banks and their lending towards Spanish SME's (Cardone-Riportella, Trujillo-Ponce, and Briozzo (2011); Izquierdo et al., 2017) and Impact Assessment by ACCA (2011), IIF (2010) and OECD (2012). However, no article exists in the existing literature investigating Basel III's impact on BCBs' and their lending towards SME's to the researcher's best knowledge. Therefore, this study will contribute to the literature in two ways. Firstly, contribute to the existing literature by investigating Basel III's impact on Bangladeshi commercial banks and SME's. Secondly, by extending existing research by Riportella, Trujillo-Ponce and Briozzo (2011) and Izquierdo et al., (2017) to the Bangladeshi context.

1.7 Summary of the Result

RQ 1 – How does Basel III affect the capital structure of Bangladeshi commercial banks?

Basel III proposed a similar risk-based approach as Basel II while calculating minimum capital requirement for banks. Research respondents view changes made by Basel III in capital structure represent a significant change in BCBs' capital holding. The majority of the respondents sees these changes in the capital structure as positive and stated that this change would strengthen BCBs' capital structures and loss-absorbing capacities. Although respondents positively welcomed changes in the capital requirement, they are concern about the method used by BCBs to raise capital. To increase Tier 1 capital, BCBs are using retained earnings and the right shares. However, both approaches are not preferable by shareholders because an increase in retained earnings reduces dividend payment, and the right share issue reduces investors' existing investment values.

On the other hand, BCBs are raising Tier 2 capital, mostly using subordinated bonds. Respondents expressed different opinions while asked whether BCBs can raise the required money to meet the minimum capital requirement. It was observed that some respondents think BCBs may struggle during the implementation stage, but they are capable of raising minimum regulatory capital. However, some respondents stated that most PCBs/FCBs are apt to raise new money but it may be difficult for SCBs to raise capital. Further investigation on 36 BCBs financial statement analysis revealed that some SCBs were already struggling to meet the Basel II minimum capital requirement. In 2017 all sampled SCBs had capital deficiencies under Basel III. A recent report from Bangladesh Bank also suggests that FCB CAR were the highest among other BCBs and all SCB failed to raise the required minimum capital in 2019.

RQ 2 - How does Basel III improve banks risk management systems and how it impacts banks' lending?

Basel III introduced new risk management policies and guidance to enhance banks' existing risk management frameworks. Respondents stated that Basel III introduced both structural and procedural changes into the existing risk management framework. It was observed that Basel III prescribed both technical and structural changes to strengthen banks' risk management strategy. Technical changes indicate that new changes are based around banks risk-based capital and liquidity measure. As per the respondent's opinion, technical changes strengthen banks risk management strategy because recent changes are integrated with banks' overall strategic planning to identify, monitor, and mitigate risks.

Furthermore, it was also evident that BCBs implemented a risk management benchmark that Bangladesh Bank regularly reviews to ensure Basel III compliance. According to respondents, BCBs established a separate risk management division, board risk committee and asset-liability committee. Respondents recognised the Basel III risk management framework as positive to control banks' risk appetite. They think different risk parameter and risk handling procedures introduced by Basel III positively influence their banks' risk-taking and help commercial banks reduce non-performing loans by controlling banks' risk appetite. This statement by respondents was further analysed in the BCBs NPL situation. It was observed that respondents think Basel III risk management policies have helped them to build a safe credit

policy by controlling banks' risk appetite and risk-taking. Respondents also said credit risk management guidelines by Basel III help them make better lending decisions and reduce non-performing loans. However, It was evident that PCBs/FCBs were able to reduce their NPL where all SCBs failed to control their NPL due to corruption in the credit granting process.

RQ 3- Does Basel III influence Bangladeshi commercial banks' lending decision to SME's? Did Basel III affect Bangladeshi SME's accessibility to credits?

Basel III introduced a new credit rating and different risk weight on SME lending based on SME's credit rating. Basel III has indeed made it easy for SME's to access credits. Still, respondents said Based III had made access to credit easy for those SME's which have satisfactory credit ratings and can provide high-value collateral. However, SME's with lower credit ratings or can't offer high-value collateral; respondents said they are most likely to be refused by the Bank. This finding was also supported by SME owners who said it is easy for SME's to get a loan if they can provide high-value collateral. They said they have experienced that banks give priority to those who have good credit ratings and good collateral over low credit ratings and less valuable collateral. Moreover, Basel III has increased SME's cost of getting finance from banks, and SME owners pointed out that they had had to bribe cash for finance although they had good credit ratings and secured their loans using high-value collateral.

RQ 4 – Whether a different generation of banks who implemented Basel III standard have better financial performance?

It was observed from 36 BCBs financial statement analysis from 2014 to 2019 that SCBs continued to fail to raise capital from 2014. The number of capital shortfalls among SCB increased gradually over the year. Moreover, the higher minimum capital requirement also altered the PCBs/FCBs dividend policy. It was observed a sharp increase in the number of zero dividend-paying banks from 2015 to 2018. Lastly, the performance gap among different generations of BCBs who successfully implemented Basel III standards between 2019 has been measured in the last part of the financial analysis chapter. The analysis clearly shows that newly established banks are ahead in almost all Basel standards than first-generation banks.

1.8 Structure of the thesis

This study is structured as follows

Chapter 2 discusses the brief history of Basel III and the current state of SME's in Bangladesh. It also examines the literature related to the impact of regulatory capital requirement on banks and banks' operation. Chapter 3 discusses the theoretical framework and presents agency theory to address the research questions. Chapter 4 discusses the research methodology adopted in this research, including how research data was sourced, collected and used in this research and how collected data was analysed. Chapter 5 outlines the analysis of this study. Chapter 6 shows Basel III's impact on a different generation of banks financial performances who implemented Basel III norms. Chapter 7 concludes the outcomes of the analysis and presents the limitations of the study. This chapter also outlines the contributions of this study and suggests scope for further research.

Chapter 2 Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The majority of the academic literature on banking regulations relates to the impact of banking regulation on banks and how banks may react due to the new code. Interestingly, banks' capital seems to be a controlling instrument to regulators for improving the banking industry's financial stability. Therefore, the impact of changes in banks' capital structure was of significant interest to researchers as changes in capital structure lead to a change in banks' operations and their services to stakeholders. On the other hand, existing literature views SME's as a troubled industry. The majority of the articles in the current literature regarding SMEs are related to SMEs' difficulties in accessing formal credit sources.

Moreover, the number of articles relating to SME's problems worldwide is relatively high compared to the number of articles on Basel III and SME. However, research on Basel III's impact on Bangladeshi SMEs is almost non-existent, according to the author's best knowledge, because Basel III is a relatively new regulation and BCBS are yet to finish the full implementation of Basel III. Following a list of a seminal article covering the impact of banking regulation on banks' capital and their potential influence on SMEs' access to credit.

Author	Title	Samples	Findings
Gambacorta and Mistrulli (2004)	Does bank capital affect lending behaviour?	Financial data from 556 Italian financial institutions, of which 155 Italian banks and 401 Italian credit cooperatives.	Bank capital matters in propagating different types of shocks to lending and the existence of regulatory capital constraints and imperfections in the market for bank fund-raising.
Altman & Sabato (2005)	Modelling Credit Risk for SMEs: Evidence from The Us Market,	Over 2,000 U.S. firms (with sales less than \$65 million) from 1994 to 2002.	They showed the impact of credit risk capital charge if SME's are categorised as corporate rather than retail entities.
Berger and Udell (2006)	A complete conceptual framework for SME finance.		They argued that financial institutions' traditional complex lending technologies affect SME's credit availability and often yields misleading conclusion.
Cardone-Riportella, Trujillo-Ponce, and Briozzo (2011)	What does Basel Capital Accords mean for SMEs?	The study uses an extensive database of Spanish Firms and covers the period from 2005 to 2009.	They impact Basel II and Basel III on the Bank's capital requirements in SMEs' portfolios when the internal ratings-based (IRB) approach is used.

Chapter 2 Literature Review

Saurina and Trucharte (2004)	The Impact of Basel II on Lending to Small-and-Medium-Sized-Firms: A Regulatory Policy Assessment based on Spanish Credit Register Data.	Financial data from the Spanish Credit Register for the period 1994 to 2001	They Found that the Bank's capital requirement for SME lending depends on banks chosen probability of default method, and if SME's were put in the corporate category, the capital requirement for SME landings was reduced significantly irrespective of the method chosen by the banks.
BCBS (2004)	Basel II: International Convergence of Capital Measurement and Capital Standards: a Revised Framework,	Legal obligation for banks	Basel II is a second international banking regulatory accord based on three main pillars: minimal capital requirements, regulatory supervision, and market discipline.
BCBS (2011)	Basel III: A Global Regulatory Framework For More Resilient Banks And Banking Systems	Legal obligation for banks	Basel III is an internationally agreed set of measures developed by the BCBS in response to the financial crisis of 2007-09. The standards aim to strengthen the regulation, supervision and risk management of banks.
Alam and Ullah (2006)	A complete conceptual framework for SME finance.	SME finance data between 2001 to 2003	They researched the major obstacle faced by Bangladeshi SMEs in accessing finance and recommended ways to overcome them.
Izquierdo et al., (2017)	Impact of capital regulation on SMEs credit.	Credit growth data of the Spanish banking sector between 2003 to 2016	They showed that SMEs ' access to credit could be positively influenced by applying supporting factors in loan data on Basel II and Basel III.
Barth, Caprio, and Levine, (2004)	Bank regulation and supervision: what works best	Database on bank regulation and supervision in 107 countries.	They suggested rather than increasing capital, policies that force accurate information disclosure, empower private-sector corporate control of banks, and foster incentives for private agents work best to promote bank development, performance and stability.
Beck et al., (2006)	The determinants of financing obstacles	The authors use survey data on a sample of over 10,000 firms from 80 countries	They suggested older, larger, and foreign-owned firms report fewer financing obstacles due to their which shed doubts on other classifications used in the literature. Their results also suggest that institutional development is the most crucial country characteristic explaining cross-country variation in firms' financing obstacles.

ACCA (2011)	Framing the debate: Basel III and SMEs	Discussion Paper on impact assessment of Basel III on SME's credit eligibility from Bank.	Smaller businesses have less bargaining power against a bank and are likely to face higher credit costs in the future and small firms are now expected to turn towards other sources of credit.
Magda (2014)	Basel III: Impact on Banking Sector & SMEs Financing		This article identifies and underlines the main measures applicable in the present, their implementation schedule and possible effects on SMEs financing
BCBS (1999)	Capital Requirements and Bank Behaviour: The Impact of the Basel Accord	Discussion Paper	This paper looks at two possible side effects. Firstly, whether in some periods, capital requirements may have affected bank lending, thereby causing a credit crunch. Secondly, whether the introduction of fixed minimum requirements for banks affected their competitiveness relative to other intermediation forms.
Berger (2006)	Potential competitive effects of Basel II on banks in SME credit markets in the United States	They used data from the June 2002 Call Report and the May 2002 Survey of Terms of Bank Lending to Businesses.	IRB approach positively influences SME access to credit compared to the standardised approach.
Martynova (2015).	Effect of Bank Capital Requirements on Economic Growth: A Survey	Empirical Research	Higher capital requirements can reduce credit supply and decrease credit demand by raising lending rates which may slow down economic growth.
Berger and Udell (1994)	Did Risk-Based Capital Allocate Bank Credit and Cause a 'Credit Crunch' in the U.S.?	Bank lending data on virtually all U.S. banks from 1979 to 1992	Higher capital requirements encourage banks to reduce lending to the riskiest categories of borrowers such as SMEs.

Table: 2.1 The list of seminal article

2.2 Evolution of Basel Accord

2.2.1 Basel I

BCBS introduced *the minimum capital standard framework* known as Basel I in 1988 (BCBS, 1988). Basel, I was introduced to establish a level playing field for banking regulation (Ramona, 2013). Most importantly, it was intended to improve the international banking system's safety and reliability (Elizalde, 2007). Basel I was welcomed by the global banking industry because they assumed that Basel I would stop banks from taking excessive risk, especially regarding credit risk.

The Basel I accord required banks to hold a fixed capital ratio of a minimum of 8% of RWA (BCBS, 2016). According to Basel I, total capital is divided into two tiers; core capital (Tier 1), containing equity and other reserves, must be 4% of total capital and supplementary capital (tier 2) is left up to the national supervisor to choose. Eventually, Basel I was adopted in G10 member (currently G20) countries' banks but in most countries with internationally active banks. The Basel I accord was amended over time. Although Basel I was highly admired for achieving its initial goal to set a capital requirement for banks, it is severely criticised for its low-risk sensitivity of minimum capital requirement (Elizalde, 2007). Moreover, Basel I was also criticised for its influence of lower capital requirement for greater risk-taking and for providing regulatory capital arbitrage practices by banks (BCBS, 1999, Jones, 2000).

2.2.2 Basel II

Basel II is the second of the Basel accord. Published in 2004, Basel II was intended to create an international banking standard and help banks control their risk exposures using their capital requirement (Ramona, 2013). Basel's successor relied upon three pillars (minimum capital requirements, supervisory review, and market discipline) to attain the financial industry's safety and soundness. (Elizalde, 2007). Basel II comprises three main objectives.

Pillar 1: Minimum capital requirement for credit, market and operational risk which should be calculated using different methods introduced by Basel II (Ramona, 2013)

Pillar 2: Supervisory review provided assessment tools to national supervisors and empowered central banks to determine whether a bank has adequate resources to act as a financial intermediary (Ramona, 2013).

Pillar 3: Market discipline and transparency required banks to disclose their financial information regarding their reserves, risks, management, etc. (Ramona, 2013).

Figure 2.1: Basel II (BCBS, 2006)

Basel II was criticised for the following reason. Udeshi (2004) stated that Basel II created *Pro-Cyclical Process*. The *pro-cyclical Process* means that banks require less capital to cover risk exposure if there is an economic boom in a country. If that country's economy falls, banks need more capital for covering their risk exposure.

Basel II was also heavily criticised for the excessive use of credit rating systems provided by external credit rating agencies (Hussain et al., 2012). Many banks didn't have any credit assessment department, and most relied upon an external credit rating agency. Consequently, when external credit rating agencies wrongly assessed risks, banks could not identify the conflict (Teply, 2010). Moreover, risk measurement approaches like Advanced Internal Rating Based (AIRB) for credit risk and Advanced Measurement Approaches (AMA) for operational risk were too complicated for small banks to follow and only implemented by larger banks (Mohanty, 2008). This conflict in measuring credit and operational risk influenced many banks to take additional risk.

2.2.3 Basel III

The reckless trading of European and US banks and larger investment banks' insolvency, such as Lehman Brothers, triggered the worst financial recession since 1929 (Angelkort and Stuwe, 2011). Even before Lehman Brothers collapsed in 2008, it was apparent that a new fundamental regulation was needed to strengthen the existing Basel II accord. Banks were suffering from high leverage, inadequate liquidity buffers, poor risk management, corporate governance failure, and inappropriately designed incentive packages (BCBS, 2016). As a response to the

above risk factors, it was evident that improvements were needed in Basel II to ensure flexibility of the financial market to increase public confidence in financial institutions and to increase supervision on banks' activities to ensure banks' future economic activities did not spill over to global economies (Angelkort and Stuwe, 2011)

In December 2010, BCBS introduced new international banking regulation known as Basel III to respond to the last financial crisis (BCBS, 2010). Basel III aimed to strengthen banks' solvency, stability, and liquidity without reducing money flow to the financial market (BCBS, 2010). To increase transparency, Basel III emphasised improving banks' risk management, capital structure, corporate governance, and disclosure requirements which BCBS stated as the key reasons for recent banking failure (BCBS, 2010).

Figure 2.2: The birth of Basel III (Magda, 2014).

While Basel II introduced significant changes in banks' capital accord, compared to Basel I, Basel III does not imply any substantial change in the capital accord. However, changes in Basel III is introduced to complement capital accords (BCBS, 2016). Furthermore, Basel III simplifies and strengthens the numerator of capital

ratio and adds a couple of macro-prudential components to the international banking regulation (BCBS, 2016).

2.2.3.1 Definition of Capital

Basel III significantly tightened the definition of capital, representing higher minimum capital requirements and a macro-prudential overhaul for banking regulation (BCBS, 2016). Furthermore, The Basel Committee and G20 leaders emphasised economic recovery from recession and BCBS (2010) stated that Basel III introduced the new banking regulation and definition of capital under Basel III. The total regulatory capital consists of Tier 1 capital and Tier 2 capital. Tier 1 capital is divided into (i) Common Equity Tier 1 capital (CET1) and (ii) additional Tier 1 capital. The changes in capital structure introduced by Basel III are as follows:

- *The minimum CET1 capital requirements increased to 4.5% from 4%.*
- *The minimum capital requirement raised to 10% from 8%, of which 6% must be Tier 1 capital.*
- *Basel III introduced two capital buffers; CCB (2.5% of CET1) and Countercyclical Buffer (0% to 2.5% depending on the supervisor's discretion).*

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Minimum Common Equity Tier-1(CET-1) Capital Ratio	4.00%	4.50%	4.50%	4.50%	4.50%	4.50%
Capital Conservation Buffer	-	-	0.63%	1.25%	1.88%	2.50%
Minimum CET-1 plus Capital Conservation Ratio	4.00%	4.50%	5.13%	5.75%	6.38%	7.00%
Minimum T-1 Capital Ratio	5.00%	5.50%	5.50%	6.00%	6.00%	6.00%
Minimum Total Capital Ratio	10.00%	10.00%	10.00%	10.00%	10.00%	10.00%
Minimum Total Capital plus Capital Conservation Buffer	10.00%	10.00%	10.63%	11.25%	11.88%	12.50%

Table 2.3 Basel III capital requirement and implementation timeline, Bangladesh (Bangladesh Bank, 2014)

2.2.3.2 Tier 1 Capital

Tier 1 capital is sub-divided into CET1 and additional Tier 1 capital. CET1 consists of common equity, share premium, retained earnings, other disclosed incomes, and reserves. Additional Tier 1 capital includes instruments issued to meet CET1 criteria but not included in CET1, such as common share issued by subsidiaries, minority interest, etc.

2.2.3.3 Tier 2 Capital

Tier 2 capital consists of instruments issued by the Bank to meet criteria for Tier 2 capital but not included in Tier 1 capital, such as subordinated debt, instruments issued by consolidated subsidiaries of the banks and held by third parties, etc. (BCBS, 2010). Under Basel II, Tier 2 capital consists of undisclosed reserves, revaluation reserves, general provision, hybrid debt capital instruments, subordinated debt (IBM, 2018).

2.2.3.4 Capital Conservation Buffer (CCB)

Basel III introduced CCB to ensure that banks build up capital buffer during the period of little or no stress to ensure that banks' capital does not fall below minimum capital requirement during the stress period (BCBS, 2010). CCB must be made of CET1 and should be 2.5% of RWA on top of their minimum capital requirement which raised the minimum regulatory capital requirement to 12.5% of RWA at the end of the Basel III implementation period. Capital conservation buffer is designed to absorb banks' losses during distress time (IBM, 2018).

Figure 2.4: Basel III capital requirement (Magda, 2014)

2.2.3.5 Countercyclical Capital Buffer

Countercyclical Capital Buffer (CCB) serves as an extension to the capital conservation buffer, a discretionary capital ranging from 0% to 2.5% as decided by the national supervisor. CCB must be made of common equity or other loss-absorbing capital agreed by the national supervisor and must raise during the period of excess credit growth (IBM, 2018).

2.2.3.6 The Leverage Ratio

A higher leverage ratio was stated as one of the underlying reasons behind the recent financial crisis (Magda, 2014). BCBS (2010) said that excessive on and off-balance sheet leverage in the banking system led to financial distress in 2008. Under Basel III, the leverage ratio is calculated similarly across jurisdictions and can be adjusted for different accounting standards worldwide (BCBS, 2010). The leverage ratio is calculated by dividing Tier 1 capital by the Bank's average total consolidated assets. Banks are expected to maintain a leverage ratio of 3%, but it can change depending on the country's jurisdiction and accounting standard (BCBS, 2010).

2.2.3.7 The risk-weighted assets (RWA)

RWA is an asset classification system that is used to define the minimum capital requirement. Under Basel III, RWA defines the minimum capital requirement that a bank should keep as a reserve to reduce insolvency risk (BCBS, 2010). Banks are exposed to danger from lending default and investment devaluation. Maintaining a minimum capital based on RWA helps banks mitigate those risks from lending default and investment devaluations.

Banks held different categories of asset which carries different risk weights. Basel III RWA minimum capital requirement allows banks to adjust the risk associated with their assets and discount lower-risk assets. For example, SME lending has a higher risk of weight compared to government bonds. As a result, banks who want to maintain a lower level of RWA need to hold more government bonds than lending to SME's.

2.2.3.8 Value at risk

Value at Risk (VaR) probably the most prevalent risk measure among financial institutions around the world. VaR is the market risk measure suggested by Basel II and Basel III accord. In particular, 99% VaR is the loss that is likely to be exceeded only 1% of the time, and banks worldwide use VaR to estimate the probable loss in an investment in a given time. Specifically, VaR is used to measure the potential loss in a portfolio's value over a specific period (Sharma, 2012). According to BCBS (2011), Basel III prescribed minimum capital requirements in line with their levels of credit, market, and operational risks and financial organisations use VaR to measure and control the level of risk exposure.

Although VaR is a widely used risk measure among financial institutions, it was criticised for its inability to measure worst-case loss. For example, if 99% VaR means a 1% probability, a portfolio's loss is estimated to be greater than the VaR amount. However, the VaR estimate does not indicate the parameter of losses within 1% trading days or the size of a maximum possible loss. Furthermore, according to Sharma (2012), VaR gets complex while applied to more extensive portfolios. Banks use VaR to measure volatility and return of individual assets and a possible correlation between them. Sharma (2012) stated that as banks use diversified financial instruments and positions in the portfolio, it gets complicated and costly for banks to calculate VaR for more extensive portfolios.

BCBS (2010) stated that a substantial capital requirement is necessary for stability in the banking sector, but significant capital alone cannot sufficiently ensure its stability. According to BCBS (2010), a robust liquidity ratio provides a strict supervisory review, which is as essential as a strong capital structure to ensure the global banking sector's stability. Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR), introduced by Basel III, is intended to promote elasticity to possible liquidity interruption over the thirty-day horizon (BCBS, 2010). LCR should also ensure that a bank has adequate unencumbered and good quality liquid assets to balance net cash outflow during short-term financial distress. Net Stable Funding Ratio(NSFR) promotes elasticity over the long-term by generating more incentives for banks to fund their activities with more steady funding sources on a continuing structural basis (IBM, 2018).

2.3 Impact of Basel III on banks

It is difficult to predict how BCBs will behave after the full implementation of Basel III. However, it is evident from history that banks exposed to new regulations tend to seek loopholes to reduce the financial impact. Therefore, until BCBs implement Basel III in full, it is difficult for BCBs to identify an alternative and innovative way to continue compliance with Basel III. Although Bangladesh Bank provided a five-year timeline for Basel III's gradual adoption, some BCBs may still find it challenging to implement Basel III properly.

2.3.1 Financial Stability

The most popular argument for the proposed Basel III regulation is that it will enhance banks' financial stability. It was argued that Basel III would improve banks' financial stability by minimizing the probability of banks' financial distress and by reducing banks' losses (Martynova, 2015). Research by Bank for International Settlement (BIS) suggests that Basel III will prepare banks well against future financial distress (BIS, 2010). However, concerns have been raised that Basel III may push banks to take strategies that might have negative impacts on the economy (MAG, 2010). For example, suppose banks choose to raise the lending cost to accommodate a higher capital requirement. It will lift borrowing cost which most likely will limit the Bangladeshi private sector's access to debt-finance. Therefore, Basel III may increase financial stability but can also work as a barrier to economic development.

2.3.2 Profitability

Banks around the world operate in a highly regulated market. BCBS (2011) stated that Basel III's impact on the global banking sector would be significant. BCBS (2011) also added that banks could implausible to offset Basel III's impact on their profitability. In 2011, BCBS (2011b) predicted that the return on equity (ROE) of an average European bank would be declined by 3% in 2013 and a further 2.1% by 2016. BCBS also predicted that European banks needed over €1.1 trillion additional Tier 1 capital alone by 2019 to maintain required capital levels (BCBS, 2016b). Their analysis was based on the most recent balance sheet of 45 top European banks. Another way of looking at Basel III's effect on banks' profitability is to look at the market perception of banking regulation.

Eyssell and Arshandi (1990) and Madura and Zarruk (1993) studied banking regulation's market behaviour on banks' share price by analyzing share price before and after the regulatory announcement. They found that new code and banks' share price is correlated, and new banking regulation adversely affects banks' share price, reflecting on banks' profitability. Furthermore, Madura and Zarruk (1993) also found that banks with deficient capital level compared to mandate levels of capital suffered enormous relative losses. Further research in this area by Wagster (1996) reported shareholders wealth gain due to regulatory change. His research was based on

share price collected from seven developed countries international banks and observed those banks share price reaction to eighteen regulatory announcements, including Basel I accord from 1985 to 1990. Wagster (1996) found that banks from all countries studied experienced significant wealth gain for some events. Still, only the Japanese bank shareholders experienced a positive cumulative wealth gain from all eighteen events because of Japanese banks' higher capital holdings.

Further research in this area suggests that the regulatory capital requirement and banks profits are correlated. Beltratti and Stultz (2009) studied the relationship between banking regulation, banking governance, banks' balance sheet characteristics, and banks' profitability. They found that those banks that experienced the most extensive returns before the financial crisis experienced the most significant losses during the crisis. Banks with higher Tier 1 capital managed well during the crisis period and experienced fewer losses. This research finding was also supported by Xiao (2009) who found that banks that had higher Tier 1 capital before the financial crisis incurred fewer losses and gained higher returns during the financial crisis.

Interestingly, researchers have also found no relationship between pre-crisis higher capital level and performances during the crisis (Huang and Ratnovski, 2009). It was argued that well-capitalized banks took a more elevated risk before 2008 (Toader, 2014). Most banks that governments bailed out during the recession had less levered capital structure (GFSR, 2009) which means less levered capital structure did not stop banks from experiencing heavy losses.

2.3.3 Efficiency and effectiveness

It was argued that the service industry productivity is measured based on two key concepts which are efficiency and effectiveness (Sherman & Zhu, 2006). Efficiency is defined as the bank's capability to produce output with minimum input, while effectiveness is defined as the banks' ability to set a target and achieve its pre-determined goals and objectives (Sherman and Zhu, 2006; Chen et al, 2008). The efficiency and effectiveness of financial institution have been widely researched in the last few decades. Berger et al. (1993) stated that financial organisations efficiency is defined by improved profitability, volumes of the channelled fund, higher quality of service provided by the financial organisation at lower price and grater

safety by having a higher capital buffer for absorbing risks. Therefore, a financial organisation's efficiency determines how a financial organisation can maximise their profitability by minimising its costs. As a result, higher efficiency leads to higher profitability (Othman et al., 2016).

Measuring financial organisation's efficiency has become an important research area in recent years due to frequent changes in the regulatory and economic environment (Ahmad, Nawi and Aleng, 2013). According to Chen (2002), two methodological approaches have been developed in the existing literature for measuring banking sectors efficiency, the parametric approach also known as the econometric approach and the non-parametric approach also known as mathematical programming. In the existing literature, many researchers have investigated the technical efficiency of the banking industry using both data envelopment analysis (non-parametric approach) and stochastic frontier approach (parametric approach) (see Ferrier and Lovell, 1990; Pastor et al., 1997; Resti, 1997; Bauer et al., 1998; Berger et al., 2000; Altunbas et al., 2001; Maudos et al., 2002; Weill, 2004). Since the acceptance of data envelopment analysis and stochastic frontier approach fluctuates both in structure and implementation, empirical evidence indicates that both methods provide significantly different efficiency scores (Ahmad, Nawi and Aleng, 2013).

It was reasoned that the Basel accord had had a positive impact on banks' efficiency. Pasiouras, Tanna and Zoupoundis (2009) researched the effect of three pillars of Basel regulation on banks' efficiency. Based on the sample collected from 615 banks from 74 different countries, their research found that the code increased market discipline, which led to enhanced cost efficiency for banks. They suggested that Basel regulation positively impacts banks' efficiency but may harm banks' profitability. Firstly, the bank as a financial intermediary takes customer deposits as input and transform them into outputs such as mark-up transactions. Thus, regulatory capital flexibility is vital to perform efficient lending activities. Secondly, proportionating banks' capital requirements with risk-taking may affect banks' investment decisions, altering banks' profit levels and profit generation capabilities. Dietrich and Wanzenried (2011) examined the relationship between bank regulation and banks' profit efficiency. Based on financial data collected from 372 Swiss banks before and after the financial crisis, their research found that strict capital

requirement had an established negative impact on banks' profit. The main factors they consider in their study were operational efficiency, funding costs, lending growth, and banks' specific business models.

However, little is known about Basel's effect on the efficiency of South Asian banks. Empirical work of Basel regulation on banks' efficiency in the Asian context is minimal. The only known research found to the researcher's best knowledge in the existing literature is performed by Thangavelu and Findlay (2010). The authors researched Basel regulation and supervision on banks' efficiency based on financial data from 1994 to 2008. They found that higher supervisory control improved efficiency in the Southeast Asian region, although they didn't find any positive relationship between private monitoring and banks' efficiency

2.3.4 Risk-taking

Bank shareholders have limited liabilities and gain from a higher return while depositors have an implicit safety net (Baker and Wurgler, 2015). As depositors do not fairly value banks' asset risks either because of information asymmetry or their lack of skills on how to assess banks' asset risks, banks do not incorporate full asset losses which influence banks to take higher risks (Kane, 1989; Cole et al., 1995; Martynova, 2015). It was argued that higher regulatory capital requirement alerts shareholders towards downside risk which minimizes banks' appetite for taking the risk (Rochet, 1992). Martinez-Miera and Suarez (2014) investigated the macro-prudential role of banking regulation on banks' systematic risk-taking using a dynamic equilibrium model. Their research found that banks tend to select frequent risk exposure by safeguarding capital values and exchanging gains from risk shifting. They suggested that higher regulatory capital requirements can reduce systematic risk-taking in lending, reducing the cost and probability of banks' recurring crisis.

In the existing empirical research, it is evident that higher capital requirement decreases banks' RWA. Using extreme value theory, De Jonghe (2010) measured US banks' systematic risk appetites. He observed that higher capital requirements minimized banks' exposure to systematic risk. Miles, Yang, and Marcheggiano (2012) studied the relationship between leverage and equity beta. Their research using the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) suggests that Basel III's higher capital requirement can significantly minimize risk-taking and the probability of a banking

financial crisis. A recent study by Baker and Wurgler (2015) suggests that well-capitalized banks have lower idiosyncratic risk (asset risk) and beta risk (systematic risk). Their research-based on selected US banks 40 years of financial data suggest that Basel III capital requirement can reduce banks' risk-taking.

Further empirical research has been done in this area by Klomp and De Haan (2012). Using OECD countries' selected 200 banks' financial data and risk indicators, they found that higher capital requirements can minimize banks' capital and asset risks. They also observed a similar result in 2014 using financial data from emerging and developing countries' banks (Klomp and De Haan, 2014). The above research suggests that Basel III can control banks' risk-taking using higher minimum capital.

However, it can be reasoned that Basel III's capital increase may influence banks to take higher risks. Firstly, a higher capital requirement may lower profits, decreasing banks' investment values and potential future profits (Hellmann, Murdock, and Stiglitz, 2000). Secondly, lower investment value decreases shareholders' wealth, influencing banks to undertake high-risk investments for higher returns to increase shareholders' return. However, Repullo (2004) suggests that a high-risk, high-return strategy can weaken the higher capital requirement principle (Repullo, 2004). Blum and Hellwig (1995) also pointed out that the future probability of higher capital requirements may lead banks to take a higher risk today. Recent research by Martynova, Ratnovski, and Vlahu (2014) suggests that higher capital requirement increases banks' core banking activities' value and allows banks to attract new investment that they can use in high-risk investments higher return to increase profits.

Although the above empirical studies claimed strong connections between banks' risk-taking and higher capital requirement, the following empirical studies suggest no substantial relationship. For example, Barth, Caprio, and Levine (2004) researched the relationship between regulatory higher capital requirements, banks' risk appetite and banking crisis using a data sample collected from 107 countries' banks. Their research suggests that, although higher capital requirement reduces nonperforming loans, no strong connection was found between regulatory higher capital requirement and banks' risk-taking. A similar result was also suggested by

Demirgüç-Kunt and Detragiache (2011) who used financial data from 3000 banks from 86 different countries. They applied the Z score model and found that capital regulation doesn't strongly influence banks' risk takings. The Z-Score is developed by Edward Altman and uses businesses' profitability, solvency, liquidity, leverage and other activities to measure insolvency probability. The Altman Z-Score model is a numerical measurement used to predict a business's likelihood of going bankrupt (Altman, Iwanicz-Drozowska, Laitinen and Suvas, 2016).

From the above empirical and theoretical analysis, it is unclear whether Basel III will minimize banks' risk takings to reduce the probability of a future financial crisis. The above study clearly shows both positive and negative results. Furthermore, none of the above empirical research is based on Bangladeshi commercial banks. Therefore, how Bangladeshi commercial banks might behave because of higher capital requirements is yet to be investigated.

2.3.5 Capital Structure

2.3.5.1 Capital ratio

As mentioned earlier that Basel III has increased banks' capital requirement, compared to Basel II and, to meet the increased capital requirement specified by Basel III regulation, banks have two options a) to increase the numerator or b) to reduce the denominator. Banks minimum capital ratio is calculated using the following formula.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Basel Capital Ratio} &= \frac{\text{Capital}}{\text{Risk Weighted Assts}} \\ &= \frac{\text{Total Eligible Capital (Tier 1 + Tier 2)}}{\text{Assets (Crdit RWA + Market RWA + Operational RWA)}} \end{aligned}$$

Banks that have already met or exceeded required capital requirements do not need to follow the above two options. However, banks that are yet to meet the capital requirement indicated by Basel III can choose any of the above options. How they choose and respond to increased capital adequacy requirements depends on banks' internal target capital ratio.

2.3.5.2 Increase numerator

The numerator can be increased by either issuing new equity in the market or withholding dividend payments or bonuses (BCBS, 2010). However, raising equity capital by issuing new shares represents information asymmetry because managers have more information about the company than new shareholders (Vale, 2011). Information asymmetry is essential because new equity dilutes share values. As a result, if new shareholders want to sell their equity, they must sell their shares at an undervalued price. Information asymmetry also raises another problem known as “*The Lemons Problem*” in the financial market terminology. The lemon problem is caused by information asymmetry between two parties when one party has more information (Vale, 2011). George Akerlof (1970) stated that information asymmetry between buyer and seller in a market could degrade the quality of goods traded, leaving the only lemon behind. In an American context, a lemon is a car that is found defective after it is bought due to information asymmetry between buyer and seller.

Moreover, overvalued banks have the strongest motivation for issuing new equity to raise numerators, sending a negative signal to the capital market (Vale, 2011). One positive sign of issuing new equity to increase numerator is that market participants know about regulatory change which means issuing new shares to increase numerator may not necessarily send a negative signal to the market.

2.3.5.3 Reduce denominator

Because of capital market resistance regarding new shares and the lack of popularity of withholding dividend payments and bonuses among shareholders, many banks prefer to reduce their denominator rather than increasing their numerator. Decreasing the denominator to raise the capital ratio involves adjusting assets' composition (Jackson et al., 1999). It means that banks either need to reduce their fixed assets or move to less risky asset portfolios rather than issuing new equity or stopping dividends to shareholders. The denominator can be reduced as follows:

2.3.5.4 Reducing assets

Banks' monetary policy is known as the transmission mechanism and works through several channels (Loayza and Schmidt-Hebbel, 2002). Generally, banks have three standard channels that control transmission mechanisms: demand, currency, and expectation. However, recently there has been a debate as to whether there is an

additional channel to the above three standard media that may explain the reduction in credit. Bernanke and Blinder (1988) first discussed the effect of monetary policy on banks' lending channel and their impact on banks' credit supply. Bernanke and Blinder (1988) stated that banks lending channel is a part of the credit channel that deals with the monetary policy on personal and commercial loans due to information asymmetry. Bernanke and Blinder (1988) suggested that to compensate for information asymmetry, and banks apply extra financing premium.

Moreover, banks' lending channels deal with all the additional costs associated with banks' borrowings, affecting both lending practice and interest rates on lending. It was argued that when banks' cost of funding increases, it may reduce credit supply (Jacobsen, 2012). To what extent this reduction of credit supply might affect SMEs, we will discuss in the result chapter.

Because of the simplified assumption made by Bernanke and Blinder (1988), there have been numerous discussions in the existing literature regarding the existence and effect of banks' lending channels. However, only a handful of empirical studies carried out in this field have found evidence of the presence of such an outcome. Jiménez et al. (2010) investigated the impact of banks' lending channels on banks' credit supply. Their research found evidence that banks' lending channel causes changes in credit supply rather than loan demand or quality. They also found that banks with higher capital ratios are more willing to lend than banks with low capital ratios. Their finding suggests that banks that are just meeting the regulatory capital requirement or close to the capital requirement may prefer to reduce their lending rather than issuing new equity to reduce their denominator. If this is the situation, banks may be willing to reduce their high-risk lending rather than their less risky lending.

2.3.5.5 Changing balance sheet structure

According to Furfin (2000), to explain changes in banks' portfolios, the capital requirement is a critical component to consider. A rise in the capital ratio can simultaneously explain a decline in lending which brings us to a logical assumption that there is a strong connection between banks' balance sheet structure and capital requirements (Furfin, 2000). Therefore, to increase regulatory capital, banks' may prefer to acquire assets with lower risk-weights and substitute risky investments with

less risky assets (Jackson et al., 1999). Therefore, it is logical to assume that banks will prefer to lend to high-rated SME's due to their low-risk weight rather than poor rated SME's who attract higher risk weight. Although lending to SME's may incur more funding cost for banks, SME lending secured by high-value collateral to high-rated SMEs can reduce banks' capital requirements because of their lower risk weight. It can work as a motivational factor for banks to include higher rated SME's in their loan portfolios and ignore low rated SME's. The above may explain why Bangladeshi commercial banks may prefer to lend to high-rated SME's (Please see result chapter).

However, shifting to low-risk assets from high-risk assets will result in lower average investment. In this situation, banks may use regulatory arbitrage opportunities to change their book profile (Furfin, 2000). Regulatory arbitrage is defined as banks' effort to keep funding costs minimum (Petitjean, 2013). Jackson (1999) stated that capital arbitrage uses the eccentricity in the real economic risk and the measure of trouble in the regulatory framework. If the capital requirement stated by Basel III exceeds banks' voluntary capital level, banks may prefer to view the excess capital requirement as a regulatory tax (Petitjean, 2013). Petitjean (2013) argued that this taxation motivates banks to do financial innovation, i.e. an alternative way to raise capital or cut the cost of funding. Therefore, Basel III tried to reduce capital arbitrage opportunities by increasing the capital requirement to check the leverage ratio and complex risk management measures to ensure monitoring. Although regulators introduce complex and more stringent regulatory requirements to discourage risk-taking and keep similar standards throughout the industry, the complex regulatory requirement may create loopholes that were evident after Basel II's implementation. Basel II gave banks the freedom to develop and use their risk management model and determine their capital requirement, which many banks abused globally.

2.3.6 Risk Management

Risk is an integral part of human life and risk-related activities are most predominant in the financial sector (Raghavan, 2003). Due to the nature of banking sectors' activities, banks are generally exposed to credit, operational and market risks. These risks are asymmetric to banks and arise from the probability of a transaction ending in a positive or negative outcome to the bank (Raghavan, 2003). Therefore, to achieve a positive result from a trade, banks are generally expected to manage their

risk factors efficiently to reduce the probability of losses and increase the likelihood of maximum profits (Pandy, 2004). As a result, risk management has been a core function of every financial organization. Risk management involves discovering, measuring, monitoring, and regulating the financial organisation's risks (Mensah, 2014).

2.3.6.1 Credit Risk

Based on different services provided by banks around the world, credit risk is the most prominent systematic risk to which all banks' are exposed to. Credit risk is defined as the probability of a borrower's inability to settle its financial requirement with banks in either the long term or the short term (Agyekum, 2011). The main objective of credit risk management is to reduce the probability of non-performing loans (NPL) and to maximize banks' profit as well as banks' risk-adjusted rate of return (RAROR) by predicting and maintaining banks' credit risk exposure according to banks' or regulators' given benchmark level (Mensah, 2014). The RAROR measures the return an investor will get back from his investment relative to the initial investment risk. The NPL is defined as a loan that is in default or close to being the default. An NPL occurred when the borrower failed to make scheduled repayment for a given period (Klein, 2013).

Ekrami and Rahman (2009) stated that a high NPL number leads to higher credit risk and increases banks' market and liquidity risks. Morton (2003) argued that NPL is caused by weak credit evaluation criteria and ineffective risk acceptance policies. One of the earliest studies that examined the relationship between credit risk management and NPL was conducted by Keeton and Morris (1987). They examined loss data from 2,470 insured commercial banks in the USA from 1979 to 1985. Using the NPL net of charge-offs as the primary measure of the losses, they found that US commercial banks with higher risk appetite recorded higher NPL losses. Keeton and Morris (1987) suggested that risk appetite and NPL losses are related and, to reduce the number of NPL, they indicated that banks should control their risk appetite. Several studies which followed Keeton and Morris (1987) have proposed either similar or other explanations behind non-performing losses. Haneef et al. (2012) suggested that banks' risk management system's weaknesses gave rise to the number of non-performing loans and reduced banks profitability. Ahmed (2006)

reported that non-performing loans in Bangladesh are influenced by three major factors, i.e. loan credit terms, banks' risk preference, and microeconomic shocks.

It is evident from the above analysis; credit risk management has greater importance in managing banks' losses. Credit risk management ensures that loans are given on reasonable terms and it can reduce banks' potential losses by reducing the number of NPLs.

5.3.6.2 Market risk

Market risk is defined as the probability of losses or gains in earnings due to variation or changes in the market variables such as interest/exchange/bond rates, commodity/equity prices, etc. (ACCA, 2011). Casu, Girardone, and Molyneus(2006) stated that Market risk is vital for banks because it affects banks' off-balance-sheet position because of market variables' movements. Therefore, banks must maintain effective and efficient market risk management policies to ensure useful and comprehensive information to measure, monitor and mitigate market risks (Mensah, 2014).

5.3.6.3 Operational risk

Wilson (1997) defined operational risk as the potential losses resulting from the failure or lack of systems such as internal control, human error, or external events that are not covered by credit or market risk. The area of operational risk is so vast that Raghvan (2003) suggested that the actual causes of most financial scams in history and some of the credit and market risks are caused by operational risk management failure. To mitigate operational risks, regulators often bring changes and advise banks to strengthen their internal control and internal audit.

Figure 2.5: Banks risk management framework Source: Deloitte (2015)

2.3.7 Risk management and Basel III

Financial institutions always acted as a channel on behalf of their clients in investing their excess funds whenever required (Schweder, 2011). However, potential bank losses from different risks and weaknesses in the existing risk management system transformed those losses into the financial crisis. Many large banks were required to be bailed out by their respective governments. The financial crisis pushed international regulators to develop stricter global financial regulation, especially in the capital requirement and risk management areas (Schweder, 2011). BCBS introduced Basel III to address three fundamental reforms in the banking industry a) Capital reform, b) short-term liquidity reform c) improve financial stability (KPMG, 2011).

To reduce bank losses and safeguard banks' capital, Basel III introduced a strict risk management framework that defines and provides a precise mechanism to manage risks (KPMG, 2011). However, the provisions introduced by Basel III to strengthen banks' risk management structure are also connected to banks' capital requirements as well as lending. To improve banks' liquidity and prevent a liquidity crisis, Basel III introduced a 30 days liquidity coverage ratio to strengthen banks' short-term liquidity

and promote stability (BCBS, 2010). Moreover, Basel III increased the minimum capital requirement from 8% to 10.5% to mitigate credit risks. Considering banks' capital inadequacy, which was blamed for the recent financial crisis, the Basel III framework proposed that banks' total assets should not exceed their capital by more than 33 times (KPMG, 2011).

Janson (2009) viewed the Basel III changes as positive because they would strengthen banks' capital base. However, Janson (2009) argued that some specific capital charges, such as capital charge specifically for Credit Value Adjustment (CVA) risk, are most likely to harm bank lending because banks may reject loans to the high-risk counterparty. Research by Cebenoyan and Strahan(2004) suggests that banks with better risk management systems have more outstanding capabilities to manage credit risks. They also stated that those banks are most likely to operate with greater leverage and tend to lend more to high-risk borrowers. Cebenoyan and Strahan(2004) claimed that advanced risk management systems might lead to greater credit availability than reducing risks in the banking industry.

2.3.8 Impact of Basel III on lending

Banks' capital works as a buffer against losses (BCBS, 2010). The implementation of Basel accords (Basel I, II and III) generated much literature that concentrated on Basel's consequence on banks' behaviour, specifically on the relationship between regulatory capital requirements, capital ratio, and banks' lending behaviour. As Basel III is relatively new, compared to its previous version, existing literature relates more to Basel I and Basel II than to Basel III. However, the researcher considers the following literature as valid and can indicate Basel III's impact on banks' lending. The empirical literature on the effect of regulatory capital requirement on banks' lending can be divided into two streams.

The first empirical literature stream focuses on Basel I. Majority of the related research in this area was carried out to examine Basel I's impact on credit supply to the macro-economy. Much of the existing literature in this stream examined whether the slow recovery of the U.S.A economy from the 1990-1991 recession resulted from Basel I adoption and whether Basel I had obstructed banks' lending activities and acted as a bottleneck to economic growth. Bernanke and Lown (1991) examined the relationship between capital requirement and credit supply using a regression model

that linked banks' credit supply with banks' capital ratios. They found that banks' credit supply was positively related to banks' capital ratios between 1990: Q2 and 1991: Q1. However, Naceur and Roulet (2017) noted that the economic environment's impact more significantly impacted banks' credit supply than banks' capital. These findings suggest that data used by Bernanke and Lown (1991) in their research was collected just before the US credit crunch in the first quarter of 1991. Therefore, their research result may not represent an actual relationship between credit supply and capital requirement.

Berger and Udell (1994) provided some evidence of why banks' credit supply was reduced in the early 1990s, which might have caused the American credit crunch. According to Berger and Udell (1994), Basel I required commercial banks to hold capital in proportion to their asset risks. Berger and Udell (1994) argued that capital is more expensive to raise compared to deposits. As a result, commercial banks might have viewed RWA capital as a regulatory tax under Basel I. Therefore; they assume that implementing risk-based capital (Basel I) inspired banks to substitute assets that are in the 100% risk category to 0% or less risky risk categories such as treasury securities. Using the above assumption, Berger and Udell (1994) explained that the reason behind significant reduction in credit to commercial borrowers by banks might have been caused by banks' risk-shifting approach rather than Basel I capital requirement, which caused a credit crunch. Consistent with Berger and Udell (1994), Naceur and Roulet(2017) also stated that in the early '90s, U.S. commercial banks reduced credits to commercial borrowers and increased their treasury holdings.

The above research suggests that banks may shift their investment from high-risk high-return to low-risk lower-return investment to substitute capital increase if regulatory capital requirement goes up. The above result can also explain how regulatory capital requirement may affect banks' credit supply to high-risk borrowers. Furthermore, it was also evident that weakened economic condition may also influence banks to reduce their credit supply.

The second literature stream investigated the role of regulatory capital requirement capital on banks' lending activities. Several articles appeared in this area in the early 2000s. The influence of bank capital was considered as the key determinant to the

extension of lending. Empirical literature in this area also focused on the extant role of banks' capital requirements on banks' lending activities (Kishan and Opiela, 2000; Gambacorta and Mistrulli, 2004; Berrospide and Edge, 2010; Beatty and Liao, 2011; Carlson et al., 2013; Bridges et al., 2014; Labonne and Lame 2014; Olszak et al., 2014; Kosak et al., 2015).

Kishan and Opiela (2000) examined banks' loan supply shifts for the period from 1980 to 1995 in the USA by isolating banks according to their asset size and capital leverage ratio. They found that the lending growth of capitalized and undercapitalized banks was significantly affected by Basel I higher capital requirement. However, most recent research in this area suggests that well-capitalized banks are more efficient than undercapitalized banks in managing their lending even during the recession. Using Italian banks' data from 2007-2009, Albertazzi and Marchetti (2010) found evidence that suggests that reduction in banks' lending is positively related to undercapitalization. Research by Kapan and Minoiu (2013) also presented similar findings. They used 800 banks' financial data from 55 countries during 2006-2010. They found that banks' capital worked as a bumper against losses, and well-capitalized banks' lending was reduced less than undercapitalized banks where both were subject to financial distress.

The above literature suggests that banks' lending stream depends on banks' capital level and higher capital requirement, which has a similar effect on both undercapitalized and well-capitalized banks. However, well-capitalized banks managed their lending better compared to undercapitalized banks. Therefore, it is evident that banks' lending activities are directly connected to their capital level.

Gambacorta and Mistrulli (2004) examined the role of bank capital on lending. Their research was based on Italian banks' samples, which indicate that bank capital circulates different types of shocks to lending caused by regulatory capital constraints and market imperfections. Berrospide and Edge (2010) used simple empirical relations between collective commercial-bank assets and leverage growth to examine the role of capital on lending. They found that the regulatory capital requirement has a negligible effect on lending growth. Beatty and Liao (2011) argued that when regulatory capital requirement increases, banks tend to reduce lending and vice versa. Bridges et al. (2014) studied the effect of regulatory capital

requirement on banks' capital ratios and bank lending in the UK from 1990-2011. They found that capital requirement affects lending with mixed responses in different sectors of the economy, i.e. banks employed more lending cuts in unsecured lending than secured lending. Labonne and Lame (2014) examined the sensitivity of lending with banks' capital ratio and the French banking sector's regulatory capital requirement from 2003 to 2011. They found that the elasticity of lending to capital depends on the concentration of the supervisory capital requirement. They suggested that banks with more significant regulatory capital constraints have slower lending growth than unconstrained banks.

Olszak et al. (2014) investigated the impact of bank capital ratios on loan supply in the EU. They found that banks with more procyclical loan loss provisions are more sensitive to capital ratios and their sensitivity slightly increases during contractions. They also found that more limited capital regulation and stringent supervision minimize the scale of the effect of banks' capital ratio on banks' lending. Therefore, they conclude that capital ratios are an essential factor that affects lending in large EU banks.

Researchers have found both positive and negative results between higher capital and credit supply during recession periods. It was argued that if banks' assets value fall extensively, high capital works as a safeguard that ensures banks can absorb incurred losses (Dewatripont and Jean, 1996). Kosak et al. (2015) analysed the role of bank capital and determinants of banks' lending behaviour during the credit crunch period using a worldwide bank sample from 2000 to 2010. They found that banks' funding strategy (Tier 1 capital), high-quality capital and government's financial backing were crucial factors for banks to continue lending during the credit crunch period. They also suggested that, although Tier 2 capital did not support lending activities during the credit crunch period, it can be an essential factor to facilitate lending during a regular period. Their research suggests that high-quality capital is a competitive strength during the credit crunch period for survival. Carlson et al. (2013) examined the impact of bank capital on lending by comparing lending growth differences with differences in capital ratios on several banks that are matched based on geographic area and the size and various business characteristics. Based on data from 2001 to 2011, their research found that the relationship between capital requirement and lending was only significant during the

credit crunch and shortly after the credit crunch period but not all the time. Their research also suggests that the relationship between capital requirement and banks' lending growth is more robust for those banks whose lending portfolios were shrinking compared to those whose lending portfolio was expanding.

The above empirical research provides mixed results. From the above discussion, it is evident that some researchers found higher capital requirements put pressure on banks' financial mechanism and negatively affected lending. This research also suggests that higher regulatory capital may keep banks' credit availability steady and reduce financial fragilities even during a crisis period. It is also evident that capital ratio alone is not always significant in determining banks' lending stream but, when significant, can have both positive and negative impact on banks' lending depending on the bank's holding of the capital level. One possible reason behind the differences in finding can be explained by the heterogeneity of the sample used by researchers, e.g. bank type such as publicly-traded, commercial banks, or simply because of demographic differences or perhaps the different methods used by other authors in their research. Moreover, none of the above analysis was based on Basel III's impact in the Bangladeshi context. Therefore, the researcher expected that this research in the Bangladeshi context could work as a benchmark for future Basel III research.

2.3.9 Impact of Liquidity on Banks' Lending

Following the financial crisis in 2008, BCBS developed a framework for liquidity assessment alongside strict capital requirement to improve banks' liquidity management and stabilities (BCBS, 2010). Basel III requires banks to maintain regulatory leverage ratio along with risk-weighted capital ratios. Thus, banks need to modify their balance sheet structure to improve their asset liquidity and funding stabilities. Naceur and Roulet (2017) claimed that Basel III liquidity requirement most likely will affect banks' broad area of operations, notably their credit-related activities.

In the empirical literature, liquidity variables were widely used along with bank capital as bank lending determinants (Alper et al., 2012). Cornett et al. (2011) studied how banks manage liquidity shocks during a crisis, specifically how they manage their holding of cash and other liquid assets and to what extent their efforts to manage liquidity affect loan supply. Their study found that banks that were highly dependent on stable financing source, i.e. on core deposit and equity finance, had relatively

higher lending than other banks during the financial crisis (2007-2009). On the other hand, banks with more illiquid assets in their balance sheets during the crisis reduced lending to improve their liquidity. They claim that banks' effort to manage liquidity leads to a decline in lending. Allen and Paligorova(2015) studied the effect of liquidity crunch on banks' borrowing towards private and public companies. Their finding suggests that banks tackle liquidity shocks by reducing lending to certain types of borrower. They indicated that banks' liquidity shocks were passed to public companies rather than private companies during the crisis period.

Berger and Bouwman(2009) stated that with easy monetary policy and low interest on government bonds, loan spread becomes weaker because of higher risk premium. In contrast, Naceur and Roulet (2017) stated that under the deteriorated economic condition and financial crisis, strict regulatory liquidity requirements reduce banks' credit supply and push banks to shrink their fixed/semi-liquid asset holdings and increase banks' liquid assets holding. Naceur and Roulet (2017) argued that banks prefer to reduce their low return, risky and illiquid credit activities, and increase liquidity buffers of risk-free but low return government securities when the regulatory liquidity ratio rises. Naceur and Roulet (2017) also suggested that banks prefer to diversify their stable funding to other activities such as more liquid assets rather than financing private sectors to comply with the higher regulatory return. Their findings contradict research by Allen and Paligorova(2015), who stated that banks pass liquidity shocks to public companies rather than private companies. Furthermore, research finding by Naceur and Roulet (2017) has more significant importance because the last financial crisis has penalized banks with higher liquidity requirements introduced by Basel III. As a result, banks have faced tighter conditions in accessing private sector funding activities, which may securitize their lending to the private sector (Naceur and Roulet, 2017).

From the above discussion, it is evident that higher liquidity requirement shifts banks' lending activities from high risk private/public sector to low risk government bonds and securities to comply with higher liquidity requirement; and higher liquidity asset ratio may be related to lower lending.

2.3.10 Impact of capital structure on banks performance

Capital structure is defined as the form of finance through which an organization is financed. The relationship between banks' capital structure and performance has been extensively studied. In this research context, it is also essential to determine how BCBs' are meeting higher capital requirement imposed by Basel III and its possible impact on Bangladeshi commercial banks' performance.

2.3.10.1 Debt Financing

Tirole (2006) stated that debt finance could take many forms. The fundamental nature of debt is that the borrower must repay the borrowed amount within the agreed time frame and charges such as interest as decided during borrowing. However, suppose the borrowed amount is not refunded. In that case, as approved, the lender can start a collection procedure which can be uncomfortable for borrowers who can lose their business or any assets provided as collateral to secure the loan. Still, most companies prefer debt finance over equity finance because debt finance is cheaper, and the owner retains complete control of his/her business Tirole (2006). Furthermore, interest and other debt finance charges are tax-deductible, one of the significant debt financing incentives. Disadvantages include repayments need to be done on time, and regular repayment may affect cash flow and failing to repay the debt on time may destroy credit rating or lead to bankruptcy (Tirole, 2006).

2.3.10.2 Equity financing

Equity financing is the process of raising capital through the sale of equity share. This process is also known for raising money through the sale of ownership interest. One of the main benefits of equity finance is that the profits earned using this process can be fully reinvested in the business or paid out to the shareholders, unlike debt finance, where regular repayment is necessary. However, Tirole (2006) stated that equity finance is demanding, costly and may shift management's concentrations away from their main activities.

2.3.10.3 Impact of capital structure on profitability

Banks are the most regulated among all the financial institutions, and the financial sector is the most regulated in any given economy (Gropp and Heider, 2010). In any large organization, capital structure is comprised of equity and debt components, i.e. financed with both equity and debt. However, according to Berger, Herring and

Szegö (1995), banks differ from other traditional organizations in two aspects that affect their capital structure. (1) government safety nets guard the financial system's reliability and are likely to minimize banks' capital because they protect depositors from financial distress. (2) Regulatory capital requirements are aimed to increase banks' capital to control risk-taking. As a result, banks have higher leverage, making their capital structure different from other traditional organizations. Banks also have higher leverage because even though customer deposits are a liability, they do not require repayment according to a fixed schedule.

There have been many studies that have examined the relationship between capital structure and organizational performance. Modigliani and Miller (1958) stated that capital structure decisions do not influence the firm's value under perfect market conditions, but its elemental earning power solely determines an organization's value. However, later they proposed that, by taking the tax benefit of debt financing, the firm's value can be maximized by integrating more debt into the capital structure. They suggest that in a perfect market condition, the optimal capital structure should be made up of 100% debt (Modigliani and Miller, 1963). However, the assumption held by Modigliani and Miller in their theory, namely perfect market condition, doesn't exist in reality, which promoted the introduction of several approaches in this area, such as trade-off theory and pecking order theory. These theories aim to explain the determinants of the capital structure decision, given the assumption of shareholder-value maximisation.

Arbabian and Safari (2009) reported a significant positive relationship between capital structure and a firm's performance. They collected data from 100 firms from 2001 to 2007. Umar et al. (2012) collected data from 100 listed firms between 2006 and 2009. Their findings also suggest that there is a significant favourable influence of capital structure on firms' performances. Salteh et al. (2012) inspected the impact of capital structure decision taken by 28 firms from the Tehran stock exchange and noted the potential effect of capital structure decision on their performances. Nikoo (2015) also observed a significant positive impact of capital structure choice on banks' performance by employing data from 17 Iranian banks over five years.

However, many researchers have observed a negative relationship between the capital structure decision and organizational performance compared to the above

positive relationships. Ramadam and Ramadan (2015) analyzed the impact of capital structure decision of 72 Jordanian firms for the period from 2008 to 2012 and their potential impact on those firms' performances. Their analysis was based on both dependent and independent variables and found that capital structure decision was taken by management negatively affected those firms' financial accounts. Ramadan and Ramadam (2015) observed that relatively high debt ratio levels to equity in the capital structure generate lower returns on investment than higher equity presence in the capital structure. Similar research as above was carried out by Memon et al. (2012) on 141 Pakistani textile companies from 2004-2009. They analyzed the relationship between the capital structure decision and the firm's performances using the return on asset (ROA) as a performance indicator. They reported a negative association between ROA and total debt obligations to an absolute asset. In another study, Muritala (2012) examined the influence of leverage in the Nigerian firms' capital structure and its potential impact on firms' performance. His research was based on ten large Nigerian firms data gathered from 2006 to 2010 and observed that debt finance negatively influences the ROA. However, his study is weakened by having such a small sample size.

Salim and Yadav (2012) investigate the relationship between the capital structure decision and the firm's performance using multiple performance measures such as earning per share (EPS), ROA, return on equity (ROE). They have used data collected from 237 Malaysian companies from 1995 to 2011 and reported a significant negative influence of using debt finance on a firm's performance. Manawaduge et al. (2011) also found an inverse impact of leverage on a firm's profitability. Their research was based on 155 Sri Lankan-listed firms demonstrate that debt finance has a significant negative effect on firms performance. However, the study should have used a market-based measure of performance in addition to accounting-based standard (e.g. ROA, ROE) as market-based performance tends to reflect firms long-term or future performance.

To summarize, some researchers observed a positive relationship between capital structure decision and a firm's performances, while others reported a negative relationship. However, some studies reported no association between capital structure and a firm's financial performances.

Al-Taani (2013) studied the relationship between capital structure choice and Jordanian firms' profitability. Using data collected from 2005 to 2009, he reported no statistically significant relationship between return on asset and debt ratios. Ebaid (2009) also conducted similar research on 64 Egyptian firms on the data collected from 1997 to 2005. His regression analysis shows a weak to no relationship.

The banking sector plays a vital role in the economic acceleration process in Bangladesh, and as a result, the influence of capital structure decision on banks' performance has greater importance. Several studies carried out on the impact of capital structure decision on organizations' financial performances in the Bangladeshi context.

Safiuddin et al. (2015) used descriptive statistics to identify the influence of finance structure on financial and non-financial organisations operating in Bangladesh. They collected data from 40 firms from 2008 to 2012 and observed that leverage plays a crucial role in determining a firm's performances. However, their findings were criticized for using descriptive statistics and not using any model to explain the relationship (Siddik, Kabiraj, and Joghee, 2017). Moreover, their sample size is low enough to cause concern about the validity of the result. Hossain and Hossain (2015) used data collected from 74 Bangladeshi manufacturing companies from 2002 to 2011 and analysed it using a regression model. They observed a negative association between most dependent and independent variables and concluded that most Bangladeshi firms follow the trade-off theory and pecking order theory. Rouf (2015) performed similar research, but he employed ratio analysis rather than the regression model. Rouf (2015) collected data from 106 Bangladeshi manufacturing companies from 2008 to 2011 to investigate the impact of capital structure on its performance. He analyzed the manufacturing company's financial performance using the return on asset and return on sales (ROS) and observed a significant negative influence between the relationships. Chowdhury and Chowdhury (2010) studied the impact of capital structure on maximizing a firm's value. They collected data from 77 Bangladeshi non-financial organizations from 1994 to 2003 and observed that capital structure decision positively influences maximising the firm's value.

However, the above studies were carried out mainly on non-financial and manufacturing companies. The only research found so far on the impact of capital structure on banks' financial performance in Bangladesh was conducted by Siddik, Kabiraj, and Joghee (2017). Their research was carried out on 22 Bangladeshi commercial banks. They used dependent variables such as return on assets, return on equity, earning per share and independent variables such as short-term/long-term/total debt obligations to the entire investment as a performance indicator. Siddik, Kabiraj, and Joghee (2017) found that banks' capital structure choices have a significant negative impact on their financial performance. They suggested that financial managers should try to finance from retained earning first rather than using too much debt in their capital structure. However, they also mention that debt capital should be their last resort of finance. Siddik, Kabiraj, and Joghee (2017) suggested that to maximize Bangladeshi commercial banks' performances; bank managers should choose an optimal capital structure using internal sources first and move to external sources as a last resort performance boost. They recommended legislative reform to reduce Bangladeshi commercial banks' dependency on debt finance. However, the market-based measure of performance should also have been used to research a long-term performance indicator.

As mentioned earlier, it is challenging to determine Basel III's impact on banks as the above section has shown that there is no definitive answer. Therefore, how banks will behave because of Basel III is based on several factors such as banks' existing capital level, the economic situation of that specific country and perhaps just the size of the bank. Although theories can predict a possible outcome, they cannot guarantee an exact result. Despite uncertainty associated with Basel III's impact on banks, it is assumed that changes implied by Basel III on banks' capital structure, risk management policies, liquidity, etc., are going to have some impact on banks initially. However, how banks might react to Basel III depends on banks' initial financial positions.

2.4 SME's in Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, the definition of SME's is based on the number of employees employed by an enterprise. According to the *Bangladesh National Industrial Policy (BNIP) 2010*, any firm which employs more than 25 but less than 99 employees are called a small enterprise (depends on industry). On the other hand; businesses which employ over 99 to 249 employees are called medium-sized enterprise. Any enterprise employing less than 25 employees falls in the micro-enterprise category. BNIP (2010) stated that SME's play a significant role in poverty alleviation in Bangladesh, and they are expected to reduce unemployment rates by creating new jobs every year. According to the figures published by the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (2013), SME's have been the most active component of the manufacturing sector for the period from 2005 to 2011 and accounted for 4.5% of the country's total employment and 12.4% of GDP. In 2018, SME's accounted for 25% of Bangladesh GDP, and this number is most likely to increase if informal micro-enterprises are taken in to account (The Independent. 2018). Despite their fast growth and economic contribution towards GDP, the SME sector experienced several constraints which worked as a barrier to their development, such as lack of freehold land, weak and inadequate legal and government support and access to finance (Zaid, 2015).

2.4.1 Definition of SME

Like in many other countries, SME's in Bangladesh are defined by their employee number and asset size. Bangladesh Bank (2011) defined SMEs based on asset size, employees, and their industry. SMEs based on Small enterprise is solely owned and operated by owner(s) which can have an asset size between BDT 5 Lac to BDT 1000 Lac and 10 to 99 employees. The medium enterprise has more employees than a small enterprise but fewer employees than corporate organizations (typically from 99 to 250). Although medium enterprises usually have a more extensive asset base and more employees than small enterprises, the definition varies from country to country. Medium enterprises are expected to have an asset size between BDT 100 Lac to 3000 Lac, which depends on the industry it operates.

Medium Industry/Enterprise		
	Asset size (Lac)	Employees
Service/ Others Concern:	100 to 1500	50 to 100
Trading Concern	100 to 1500	50 to 100
Manufacturing Concern	1000 to 3000	100 to 250
Small Industry/Enterprise		
Service/ Others Concern:	5 to 100	10 to 25
Trading Concern	5 to 100	10 to 25
Manufacturing Concern	5 to 1000	25 to 99
Micro Industry/Enterprise		
Service/ Others Concern:	Less than 5	Less than 10
Trading Concern	Less than 5	Less than 10
Manufacturing Concern	5 to 50	10 to 24
Cottage Industry/Enterprise		
Family Concern	Less than 5	less than 10

Table 2.6: Definition of SME's in Bangladesh (Source: Bangladesh Bank, 2011)

2.4.2 Sources of SME finance in Bangladesh

2.4.2.1 Banking sector

According to Bangladesh Bank (2016), currently, 56 scheduled banks received their license under Banking Act 1991, 4 non-scheduled banks (a bank established for specific needs and objectives) and 31 non-bank financial institutes. In 2013, total loan granted to SME's were BDT 853,233 million (approximately \$102 million) which went up to 18.3% to BDT 1,009,102 million (approximately \$120 million) in 2014 (ADB, 2015). However, this figure went up by 42.63% in 2015 to BDT 1,758,940 million (approximately \$145 million) (Bangladesh Bank, 2016b). Bank and Non-Bank Financial Institutions (NBFIs) are still the primary credit provider to SME's. Bank lending accounted for 97.1%, and NBFIs made up 2.9% of total lending to the SME sector in 2014 (ADB, 2015). Due to the worldwide economic recession and unstable Bangladesh political environment, the number of NPLs went up from 2012 to 2014 (ADB, 2015). In 2012, the NPL rate was only 1.2% which grew to 7.9% in 2013 and an alarming 11.8% in 2014 (ADB, 2015).

Figure 2.7: Historical NPL rate (source: www.ceicdata.com)

BRAC Bank, the fourth largest specialized SME bank globally, is the largest SME lender among commercial banks in Bangladesh. In 2013, BRAC Bank distributed BDT 33,676 million to around 20,571 SME's and had a 6% market share (ADB, 2014). Most Bangladeshi banks divide SME customers into two segments which are secured and unsecured. Banks provide collateral-free loans and up to 75% of collateral value for unsecured loans for a secured component. Interest rates for secured loans vary from 16% to 18%, and for unsecured loans, interest rates can be as high as 23.5%. Bangladeshi SME lenders face several challenges while granting credits to SME's such as poor-quality collateral, lack of business plans and poor documentations from SME entrepreneurs.

2.4.2.2 Nonbank financial (NBFi) sources

NBFI sector in Bangladesh is significantly smaller than the banking sector. According to ADB (2014), commercial banks' SME lending grew by seven basis point in 2014 compared to 2013; NBFi's have seen only 2.9% growth in their total lending (p-126). Although NBFi's lending towards SME's has a slower growth rate than commercial banks, NBFi's offer some services such as factoring and lending, which banks do not. The Industrial Development and Leasing Corporation (IDLC) is the largest NBFi in Bangladesh, and as of 2014, SME lending was their most extensive investment portfolio among other IDLC loan portfolio. However, the main problem with NBFi's is that they are urban-centric and lack geographical coverage. Although urban SME's

are well served by NBFIs, the SME financing gap is more remarkable in semi-urban and rural areas.

2.4.2.3 Microfinance

Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) play an essential role in financing micro and small enterprises in Bangladesh. Regulated by Micro Credit Regulatory Authorities (MRA), both Government and Non-Government funded organisations (NGOs) play an essential role in financing micro and small enterprises in urban and rural areas. According to MRA (2016), currently, 685 registered MFIs and NGOs are operating throughout Bangladesh. MFI loans range from BDT 1000 to BDT 1 million. According to MRA (2015), loans below BDT 50000 are classified as microloans and loans between BDT 50,000 to BDT 1million are classified as micro-enterprise loans. However, MFIs are not allowed to take any collateral from borrowers and loans are granted based on group guarantees.

Furthermore, micro-enterprise loans are granted to those who have already successfully repaid microloans previously, which means there are few possibilities for new small enterprises to access these finance facilities unless the group guarantee is provided. MRA has set the maximum MFI interest rate to 27%. According to MRA (2015), the cumulative recovery rate of finance granted by MFIs stood at 97.7%. However, medium enterprises *are not allowed* to take loan facilities from MFIs.

2.4.2.4 Capital market

Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE) is the largest stock exchange in Bangladesh, followed by Chittagong Stock Exchange (CSE). The number of listed companies as of 2016 in DSE was 559 and in CSE was 427 (DSE, 2016; CSE, 2016). The minimum paid-up capital required for trading in both stock exchange is BDT 1 billion (approximately \$12,00,000), restricts SME's to access these markets. However, DSE operates an over-the-counter (OTC) market and only listed companies from the stock exchange can use this facility. OTC can be a potential source of finance for SME's as DSE is assessing the possibility to allow SME's which have a minimum capital of BDT 50 million to trade in the over the counter market.

2.4.2.5 *Venture capital market*

The idea of venture capital is new in Bangladesh, and venture capital firms struggle to raise funds because of the unregulated industry. Bangladeshi venture capital firms face several challenges when it comes to investing in SME's. Challenges include but not limited to failure to perform appropriate due diligence; entrepreneur's unwillingness to raise capital from the equity market; lack of quantitative and qualitative business information from SME's and various valuation opinions between SME and venture capital firms (ADB, 2014).

2.5 Impact of Basel III Regulation on SME Financing

BCBS understand the importance of SME's in rolling the wheel of a country's economic developments, which was evident from their various modifications made to Basel II to ensure that Basel II did not become too detrimental towards SME's to meet capital requirements for banks. Although BCBS altered formulas for calculating banks' regulatory capital requirements for SME's three times (BCBS, 2001; 2003; 2004), Basel II regulation increased risk premium, which banks compensated for by charging SME's. Cardone-Riportella and Trujillo-Ponce (2007) suggested that BCBS amendments for calculating capital requirements for SME's left them with their never-ending financial difficulties because the Basel II capital accord was more sensitive to risks. It is essential to know how Basel II affected SME's access to finance to understand how Basel III might affect SME's access to credit,

2.5.1 Basel II and capital requirements for SME's

Several studies found in the existing literature analyzed the impact of Basel III capital requirement on SME financing. Altman and Sabato (2005) investigated the effects of Basel II on banks' capital requirements. Using data collected from the USA, Italy, and Australia, they found if banks apply the internal ratings-based (IRB) approach for calculating regulatory capital requirement and treat SME's as retail customer, banks' profit margin goes up significantly even if they have lower capital requirements. Their observation suggests that banks' regulatory capital requirement goes up slightly if banks treat SME's as a corporate client rather than retail customers. Berger (2006) observed that if banks adopt the IRB approach for calculating their capital requirement, it does not significantly reduce the interest rate on credits granted to SME's. His investigation was based on those USA banks, which adopted the IRB

approach in calculating the capital requirement. Berger (2006) claimed that using the IRB approach might not reduce banks' interest rate to SME's but can significantly affect credit granted to small entities. However, Ruthenberg and Landskroner (2008) suggested that larger banks are expected to adopt the IRB approach and most likely to serve less risky customers because of lower risk.

On the other hand, smaller banks are expected to adopt the standardized approach because of its easy application. As a result, smaller banks tend to serve riskier borrowers, which makes them more dangerous themselves. BCB adopted the standardized method for calculating credit risk RWA under Basel II. Basel II assigned 75% standard risk weight on all SME loans for the standardized approach, increasing banks' RWA capital requirement. SME's could reduce their risk weight if their lending were secured by high-value collateral. Therefore, it is evident that under Basel II, the cost of lending to SME's for banks was dependent on two factors; the credit risk RWA method used by banks and the value of the collateral provided by SME.

2.5.2 Basel III and SME's

2.5.2.1 Impact assessment of Basel III on SME's

Although lending to SME's had little or no connection with the financial crisis (2007-2009), the economic slowdown and credit crunch that followed the recession hit SME's hard. BCBS (2010) stated Basel III is the recipe for mitigating and a way of avoiding future financial disaster; the effect of Basel III on lending towards SME's is assumed to be excessively negative (ACCA, 2011).

Since Basel III's introduction, several micro-economic estimates have been published regarding Basel III's possible impact on SME's. The Institute of International Finance (IIF) reported 3.2% SME business losses over five years (IIF, 2010). On the other hand, Basel Macroeconomic Assessment Group (MAG) reported 3.1% business losses over the four years (MAG 2010b). MAG (2010) stated that when assessing the impact of tighter regulatory capital on the supply of credit to the economy, it is vital to consider borrowers' ability and access to non-banking credit sources. In this case, bank dependent SME's may find it excessively difficult to obtain credit.

The factors that might affect the credit supply to SME's are difficult or impossible to quantify. Suppose tighter regulatory capital requirements lead financial institutions to a considerable cutback in lending to a specific sector such as SME's, which have a massive role in supporting economic growth. In this case, it is most likely to impact GDP adversely. The MAG (2010) has acknowledged the devastating effect of the Japanese credit crunch in the '90s resulted in the number of defaults, quadrupling in the late '90s compared to the early '90s. The MAG (2010) suggested that a more extended implementation period of Basel III may develop alternative non-bank lending channels for highly bank-dependent sectors such as SME's to reduce the impact of new regulation on lending. Although BCBS (2010) acknowledged that Basel III is most likely to impact commercial loans negatively, Ambler (2011) argued banks would reduce lending to SME's rather than corporations. Ambler (2011) suggested financial institutions are most likely to make the Basel III implementation period more affordable to them and minimize the impact of implementing Basel III on their ROE by reducing lending towards SME's.

Initial impact assessment of Basel III by IIF (2010) stated that regulatory change promotes discrimination in the banking system and biases credit flows from smaller entities to corporate entities that directly access the public securities market. Banks do it to reduce risk from their loan portfolios. According to IIF (2010), if banks' long-term debt liabilities or capital supply curves become inelastic, the banking system would face a sudden stop, i.e. banks would need to reduce their assets very quickly to support their working capital requirements. IIF (2010) further predicted that it would be very destructive for the economy if the above happens since banks would be forced to cut their short-term lending to support their working capital. In this case, banks will significantly cut lending to high-risk borrowers, such as lending to SME's. IIF (2010) 's arguments are logically consistent, representing a surprising agreement between banks and the regulators. According to ACCA (2010), SME's accounted for 50% of total private-sector output and approximately 63% of private sectors' employment globally, making SME's a leading indicator of GDP at the global level (Koellinger and Thurik, 2011). In many countries, SME's are the population that represents most of the growth and employment in that sector and demand most for external finance (ACCA, 2011). Even in the UK, 12% of SME's required 58% of total banks' finance (Rowlands et al., 2009). World Bank estimated that global SME loan

is outstanding at CA \$10 trillion (Ardic et al. 2011). Furthermore, SME's accounted for 46% of the RWA of international retail banks and 27% of their total banking incomes, which indicates the importance of SME's to lenders (Capgemini et al., 2010).

From the above discussion, organizations such as IIF and ACCA wrote impact assessment based on available information. However, it is also true that there is no proper way to assess the real impact of new regulation on SME's and the most detailed assessment can be widely off the mark and may represent misleading information. Therefore, policymakers must find a trade-off between financial stability gain and SME lending because the impact of regulatory reform to gain financial stability is likely to impact more severely on SME's than on larger corporate entities (Ardic et al., 2011). BCBS (2010b) stated that strong capital requirement and liquidity requirements are most likely to improve GDP and each-percentage point improvement in GDP reduces the probability of a financial crisis. Although substantial capital and liquidity requirement may improve GDP, SME's are more likely to rely on economic stability for their prosperity. Naturally, SME's are less likely to hedge their operations or finance against future financial losses than corporate companies (ACCA, 2011). Furthermore, research by Ayyagari et al. (2003) found a strong correlation between the contribution of SME's economic output and macroeconomic stability. Although Basel III capital and liquidity provision was introduced to protect banking industries from future financial distress, it is still unclear to what extent they symbolize an excellent trade-off between economic growth and financial stability (ACCA, 2011).

From the assessment report published by different financial authorities, policymakers have given little consideration to Basel III's economic impact on SME lending. However, the only clear indication of Basel III's impact on SME lending provided by assessment reports is that lending to SME's is more likely to be disproportionate to facilitate economic recovery from the financial crisis. While the SME sector produces approximately 50% of world private-sector output (ACCA, 2011), uncertainty associated with Basel III's impact on SME's makes all existing impact assessment problematic.

2.5.2.2 Basel III and capital requirement for SME's

According to Basel III, SME lending's RWA capital requirement will depend on the national supervisor's approach for calculating credit risk and SME's credit rating. Basel III offer Standardized Approach and Internal Rating Based (IRB) method for calculating credit risk, Standardized Measure Method for market risk, and the Basic Indicator Approach (BIA) and The Standardised Approach (TSA)for computing capital requirement for operational risk(Bangladesh Bank, 2014).

2.5.2.3 Risk-weighted asset

Generally, banks' assets include loans granted to borrowers such as individuals, business and governments, cash, securities, etc. Assets held by the bank have different risk characteristics. A risk weight is assigned to assets based on assets' risk characteristics to calculate total risk exposures by the bank's assets (BCBS, 2017). According to BCBS (2017), banks need less capital to cover risk exposure for safer investments and more capital to cover high-risk assets' risk exposures.

2.5.2.4 Credit Risk calculation methods

According to BCBS (2017), credit risk is the bank's risk of loss where the borrower cannot repay their debt in whole or in part. BCBS states two methods for credit risk calculation; the standardized approach and the IRB approach. Most banks around the world use the standardized approach for credit risk RWA calculation. According to BCBS (2010), banks that assigned a standardized approach must classify their risk exposure and assign weights based on credit rating given to SME's by national or external credit rating agency (BCBS, 2010). On the other hand, the IRB approach is based on banks' internal assessment that permits banks to calculate their credit risk capital requirement, which is more risk-sensitive (BCBS, 2010). To apply the IRB approach, banks need to calculate the probability of default (PD), requiring at least five years of historical data analysis (BCBS, 2010). Therefore, due to the historical data requirement, many SME's may find it challenging to meet banks' credit requirements for approving credits to SME's particularly those which have existed for only a few years.

According to the "Guidelines on Risk-Based Capital Adequacy", Bangladesh Bank (2014) has stated that all Bangladeshi schedule banks should use the standardized Approach for calculating credit risk. Under the Standardized Approach, SME's with a

higher credit rating is assigned less risk weight, generating less credit risk capital requirement for banks. The following table shows the Basel III credit rating and their relevant SME risk weight for credit risk calculation. According to the Basel III guideline, SME's will be assigned a risk weight from 20% to 150% based on their credit rating (see Table 2.8). However, unrated SME's can still seek finance. They will be assigned 75% risk weight for small enterprises less than BDT 3 million (approximately \$36K) yearly turnover and 100% risk weight for SME's with over BDT 3 million yearly turnovers. Credit rating provides a loophole for SME's with a bad credit rating as they can apply for a loan as unrated for less risk weight. On the other hand, corporate loans have been assigned a risk weight from 20% to 150% based on the credit rating.

According to Basel III, small enterprises will be assigned 75% risk weight given that bank's retail portfolio is diverse, and no loan exceeds BDT 100M (approximately \$130K) (Bangladesh Bank, 2014). However, if a bank doesn't meet the above condition, SME loans will be assigned 100% risk-weight compared to loans to governments and the central bank with a high credit rating, which will be given 0% risk weight. Consequently, the above risk weight will significantly impact banks' capital requirement, which is needed to offset small enterprises' loans.

Exposure Type	Bangladesh Bank's Rating Grade	Risk-Weights (%)
Corporate	1	20
	2	50
	3,4	100
	5,6	150
	Unrated	125
SME	SME1	20
	SME2	40
	SME3	60
	SME4	80
	SME5	120
	SME6	150
	Unrated (small Enterprise < BDT 3.00m)	75
	Unrated (small Enterprise having >_BDT3.00m & Medium Enterprise)	100

Table 2.8: SME's risk weight Source: Bangladesh Bank (2014).

For example, a bank grants a BDT 10k (approximately \$120) to an SME with a SME1 credit rating. This loan will generate BDT 2K (approximately \$24) RWA for banks ($10000 \times 20\%$ RW) and BDT 4k (approximately \$48) for SME2 rated SME ($10000 \times 40\%$ risk-weight). However, RWA exposure can be minimized by taking collateral values into account. In this situation, what if Bangladeshi commercial banks decide to finance SME's which have higher credit rating and ignore low credit-rated SME's to avoid higher risk-weighted capital requirement?

2.5.3 Negative effect of Basel III on SME's finance

There are significant policy concerns and debate about whether the new Basel III could adversely affect SME's access to finance. The tension between regulatory bodies and financial organizations increased during the last financial crisis when BCBS announced Basel III. BCBS has also announced that Basel III will decrease banks' leverage and increase the capital buffer to prevent future global economic disaster. Amable et al. (2002) stated that new banking regulations are a trade-off between higher standards that strengthen the banking system and costs that constrain credit allocation. Therefore, any new law's negative impact becomes prominent in the short-run, while positive aspects of banking regulation are long-run prospects.

According to Basel III, banks' capital requirement depends on the riskiness of lending and borrowers' credit rating. Naturally, relatively riskier borrowers will be the most affected by a new regulation that will affect banks' overall lending. Therefore, because of the higher risk weight involved in a capital requirement for riskier borrowers, they are most likely to experience the most damaging effect of regulatory requirement change as they demand more regulatory capital as well as increase liquid asset for banks (Bonino et al., 2011; Schizas, 2011; OECD, 2012). The above suggests that Basel III regulation may jeopardize SME's access to finance because SME's are relatively risky and rely upon banks' funding (OECD, 2012; Kremp and Sevestre, 2013). SME's dependence on bank finance is initiated by poor track record, collateral backed loan and regulatory environment/inappropriate legislation (OECD, 2012). As a result, the burden of higher regulatory capital requirement can be mostly felt by SME's. Bank-dependent borrowers can also benefit from a stable banking system through a better and secure financing system.

Moreover, it was argued that higher regulatory capital requirement might negatively impact banks' ability to lend, especially to SME's because of the higher risk associated with SME lending (BarbaNavaretti, Calzolari and Pozzolo, 2015). Several researchers also suggested that Basel III's capital restriction could negatively impact banks' lending conditions to SME's and increase finance costs for SME's (Admati et al., 2010; Miles, Yang, and Marcheggiano, 2012). Firstly, the capital requirement can work as a bottleneck to banks' capital as banks can't lend to SME's without increasing their capital ratio (see the formula in section 2.3.5.1), limiting banks' lending scopes to SME's (Admati et al., 2010). Secondly, a strict regulatory capital increase is most likely to increase financing costs for banks which is expected to be paid by borrowers such as SME owners (Miles, Yang, and Marcheggiano, 2012)

The above researchers argued that the Basel III capital requirement should reduce banks' ability to lend to SME's due to higher risk. However, using Modigliani and Miller (1959) theorem, researchers such as BarbaNavaretti, Calzolari and Pozzolo (2015) and Admati and Hellwig (2014) argued, banks' capital structure is irrelevant and meeting Basel III capital requirement should not cause too many problems for banks and their lending to SME's. On the contrary, researchers such as Beck (2015), Clerc (2015) and Rochet (2015) disagreed with Modigliani and Miller (1959) theorem. They suggested that because of Basel III higher capital requirement, market friction is most likely to create a significant gap in banks' capital structure which could have a reasonable impact on banks' lending. Although Beck (2015) concluded a modest effect of Basel III on banks' funding cost and returned on investments, Clerc (2015) predicted that the higher price of raising both short and long-term capital demand to meet Basel III regulatory capital and borrowers are most likely to pay those additional costs of raising money. It is already hard for many Bangladeshi SME's to receive financial assistance from banks, and the higher price will put extra pressure on SME's. Although BCBS (2017) argued that SME's have a risk-weight advantage (see Table 2.8) compared to corporate entities, banks may still view lending to SME's as high risk than corporate lending because of SME's size, uncertainty and lack of history.

There are very few quantitative analyses in the existing literature that focuses on Basel III's effect on SME's access to finance. There is only one article by Cardone-Riportella et al. (2011), which falls in this criteria to researcher's best knowledge, but

their paper was based on mostly Basel II outcomes. Cardone-Riportella et al. (2011) used regulatory capital requirement computation and confirmed that Basel Accord boosts banks' risk assessment and loss absorbency capacity. They stated that regulatory requirements shouldn't be too binding for SME's heavily dependent on banks and use collateral as a positive sign to reduce banks' capital charge. Cardone-Riportella et al. (2011) also suggested that regulatory requirement increased SME's risk sensitivity level, leading to a rise in risk premium and credit cost. Cardone-Riportella et al. (2011) found that SME's which can use collateral or loan guarantee, Basel III increases their risk premium by 0.285%, which could reach 2.466% in the worst-case scenario. However, without a collateral or loan guarantee, this risk premium could dramatically rise to 16.216%. The above represents approximately a 14 percentage-points increase in the risk premium for SME's seeking finance from the bank in worst-case scenarios without collateral or loan guarantees.

Furthermore, Basel III's new capital requirement can influence banks to acquire more capital to sustain the same risk level as before. Banks can choose to keep the same capital levels by reducing lending to high-risk borrowers (Cardone-Riportella et al., 2011). Thus, banks that are willing to reduce their risk exposure rather than increasing capital to reduce lending to SME's are significant areas for banks to minimize risk exposure. SME lending is high-risk but low return, which requires relatively higher resources to manage each case. Therefore, as Basel III encourages banks to reduce risky propositions, banks most likely will lower their lending to SME's.

2.5.4 Positive effect of Basel III on SME finance

Basel III negatively affects banks lending to SME's and may also positively impact SME's. Banks' lending to SME's is based on SME's credit rating and risk weight assigned to SME's by external credit rating agencies, which can be positive for developing countries like Bangladeshi SME's. Generally, many Bangladeshi SME's lacks proper documentation and track records (Akhtarujjaman, 2010). However, SME's need to keep appropriate business documentation for credit rating agencies with double benefits. a) SME's need to store their business documents which reduces information asymmetry for lenders, and b) when a bank receives a loan application from SME's, they already have all documents ready for banks' inspection, which reduces the probability of refusal due to lack of records. Furthermore, Basel III

has assigned lower risk weight for high credit rated SME's, which reduces finance cost for high rated SME's and influences low rated SME's to improve their position and move to the high rated position.

To summarize the above discussion, it is evident that banks' finance to SME's mostly depends on two factors, i.e. credit risk calculation approach chosen by the banks and the risk category and risk weight assigned to SME loan. Although organizations such as MAG and IIF have published their assessment reports on Basel III's impact on banks' lending towards SME's, organizations such as ACCA (2011) have claimed it as unrealistic estimates. Furthermore, if banks use the standardized approach to calculate their credit risk capital and decide only to lend to highly rated SME's to reduce their RWA capital. In that case, it might have a devastating impact on a developing country like Bangladesh's SME sector and work as a barrier to Bangladeshi economic development. Therefore, from the researcher's point of view, it is interesting to find out how BCBs' reacts to Basel III and how Basel III might affect SME's access to bank lending.

2.5.5 Factors affecting SME finance in Bangladesh

Research indicates that SME's provide nearly 60% of total employment in the manufacturing sector in both developed and emerging economies. This number is likely to go up if other sectors are considered (Ayyagari, Beck and Demirguc-Kunt, 2007). A recent report confirms that Bangladeshi SME's contribute 25% to the Bangladeshi GDP (The Independent, 2018). An important and crucial factor in developing the SME sector is to have easy access to finance, particularly bank finance. World Bank (2015b) suggested that the lack of financial access is the most challenging factor and perceived as the greatest obstacle to SME growth in emerging economies. Several studies in this area regarding SME growth obstacles suggest financing is the biggest obstacle for SME's than larger firms in developing countries (Schiffer and Weder, 2001, Beck et al., 2006, Beck, Demirgüç-Kunt and Maksimovic, 2005).

Under Bangladesh Bank's policy, 40% of total commercial banks' SME loans are reserved for small enterprises because they are the actual vehicles for reducing a country's unemployment rate (Chowdhury, Azam, and Islam, 2015). However, many small and medium enterprises struggle to obtain loans from commercial banks.

Several factors are associated with SME lending that can influence BCB's capabilities and willingness towards SME finance in Bangladesh. Based on existing literature, it appears likely that the following factors play an essential role in SME's access to finance in Bangladesh.

2.5.5.1 Types and quality of collateral used

Banks use several techniques to mitigate their credit risks, such as taking collateral or loan guarantees. However, not all collateral provided by SME's have equal merit or capacity to reduce credit risk or lower credit risk capital for banks. Thus, only collateral provided by SME's with lower risk weight or higher value, such as high-value land or other fixed assets, will lead to a lower capital charge for banks. Therefore, banks' behaviour towards SME lending and SME's access to finance also depends on SME's quality and collateral types.

2.5.5.2 Banks' capital constraint

Most research regarding Basel III's impact on lending is based on assumption and mostly is predictive. Switzerland was the first country to implement the CCB of Basel III in 2013. According to the Central Bank of Ireland (2015), CCB is a time-varying capital requirement introduced by Basel III to ensure that the banking system is more flexible. During excessive credit growth, increased capital can be partially or wholly released during systematic financial stress. Therefore, it's a deposit of assets for the wrong time. A recent study by Basten and Koch (2015) on Swiss implementation of CCB was the first known practical assessment of Basel III implementation. In their research, Basten and Koch (2015) used a unique loan lever dataset on banks' loans to investigate the potential effect of CCB on mortgage pricing. They found that the impact of applying CCB on mortgage offer rates was higher by 2.72 base point on average for capital-constrained banks. Their finding suggests that the effect of higher regulatory capital requirement introduced by Basel III will most likely depend on banks' initial capital condition. Therefore, banks struggling to raise capital to meet the higher capital requirement imposed by Basel III are more likely to constrain their SME lending than banks with sound financial health. Therefore, based on the above research finding, it is logical to assume that BCBs with the capital shortfall or struggling to meet RWA capital charge is most likely to reduce lending to those most likely to cost them higher regulatory capital.

2.5.5.3 BCBs willingness to finance SME's

According to Islam (2012), institutional restrictions such as incompetent legal policies and regulatory framework represent significant barriers to efficient SME financing. Banks face several issues such as information asymmetry, granularity, lack of business plan and details required to grant finance. Furthermore, Bangladeshi banks don't have the required information and necessary credit systems to differentiate SME's merit and estimate the actual risk associated with SME lending (Islam, 2012), resulting in stricter credit terms and inefficient resource allocation. Moreover, the moral hazard among the SME entrepreneurs is high as they tend to take higher risks with the funds borrowed from banks compared to other companies (Ahmed, Rahman, and Haque, 2011). As a result, BCB considers SME lending a high-risk lending segment and is unwilling to lend without high-value collateral (Islam, 2012).

2.5.5.4 High finance cost

Loan repayment terms and higher finance cost are a common problem for SME's in Bangladesh. A few reasons contribute to this situation. Due to the higher risk associated with SME lending, banks tend to have restricted and non-flexible repayment plans even though SME's cash flows change from business to business (Ahmed, Rahman, and Haque, 2011). Therefore, a lack of repayment flexibilities sometimes leads to extra cost to SME's or hostile liquidation procedure.

2.5.5.5 High collateral requirements

Banks demand high-value collateral from SME's because of the high-risk factor. The SME lending system in Bangladesh is primarily based on assets-based borrowings rather than SME's predicted earnings and cash flows (Ahmed, Rahman, and Haque, 2011). In typical business lending, banks usually accept sales or revenue projections from a project before lending. However, due to asset-based SME lending, BCB only considers high-value collateral as a guarantee for lending. According to Islam (2012), banks demand valuable collateral to safeguard their lending from possible losses and reduce their RWA. Ahmed, Rahman, and Haque (2011) stated that collateral-based lending represents a significant barrier for SME finance because banks demand more excellent value collateral than the loan size, which means an unfair finance deal.

2.5.5.6 Credit information gap

Lack of credit rating agencies, limited SME ratings, absence of SME performance analysis and information asymmetry are vital constraints. It created a credit information gap in SME lending which impaired banks' ability to create a comprehensive credit model for the SME lending segment (Aktarujjaman, 2012). Islam (2012) stated if regulators can ensure the availability, centralization, and storage of data, it will promote SME's better access to finance and develop a comprehensive understanding of SME sectors' risk profile.

2.5.5.7 Excessive paperwork and limited banking network

SME borrowers must go through excessive paperwork and comprehending the documentation process to fulfil lenders' demand which is an exhausting and complicated issue for many borrowers (Uddin, 2008). Furthermore, limited banking networks, especially in small towns and rural areas, pose a barrier to SME borrowers. Although commercial banks are the primary finance source for SME's, the sector is still underserved in many rural areas due to the lack of banking networks. As a result, banks are reluctant to provide credits to new borrowers and demand at least two to four years of business performance that many new SME's cannot offer (Uddin, 2008).

2.5.6 Difficulties in SME growth in Bangladesh

A few studies have been found in the existing literature, which has investigated the underlying reason for negative SME growth in Bangladesh.

Quadir and Jahur (2011) stated that Bangladeshi SME's growth has been vulnerable because of frequent policy changes by the Bangladesh government and severe competition in international markets, which results in squeezed profitability and financial distress SME's. Uddin (2008) stated that SME's economic effectiveness, growth, and performance, particularly in developing countries like Bangladesh, depend on its microeconomic environment and SME specific promotional policies. Chowdhury (2007) stated that, in Bangladesh context, SME's growth is characterized by small capitalisation and inadequate assets and development in this sector is held by high moral hazard and lack of credit knowledge, limited but highly regulated access to finance, insufficient financial disclosure and poor recordkeeping. Furthermore, financial institutions high-risk perception lifts SME's borrowing costs to

a height which many SME's are unable to afford. Chowdhury, Azam, and Islam (2013) investigated the SME sector's low growth's underlying reason. Their investigation was based on 100 Bangladeshi SME entrepreneurs. They identified that a more extended waiting period for getting finance from banks, failure to provide collateral or loan guarantees, and lack of appropriate business structure for loan approval are the main underlying problems contributing to the Bangladeshi SME sector's slow growth. They have suggested that easy access to loans, financial incentives, and training to create a good business plan area remedy those problems. Khan et al. (2012) pointed to the lack of SME employees' training, poor government policies, and inadequate facilities that they suggested can be overcome by integrating government attention.

Miah (2007) observed that fundamental limitations for SME development in Bangladesh are limited traditional financing sources and lack of modern technologies, higher cost of credits, inadequate availability of market information, undeveloped physical infrastructures, insufficient power, and raw material supply, rapid changes in policies and absence of quality entrepreneur training. Chowdhury (2009) stated that the availability of necessary bank finance for SME's is the critical constraint for Bangladeshi SME's growth and development. He found that banks are unwilling to enlarge their SME loan portfolios because they believe lending to SME's is not as profitable as other investments. Ahmed and Chowdhury (2009) investigated why banks are reluctant to increase their SME lending portfolio. They found that banks consider SME's as high-risk borrowers because of their small capitalisation, SME's inability to comply with high-quality collateral demanded by banks, and higher admin costs because of higher monitoring and supervision with SME financing. Further investigation regarding banks' unwillingness to lend to SME's by Hasan and Islam (2008) found that banks are generally less interested in SME financing because of higher operational cost generated from higher monitoring and supervision and lower return but the higher risk associated with SME financing.

Research by Ahmed, Rahman, and Haque (2011) found that Bangladeshi manufacturing SME's faces several constraints which affect manufacturing-based SME's growth. Their finding suggests that lack of access to finance is the biggest concern for manufacturing SME's development. They found that, due to the higher risk factor associated with SME lending, banks' loan approval rates are limited for

manufacturing SME's. Furthermore, their investigation identified that higher finance cost, an unstable political environment, and poor infrastructural support are some of the critical constraints behind the slow growth of manufacturing-based SME's in Bangladesh. In line with Ahmed, Rahman and Haque (2011), Hossain (1998) suggested that Bangladeshi SME's face legal, regulatory and administrative constraints in addition to lack of finance. He said that governments need to be more transparent and accountable while making SME policies to ensure their future growth.

Meagher (1998) stated that capital extension is a critical success factor for SME growth. According to Meagher (1998), the Bangladeshi SME sectors' capital needs are underserved by the financial institutions because of the complex legislation which affects SME's potential growth. Meagher (1998) suggested that to ensure potential SME's growth in Bangladesh, the government needs to provide SME's access to necessary working capital and technical assistance. Moreover, most small enterprises follow informal banking procedures than traditional enterprises (Ahmed, Rahman, and Haque, 2011). As a result, they need specialized banking service rather than regular commercial banking services. Akterujjaman (2010) suggested that Bangladeshi financial institutions need to introduce specialized banking services specific to SME's and capital extension facilities.

Getting required finance from banks and other financial sources has been the most critical success factor for Bangladeshi SME's survival and growth. Several studies in this area also support it. According to Mahmud (2006), SME's in Bangladesh have minimal access to external finance, especially bank finance. He suggested only 10% of SME's have access to bank finance. Therefore, self-finance is the major source of finance for most SME's in Bangladesh, contributing 76.5% of fixed capital and 51% of Bangladeshi SME's working capital. After eight years in 2014, although banks remain the largest credit providers to SME's, the number of SME borrowers and credit supply has gone up dramatically. In 2013, total loans to SME's were BDT 853.233 million which went up to 18.3% to BDT 1,009,102 million in 2014 (ADB, 2015). This figure went up further by 42.63% in 2015 to BDT 1,758,940 million in 2015 (Bangladesh Bank, 2016b). Although the above credits provided by both bank and NBFIs, banks remained the largest credit provider to SME's. Bank lending

amounted to 97.1%, and NBFIs made up 2.9% of total lending to the SME sector in 2014 (ADB, 2015).

Bangladesh Bank (2008) stated that the key reasons behind Bangladeshi SME's slow developments are lack of financial support, poor utilities, policies, and technological disadvantages. The report said that banks and other financial institutions generally prefer to lend to larger enterprises because they can provide high-quality collateral and demand lower operational costs. Although micro-finance schemes have a better lending record than finance to SME's by bank' and other financial institutions, SME's cannot take these finance facilities as they don't fall into the micro-finance category. Therefore, SME's depend on financial institutions' formal funding even though the interest rate is higher. Bangladesh Bank (2008) suggested that higher growth in the SME sector can reduce poverty to a satisfactory level and create a skilled employment base by removing key constraints such as access to finance. Technological improvement and development of SME support services etc. can ensure constant growth.

2.6 Capital structure theories and SME financing

Several features distinguish SME's from larger firms in the financial management context. For example, SME's are not publicly traded and mainly rely on private equity or debt to raise finance (OECD, 2006). Another distinguishing characteristic of an SME is that the owner/manager tends to have specific expertise rather than general expertise. They have higher transaction costs than larger enterprises (OECD, 2006). It is vital to understand SME's capital structure to understand why SME's faces financing difficulties,

Although theory frameworks are discussed in chapter 3, it is necessary to refer to capital structure theories at this point of the thesis. As mentioned earlier, capital structure theories derived from Modigliani and Millar (1958), popularly known as the MM approach, state that in a perfect market condition, the company's value remains unchanged by the mix of debt/equity capital structure. Although the ideal market condition doesn't exist in real life, the theory provides a strong foundation for capital structure research. Agency theory by Jensen and Meckling (1976) provides further insight into capital structure management. According to Jensen and Meckling (1976), an enterprise manages a particular contract where the principal (owner) employ

agents (managers) to perform managerial duties on behalf of the principal. Through this agency contract, the principal transfers the decision making authority to the agents and the principal pay agents for their services. The loss in firm value caused by the agency relationship is termed the agency cost.

A theoretical justification of SME's capital structure that has gained more generous support in small business literature is pecking-order theory. Initially suggested by Donaldson (1961) and further developed by Myers and Majluf (1984), the pecking order theory suggests that every enterprise has a specific order of financing preference. The pecking-order theory can explain the capital structure adopted by an SME by considering the asymmetric information between the investors and the firm's management. According to Myers and Majluf (1984), enterprise managers know better about the firm value and prospects than new investors (shareholder/financer) because of the information asymmetry between management and investors. However, new investors expect a higher return on their investments which is only possible if they have a positive net present value. Pecking order theory views enterprise financing as organized in the hierarchical pecking order. An enterprise will first choose internal sources, external debt financing and external equity financing as a last resort. According to Myers and Majluf (1984), an enterprise will prefer inside finance rather than external debt, external debt over external equity; and short-term debt over long-term debt to keep original ownership and control.

Research has been carried out to investigate the applicability of pecking-order theory in defining financing decisions made by SME's. The majority of these studies have been carried out in developed countries that have developed banking systems. Paul et al.(2007) identified two sensible factors that provide a rationale for applying pecking-order theory to SME's. Firstly, SME's demonstrate relatively higher information asymmetry levels than large firms, particularly those with a relatively short history, i.e. start-up business. Thus, SME's represent a lack of historical performance data required for investors to make investment decisions (Paul et al.,2007). Secondly, SME manager/owner tend to demonstrate a hostile aversion to losing control over their business activities caused by new finance. Paul et al. (2007) stated that the fear of losing control by manager/owner lead SME's to have a strong preference for a financing option that minimizes the chance of outside intrusion into their business activities.

Generally, capital structure decisions, whether to use equity or debt finance in SME's are significantly different from larger enterprises. The problems related to how to finance SME's and their capital structure are primarily caused by the lack of finance and inadequate financing available to them during the start-up or growth stage, particularly for smaller businesses (Berger and Udell, 1998). Small firms' capital structure decision making has been the subject of sustained interest from researchers (See Barton and Gordon, 1987; Berger and Udell, 1998; Berger and Udell, 2006; Cassar and Holmes, 2003; Gregory et al., 2005; Mugosa, 2015; Titman and Wessels, 1988). Berger and Udell (1998) proposed a financial growth model widely accepted as the baseline for SME's capital structure. The financial growth model suggests that SME's have an economic growth cycle.

Moreover, SME's financial need and finance option changes with their growth, i.e. as they grow with time, they gain more experience and become more transparent as more information becomes available. Berger and Udell (1998) suggested that an enterprise's financial requirements and choices depend upon its age, public information, and size. Therefore, when an enterprise is at its start-up at a young age, it must rely on initial funds from the owner, friends or family. Berger and Udell (1998) stated that this is the most crucial stage for SME's and the tangible capital needed to survive. A firm gains equity and debt finance in the growth stage, such as a bank or venture capital sources. As the firm expands, it may gain public equity or debt market access in the next step. However, Berger and Udell (1998) also stated that the growth stage paradigm might not fit all SME's and in reality, firms' age, availability of information and size are not perfectly correlated.

According to Berger and Udell (2006), credit availability to SME's is also influenced by individual nation's financial and lending structure, regulatory policy, government policies, and technologies. Berger and Udell (2006) argued that these structure and procedures range from tax, legal, judicial, social to national/international regulatory environment. Lending technologies provide information on which lenders rely to determine whether to supply loans to individual SME's. Generally, there are two types of lending technologies used by the majority of lenders. Firstly, transaction lending is based purely on quantitative data analysis, such as credit granting decisions based on financial statement analysis or based on assets. Secondly, relationship lending is based on qualitative data, i.e. qualitative information gathered

through continuous contact with the firm seeking finance. Berger and Udell (2006) suggested that the above factors and the use of lending technologies may influence the availability of credit for SME's to some extent. Other factors that may influence commercial banks' decision to grant finance to SME's include management skills and strengths, future income potential, market conditions, and the country's economic situation.

Other empirical studies in SME capital structure either partially accepted or rejected the above capital structure theories or models. Research by Barton and Gordon (1987), Mariotti and Glackin(2012), Mugosa(2015) found that the capital structure decision influences the life cycle of smaller firms in general and capital structure decision has little influence on larger SME's. Titman and Wessels (1988) suggested that a firm's size and capital structure are positively correlated. However, Norton (1990) stated that there is no relationship between the capital structure and the firm's size, and thus, it is irrelevant. Kimki (1997) researched the relationship between capital structure and the industry sector. His research revealed that specific industry sectors such as food, medicine, machine manufacturing, and electronic power industry have higher debt ratios in their capital structure.

Cole (1998) stated that most SME's experience a fast growth rate and funding shortages in their early years of establishment. Inadequate finance represents a key obstacle to SME's survival and future success during the start-up period. Consequently, SME's become dependent on external finance sources, mainly external debt finance, due to the lack of internal equity finance, which supports pecking order theory(Wu, Song and Zeng, 2008). The above evidence suggests why the majority of SME's seek finance from commercial banks. Furthermore, commercial banks provide different finance options than other traditional financing organisations, pushing SME's to seek finance from commercial banks.

However, Myer's version of pecking-order theory may be invalid in the Bangladeshi SME's context because pecking-order theory cannot explain the financing behaviour of Bangladeshi SME's for two primary reasons. Firstly, SME's in Bangladesh continue to face difficulties accessing external finance (See Islam and Hasan 2008; Jahur and Quadir 2011; Akterujjaman 2012; Islam, Azam and Chowdhury 2013). It means Bangladeshi SME's may be facing more significant difficulties in moving

upward, as stated by pecking-order theory. This constraint of moving upward in accessing external finance may be associated with severe information asymmetry between the lender (Commercial banks) and the SME. Bai et al. (2006) stated that the information asymmetry between the lender and the SME tends to be severe in developing countries than in developed countries. Secondly, many informal sources of finance are widely available in Bangladesh than in many developed countries. The informal source loan agreements are relatively less strict in terms of credit history (but high interest) compared to traditional finance sources (McKernan, Pitt and Moskowitz, 2005; ADB, 2010; Akterujjaman, 2010). Akterujjaman (2010) stated the primary reason behind the rise of informal sources is the low-interest rate on bank deposit and high domestic savings. As a result, many individuals are willing to lend to SME's rather than depositing money with banks because of a higher return from their investment.

2.7 SME funding economics

In an efficient market, company size does not affect companies' ability to raise funds, and there will be a price that covers risk given that information is readily available (Beck and Demirguc-Kunt, 2006). Many researchers have challenged this economics assumption. Research shows that SME's experience higher financing obstacle and capital structure panorama compared to larger size companies (OECD, 2006; Wattanapruttipaisan, 2003; Beck and Demirguc-Kunt, 2006; Kira, 2013; Claessens, 2006). Research also suggests that SME's that struggle to get finance from traditional finance sources experience twice the negative effect on their growth than more giant corporations (Ramlee and Berma, 2013). Historically, the banking sector has always underserved SME's compared to more giant corporations (Ramlee and Berma, 2013). Other finance sources for businesses are also limited when it comes to financing SME's. SME funding economics can be explained using the demand and supply side. Demand-side can explain the issues faced by SME's while they seek finance, and the supply side can explain problems faced by the financing organization.

2.7.1 SME funding gap: Demand-side perspectives

One of the significant challenges faced by SME's are access to finance, especially in their seed and start-up phase (Ramlee and Berma, 2013). Difficulties in accessing

finance by SME's has been the centre of attention for much academic research. Research has defined SME's access issues to financial services by classifying those issues into different dimensions in the existing literature. Morduch (1999) stated SME's access to finance are related to the following dimensions; Reliability (availability of finance when needed); Stability (whether SME's can access finance continuously); Handiness (whether access to finance is easy); and Flexibility (whether financial services are tailored according to their needs). Further research by Claessens (2006) identified the following issues that prevent SME's accessing traditional financial services. They are availability (whether financial assistance is available to SME's and if they are, their quantity comparing to SME's); Cost (at what price those financial services are available to SME's); and the range, quality and types of financial services offered.

However, information asymmetry has been seen as the key reason for the lack of finance for SME's by many researchers (Petersen and Rajan, 1994; Berger and Udell, 1998; Ramlee and Berma, 2013). According to Ramlee and Berma (2013), information asymmetry is caused by poor market conditions, low levels of credit accountability; preliminary business plans; and bookkeeping records, lack of high-quality collateral, lack of transparency, and high market risk. Although loans granted to SME's tend to be small, banks are unenthusiastic about financing SME's because of the higher market risk associated with the SME loan market segment and higher operating cost but lower profit margin corporate clients. It was pointed that SME's, especially SME's having less business history, cannot seek finance from traditional financial sources because they are not financially sophisticated and unable to afford higher interest rates as more giant corporations can (OECD, 2007). As a result, most start-up SME's need to rely on either self-funds, government-financed schemes or other non-traditional finance sources. OECD (2007) suggested that to mainstream SME finance and increased SME's accountabilities to traditional financial sources, the government need to intervene and alter legal, regulatory and financial markets structure to ensure SME's access to finance.

2.7.2 SME funding gap: supply-side perspective

The funding obstacle from formal financing institutions to SME's are related to several systematic and institutional barriers, which results in cross-cutting supply-

side issues. According to Ramlee and Berma(2013), supply-side constraint includes cost-effectiveness of finance provided to SME's from the financial organizations, operating costs, lack of available information and lack of modern technologies to assess fund seeking applications. As a result of the above supply-side constraints, the number of loans allocated to SME's by formal financial institutions tends to be very low.

The cost-effectiveness of SME loan is related to the economy of scale in lending. According to Benston (1972), a higher loan amount reduces lenders' inspection cost per unit of loans and reduces borrowers' unit cost of supplying information, paperwork for a loan application, etc. Because of the correlation between the size of the finance seeking organization and loan size, larger corporations enjoy priority due to their larger loan size over SME's seeking loans regardless of finance seeking organizations' quality (Ramlee and Berma, 2013). Furthermore, financial organizations that finance SME's tend to have higher operating costs than other financial institutes, which negatively affects their ability to achieve profitability from the SME segment. Even if they would have reached profitability, their profit margin is relatively low compared to other formal financial organizations which don't serve this sector (Cole, Goldberg and White, 2004). It was argued that banks do not see financing SME's as a profitable business segment because of high transaction costs and higher systematic risks arising from information asymmetry, which reduces SME's creditworthiness and increase interest rates (Cole, Goldberg and White, 2004).

Stiglitz and Weiss (1981) stated that opaqueness in the SME sector makes the borrower selection process complex because rationing credit negatively affects borrowers' selection and increases moral hazard problem among borrowers (). Information asymmetry enhances banks' risk of making poor lending decisions. The bank's higher interest rate attracts riskier borrowers group that is attracted to invest in high-risk projects. These high-risk projects promise higher incentive, requiring banks' higher monitoring effort due to the moral hazard problem. From a Bangladeshi perspective, it is widespread that SME borrowers have limited or no credit record, concise business history, and no healthy business plan, making it difficult for lenders to identify worthwhile prospects among borrowers. As a result,

information asymmetry increases the moral hazard problem and de-motivates many traditional financial organizations to serve in the SME segment.

Research also suggests that financial organizations do not use modern financial technology to assess SME's credit applications (Uchida, Yamori and Udell, 2007; Bartoli et al., 2013; Berger and Udell, 2002; 2006). Generally, it's the best practice that every credit application by SME should be assessed whether the SME can repay loan instalment in time when due. Berger and Udell (2006) argued that banks tend to approve finance decisions based on available hard information such as financial ratios, credit score, industry statistics, and the area for an established business. On the other hand, banks tend to rely on relationship lending and soft information such as the owner's credit profile, characteristics, and business knowledge for SME's due to information asymmetry. However, this information is not readily available but can be observed and transmitted.

Furthermore, research also suggests that banks often take SME credit decision based more on financial information, i.e. problematic information rather than soft information (Cole, Goldberg and White, 2004). Therefore, it is evident from the above discussion that increasing the number of financial institutions which provide financial services to SME's is equally as crucial as addressing issues such as opaqueness, moral hazard and information asymmetry of SME's. Berger and Udell (2006) suggested better lending infrastructure can dramatically improve SME's credit availability and credit approval rates if banks can familiarize themselves with appropriate lending technologies, asset-based lending, credit scoring, and factorings.

2.8 Conclusion

This chapter provides a review of prior literature on Basel regulation and its impact on banks' operations. This chapter explores existing literature explaining how banking regulation, mostly higher capital requirements, may affect banks' other core operations. It was evident that existing literature reveals both the positive and negative influence of Basel regulation on banks' core operation. Moreover, most of the literature was based on banks' probable behaviour because of the capital requirement increase. However, it is still somewhat unclear how banks might behave once banks finish their implementation. From the existing literature, it was evident

that global banks pushed their brakes on lending whenever regulators made changes in capital requirement. Basel III has increased banks' capital requirement, introduced liquidity ratios and emphasized banks' leverage ratio. It is reasonable to expect that Basel III will have a significant impact on banks' lending.

Furthermore, this chapter also reviews literature related to SME's problem getting finance and how Basel III might affect SME's finance access. It was evident from existing literature that historically, SME's have always been neglected by traditional finance sources because of high risk. Different impact assessment report published shows that SME's are going to suffer adversely because of regulation changes in the banking industry. It was also evident that Basel III has provided more facilities to SME's rather than Basel III facilitating SME's access to finance. For example, Basel III introduced risk weight based on SME's credit rating so that high rated SME's get priority over low rated SMEs. However, the problem of collateral remains the biggest problem for SMEs.

Chapter 3 Theoretical Framework

3.1 Introduction

There has been a considerable regulatory and academic interest in the existing literature regarding how to mitigate financial organizations such as banks' excessive risk-taking behaviour, which is considered one of the primary reasons behind the recent financial crisis (Srivastav and Hagendorff, 2015). It was observed from the last financial crisis that banks' excessive risk-taking jeopardized individual organisations' safety and soundness and diminished the health of the entire financial sector. It is now clear that the banking sector's vulnerability during the last financial crisis was partly caused by extreme risk taken by some banks before the beginning of the last financial crisis (Brunnermeier, 2009, DeYoung, Peng and Yan, 2013). Although many believed that the larger US and European banks' reckless trading triggered the last financial recession, research suggests that the larger banks' reckless tradings were influenced by poor corporate governance (Becht, Bolton, and Röell, 2011). There has been considerable discussion regarding which governance failures have led banks to take excessive risk-taking. Many have questioned why banks' board of directors were unable to observe and control banks' risk management mechanisms, whether banks' executive director's remunerations influence them to promote risk-taking and whether banks' risk management systems were ineffective to detect risk (Kirkpatrick, 2009, Kashyap, Rajan and Stein, 2008).

It was evident from recent financial regulatory reform that regulators such as BCBS have emphasised reforming banks' governance to manage banks' risk-taking to ensure transparency and prevent future financial distress. Recent regulatory reforms mainly focused on banks' governance shortcomings, such as guidance on financial institutions' governance, board arrangements, board members' qualifications, and advice to redesign board members' remunerations (BCBS, 2014, Walkers Review, 2009). Kashyap, Rajan and Stein, (2008) argued that regulatory reform usually addresses specific governance limitations rather than detailed fundamental governance issues. Furthermore, Becht, Bolton, and Röell (2011) stated that recent corporate governance regulatory reforms tend to address pre-2008 crisis issues, whereas the principle of corporate governance regulation is to put shareholders in control. IMF (2014) stated that since the last financial crisis, bank regulators have

focused on the effect of corporate governance on banks' risk-taking rather than evaluating the whole governance mechanism. Stulz (2015) stated that corporate governance regulation ensures that banks undertake moderate risk levels that maximize shareholders' profits whilst considering the social cost of banks' failures.

3.2 Corporate Governance

Corporate governance is a framework through which companies are directed and controlled (Cadbury Report, 1992). Grant (2003) defined corporate governance as a general theory that aligned shareholders' interest with management's decision-making process to maximise shareholder value. The last financial crisis did not stir up corporate governance from a condition of inactivity, but research suggests that the previous financial crisis was the outcome of a governance failure (Grove et al., 2011; Pirsonand Turnbull, 2011; Becht, Bolton, and Röell, 2011; McNulty, Florackis and Ormrod, 2012). They had suggested that the principle of governance quality before the financial crisis did not fail. Still, the governance failure resulted from the lack of the application and monitoring of the governance principles, particularly risk management principles.

A bank's failure to follow good corporate governance practice is one of the most important internal factors for a bank, leading to insolvency (Llewellyn, 2008; Miller, 1996). Banks can take on risk rapidly which may not be detectable to banks' directors. As a result, banks' operational activity needs to be monitored by specialists and experienced board members which many banks lacked and failed to do during the last financial crisis (Becht, Bolton, and Roell, 2011b). Moreover, corporate governance for banks differs compared to other organizations in many aspects. Banks are subject to monitoring and are regulated by national and international regulators and depositors/shareholders. Due to information asymmetry and the fact that banks are financed by depositors' funds and controlled by management, agency problem is relatively high in banks, not only between manager and shareholders but also between borrowers, depositors, managers, and national/international regulators. Furthermore, the banks' stakeholder relationship is much more complicated than any other organisation that affects both the national and global economies. Following is a diagram to show what causes the financial crisis that led to Basel III and how it might affect Bangladeshi SME's.

Figure: 3.1 How Agency problem affect SME Lending (author)

3.3 Corporate Governance Theories

Corporate governance theories have been developed from various other disciplines such as law, accounting, economics, organizational behaviour, etc. (Mallin, 2012). According to Abdullah and Valentine (2009), the original corporate governance theory begins with agency theory, which led to stewardship and stakeholder theory development and later progressed to resource dependency and transaction cost theory. For this study, we consider agency theory.

3.3.1 Agency Theory

Generally, the owner (principal) of an organization hires managers (agents) to run the organization on behalf of the owner. The agents are expected to run the organization to meet the business objectives and maximise its profit. Although this process seems logical, there are two vital issues related to agency theory: moral hazard and adverse selection. Bonazzi and Islam(2007) stated that the separation of ownership and control might cause organizational inefficiencies and managers' viewpoint regarding the proper utilisation of the firm's assets may differ from that of the principal. Furthermore, managers may improve short-term organizational performances to increase their benefits packages ignoring long term corporate benefit (Tannous and Cheng, 2007).

Scholars in many disciplines have used agency theory. According to Eisenhardt (1989), agency theory has been used frequently in accounting, economics and finance, marketing, political science, law, organizational behaviour and sociology but is still surrounded by controversy. The development of agency theory is frequently traced to Berle and Means (1932). However, many researchers suggest that it can be traced back to as early as the 18th century and attributed to Adam Smith, who published his famous book, *The Wealth of Nations*. Letza, Sun, and Kirkbride (2004) suggested that Adam Smith efficiently identified agency problem when he argued that managers were careful while dealing with their money but not likely to be cautious while dealing with others money. Smith (1776) viewed an organization as a set of contractual relationships between principals, i.e. shareholders and agents, i.e. managers. According to agency theory, the principles of an organization appoint agents. Principals own the company but do not get involved in the management of the company. They select and entrust the agent to run the company on their behalf

and expect them to take decisions in the principal's best interest. However, agency theory assumes that agents may seek to maximize their profit and work for their benefit rather than in the principal's best interest (Padilla, 2000). Berle and Means (1932) identified agency problem in the form of separation of ownership and control, while Alchian and Demsetz (1972) identified agency problem in the form of issues raised from managerial control and monitoring. However, Jensen and Meckling (1976) saw the conflict of interest between shareholder and agent as a principal-agent problem. The separation of ownership and control in agency theory was further confirmed by Dabis, Schoorman, and Donaldson (1997).

Jensen and Meckling (1976) stated that a company's governance is based on the conflict of interest between the principal as the company's owner and the agent as the company's manager. Although shareholders want to maximize their profits from their investment in a more extended period, the managers might have a short-term interest, particularly if they don't have any ownership interest in the company. The theory suggests that, due to this separation of ownership and management, shareholders need protection because managers may have different goals that might lead to them not acting in the principal's best interest (Jensen and Meckling, 1976; Barnea, Haugen and Senbet, 1985). Therefore, although it is impossible to find a perfect contractual relationship between principal and agent, the contracting parties aim to enter into that contracting relationship that minimizes the sum of agency and contracting costs. Dowu and Louche (2011) suggested that the conflict of interest between principal and agent relationship arises because of moral hazard, effort level, earning retention and time horizon.

To minimize potential agency problem, Jensen (1983) suggested two critical steps

- 1- The principal-agent risk-taking system must be observed through the organisation's contract and nexus by stating the agents' risk-taking parameter for the principal's investments. Therefore, the principal must entrust agents by transferring some rights, and the agent must accept to carry out their duty according to their responsibilities.
- 2- Jensen (1983) stated the second step as a positive agency theory which clarifies how the organization should monitor and bond contract between principal and agent in the first step and develop a solution to the agency

problem. The cost of monitoring contract and bonding and the potential loss of organization values arising from agency problem is defined as agency cost (Jensen and Meckling, 1976). Eisenhardt (1989) stated that agency theory represents a system to reduce agency cost between principal and agent.

In the modern organization, corporate governance is used to reduce agency cost and restore shareholders' interest. Corporate governance suggests that an organization governing board should consist of external and independent directors and the position of board chairperson and CEO should be held by different individuals (Daily, Dalton, and Cannella, 2003; Balta, Woods and Dickson, 2010). Balta, Woods, and Dickson (2010) stated that when the board chairperson and the CEO are not separated and influence each other, the agency cost becomes more significant. The organization lacks a control mechanism that may lead to financial insolvency.

Although agency theory is a dominant perspective in corporate governance literature, it has been criticized for its inability to clarify principal-agent interaction's sociological and psychological mechanism (Siegfried and Blair, 1997). Agency theory assumes that a contract between principal and agent can substantially reduce but not abolish agency costs, which are indicated invalid by market imperfections (Eisenhardt 1989). Agency theory assumes that shareholders are only interested in the organization's performances while managers are believed to owe their duty only to the shareholders (Daily, Dalton and Cannella, 2003). Agency theory assumes managers are opportunistic and solely motivated by self-interest (Shleifer and Vishny, 1997). Furthermore, agency theory does not take into account the manager's skills. Therefore, incompetent managers who are honest will still fail to meet shareholders' expectations (Hillman and Dalziel, 2003). Furthermore, agency theory ignores the historic achievements of the trade-union movement and the role of social conventions. For example, a senior or middle manager not working on Saturdays would only be considered an agency cost in societies where Saturday work is typical or expected.

Agency theory suggests that having an effective corporate governance system in place will reduce agency costs. A useful governance board will reduce agency costs and improve transparency and accountability of directors' actions and ensure

principals receive feedback on the agent's performance (Balta, Woods and Dickson, 2010).

3.4 The failure of corporate Governance and agency Problem

3.4.1 The role of corporate governance

According to Tarraf (2011), corporate governance defines the classical relationship between agents, i.e. managers and shareholders. Tarraf (2011) argued that corporate governance is the solution to the classical agency problem created by the separation of control and ownership. At present, corporate governance covers and impacts all the aspect of corporate decision-making. Wells (2010) argued that corporate governance works as a balance of desire between the manager and shareholder. Good corporate governance assumes that managers have the proper incentive to work for shareholders and shareholders are well informed about the manager's activities. In Europe, the corporate governance reform started in 2003 through green paper publication (Dallas and Pitt-Watson, 2016). On the other hand, the leading American development was the Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002 in the U.S. The OECD made further development in this area in 2015 when they published corporate governance principles to deal with globalization and ensure accurate and fair corporate reporting (Tarraf, 2011).

Although there has been an extensive development in corporate governance, the idea of corporate governance existed long before the existence of agency theory (Dragomir, 2008; Tarraf, 2011). The primary purpose of an agent is to maximize shareholders' return and the role of corporate governance is to ensure that agents maximize shareholders' return in a sustainable way (Aquila, 2009). Therefore, sound corporate governance principles must serve all stakeholders' interests and ensure that an organization has sufficient control over internal and external risk factors and its operations.

3.4.2 Aggressive risk-taking and corporate governance

Although many say that the housing bubbles prompted the recent financial crisis, it was argued that the last recession was also triggered by the reckless credit cycle and aggressive lending strategy implemented by banks and mortgage brokers (Paccas, 2010; Rötheli, 2010; Sternberg, 2013). Grosse (2010) stated that financial

organizations engaged in creating and distributing mortgage-based securities did not perform a proper risk assessment of those financial instruments and agents (managers) of those organizations either ignored or failed to monitor their employees. Moreover, managers also kept a blind eye on this matter because it was maximizing their short-term performance.

Kirkpatrick (2009) argued that the critical reason behind risk management failure in the major financial institutions was improper and ineffective corporate governance structure. According to Kirkpatrick (2009), the board of director authorized risk management procedures to be put in place but failed to monitor implementation and corporate governance sufficiency. Managers either ignored or unable to identify an ineffective risk management system. Risk management is a vital feature of good corporate governance practice; theoretically, a corporate governance framework is supposed to constrain agency cost and promote management efficiency rather than allowing management's aggressive risk-taking (Tarraf, 2011). Erkens, Hung and Matos (2012) examined the role of corporate governance during the financial crisis. Their investigation was based on data collected from 296 of the world's top financial firms from 30 different countries and suggested that shareholders and board of directors allowed and encouraged managers to take excessive risks to increase return on their investments. Erkens, Hung, and Matos (2012) argued that managers had ignored the systematic risk of promoting short-term financial improvement, leading their companies towards economic instability. Lewis et al. (2010) also argued that bankers and fund managers concentrated on short-term performance improvement to pocket large incentives without giving any thoughts to their actions' long-term consequences. Bankers and fund managers were given the directors' impression that shareholders are only interested in financial returns and managers will not be blamed for any disaster if anything goes wrong (Lewis et al. 2010).

One of the main reasons for having a corporate governance framework in an organization is to ensure that the board of directors know the strategy and their organisation's risk appetite. However, for corporate governance to work effectively, the board needs to provide an efficient reporting system that incorporates effective monitoring and information flow necessary for directors' on-time response when required. Tarraf (2011) stated that shareholders entrust the board of directors to

monitor and ensure effective management practice within the company; good corporate governance practice requires efficient risk management supervision from the board. The Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission (COSO) report specifically stated that the enterprise risk management framework includes a risk assessment tool that allows directors to analyze risks and advise how those risks should be managed. After analyzing the risks, directors should develop a course of action aligned with their risk appetite. The enterprise risk management framework also stated that directors should establish and implement risk management policies and procedures to ensure effective risk response throughout the firm (Moeller, 2007). Even when all the risk management procedures and policies are in place, directors are often unable to protect themselves and their companies from financial risk exposure, questioning their ability to function as *bona fide* agent.

3.4.3 Directors' incentives

It was suggested that excessive risk-taking and failure to identify risk by the board of directors were encouraged by inappropriate incentive systems that allowed higher risk-taking levels. According to the European Commission (2009), a wrong remuneration policy in financial organizations led directors to emphasize short-term performances and encouraged excessive risk-taking and directors keeping a blind eye to the long-term effect of their activities. Kirkpatrick (2009) stated that bankers significantly influenced setting up their remuneration packages related to the company's long-term performance. Furthermore, directors' performance contingent bonus, share options influenced them to generate short-term profits rather than long-term performance. Heller (2008) argued that the directors' incentive system in the investment banking sector influenced directors to take excessive risk and didn't permit banks to cut costs when it was necessary. Therefore, losses aroused by their activities are for shareholders to bear rather than the managers who were responsible for those losses.

3.4.4 Inefficient shareholders control

In agency theory, shareholders' control is defined as an effective way to reduce the separation of interest between the principal, the agent(s) and the managerial greed (Wen and Zhao, 2010). However, in practice, shareholders have played a passive

role that immobilized shareholders' corporate control, specifically large institutional shareholders' inefficient role. Failure to control the board's reckless behaviour has been identified as one of the significant factors influencing larger financial organizations to take higher risks and ineffective risk management system failed to detect it (Wen and Zhao, 2010). However, much of the ineffectiveness of the largest institutional shareholders can be blamed on shared ownership. In the majority of cases, the largest institutional shareholders hold a minor percentage in total shareholdings.

It was not possible for institutional shareholders to have direct corporate control due to shared ownership in most cases. Furthermore, most shared ownership belongs to small investors who don't have sufficient information to influence corporate control. This shared ownership structure has made the firms' owners passive controllers in corporate governance who choose to exercise their power using exit choice.

3.5 The principle agent relationship

The global financial crisis has uncovered several weaknesses in the supervision and regulation among internationally active cross border banks. One of the significant flaws was the lack of practical cooperation between banking policymaker/regulators and national supervisors. Financial supervisory failure is also often mentioned as one of the major causes of the most recent financial crisis (Dijkstra, 2010). According to BCBS (2006), *the core principle for effective banking supervision* reflects an international consent of good practice in banking supervision and intends to facilitate convergence in the supervisory framework. *The core principle for effective banking supervision* by BCBS (2006) state that the crucial aspect of banking supervision is that the national supervisors oversee their respective banking industry on a consolidated basis. The supervisor must monitor that all group members appropriately apply prudential standards to all aspects of the group member's business. The core principle by BCBS (2006) also stated that adequate consolidated supervision also requires information exchange and cooperation between the national supervisor and the member of the banking industry.

The starting point of agency theory corresponds to the delegation of a task by the principal to the agent. In our context, we see the Basel regulations from a global

governance perspective were an interconnected set of code that monitors tusk place from the international to local, i.e. from BCBS to national states (Bangladesh Government) and their regulatory bodies (Bangladesh Central Bank) to the banking sector and banks lending (and borrowing) to the public, including SMEs and other businesses. However, BCBS do not have any jurisdictions or legal power over Bangladeshi banks to ensure that they follow Basel guidelines. Therefore, it is up to the Bangladesh government and Bangladesh Central Bank to oversee Basel III regulation in the Bangladeshi banking industry. As a result, in this case, society (Bangladesh government) is the main principle. Individual community members have been formally given the task to oversee the financial organisation they do business. According to the agency theory, the society member (principle) often lacks information, knowledge, and time to maintain financial institution efficiently. However, due to the vital role of the financial sector in society's wellbeing, this complex supervisory task of overseeing the banking industry is delegated to the government (agent).

According to Dijkstra (2010), governments worldwide hand over monitoring and supervising financial organisations to a specialized agency for several reasons. Firstly, overseeing financial institutions is highly complex, requiring specialised organisations that are knowledgeable enough to continue the task. Moreover, financial supervisors have high reputation risks and failure to supervise financial institutions harms depositors, which may reduce re-election probabilities, which is also a primary driving factor in why the government wants a specialised agency to manage financial institutions (Masciandaro, Nieto and Prast, 2007). As a result, the specialised agency is an attractive option for both the government and society. Thus, the supervisory agency becomes an agent of both the government and society. Hence, to achieve its supervisory objectives, the supervisory agency enforces prudential regulation recommended by international policymakers such as BCBS on the banking industry and becomes its principal.

3.5.1 The agency problem

From the above discussion, it is evident that the BCBS, as a global regulator, introduce banking regulation but cannot force international banks to adopt Basel regulation. However, the society member as the principal delegates the government as an agent to oversee banks, but the government delegate a specialised agency as

an agent to look after principles interest. From above, it becomes clear that three layers of agency problem exist: between society and government, between the government and the specialised supervisory agent, and between society and specialised supervisory agents.

Delegating society's tasks to government and government to specialised supervisory agents creates information asymmetry between principle agent relationships as both the society and the government have limited or incomplete information regarding the supervisory agent's actions. Given that the financial supervisors are independent and specialised agent, it is difficult to monitor their activities due to a lack of required information, knowledge and time. Therefore, financial supervisors can use their experience to mislead their principals about their behaviour. As the agent was delegated because the principle lacks the required knowledge and the agent has specific knowledge, the principle is never wholly able to check the agent's performance. Moreover, financial supervisors are required to comply with their duty of confidence, which prevents them from disclosing information obtained from their supervisory activities to the general public. As a result of information asymmetry, confidentiality and the complexity of the industry's nature, the supervisory agent sometimes uses their discretion to follow their interest rather than the principle's interest. Therefore, the question arises whether there is any conflict of goals and objectives between the society, the government and the supervisory agent? Although one would assume that they share a common goal and purpose: a stable and sound financial system.

3.5.2 The Conflict of Interest

To identify the conflict of interest between the principal and the agent, we must compare the principal's interest and the agent. In this case, we can assume that society's interest is a stable and sound financial sector. Similarly, as a part of the public sector, it is safe to think that both the government and the supervisory agency have a common goal of pursuing general goodness. However, one can raise the question of whether the politician and bureaucrats only pursue public interest? Dijkstra (2010) finds that the politician and bureaucrats do not necessarily follow the interest of the public or national interest because naturally, they act in an opportunistic way to their best interest to maximise their self-interest first. Shueler (2003) stated that supervisory agent would work in their best interest to protect their

reputation or career by disguising their agency's poor performance which Shueler (2003) described as *bureaucratic self capture*.

The supervisory agency may also act on behalf of persons or institutions such as politicians or banks who can strongly influence their career. D'Hulster (2012) stated that the supervisory agency working in favour of a person or institution could result in either industry capture or political capture, or both. Industry capture occurs when supervisory regulators act in their domestic, commercial banks' interest and endorse commercial banks' claims before the general public, i.e., society (D'Hulster, 2012). Similarly, political capture occurs when the supervisory agent promotes politicians interest before the general public. Buitter (2008) stated that both Industry and political capture could happen due to exercising regulatory forbearance, poor supervisory and enforcement practices and sloppy regulations.

3.5.3 The Bangladesh central bank

The central bank plays a vital role in any modern economy (Buitter, 2008). By principle, the BB is the de facto authority in the Bangladeshi banking industry, the supervisory agent delegated by the people of Bangladesh and the government to manage the Bangladeshi banking sector and implement monetary policies to regulate the banking sector. Although The Banking Company Act 1991 empowered the BB to regulate the Bangladeshi banking sector as an independent body, the BB has lost its independence since the Bangladesh Ministry of Finance established its banking division (Islam, 2017). Therefore, the BB has freedom as an institution but don't have full independence in creating monetary policy. Due to the lack of autonomy in formulating the monetary policy and political pressure, the BB as a supervisory agent sometimes fails to prevent commercial banks' poor performance and prevent default loan culture.

Financial supervisory failure may occur from the conflict of interest between the society and financial supervisor caused by financial supervisors own interest or political pressure. Therefore, to ensure that the monetary supervisor only chases the best interest of the principle and discourage the agent from pursuing their best interest, Dijkstra (2010) suggested an adequate incentive package and the independence of agents' activities of national politics.

3.6 Conclusion

This chapter presents a theoretical framework that this study uses to explain the underlying reason behind why Basel III was needed and why BCBS introduced Basel III. Moreover, the above theoretical analysis shows the principle-agent relationship in the banking industry. A detailed discussion of the agent-principle relationship's affects the NPL situation in the Bangladeshi banking industry included in the analysis chapter.

Chapter 4: Research Methodology

4.1 Introduction

The research methodology chapter discusses the methods and procedures which were used to address the research questions. Furthermore, this chapter discusses the research design, data collection method, research population, research sample size, research tools, and their reliability and validity and data analysis procedures.

4.2 Research Design

Research design is a master plan that outlines and discusses methods and procedures that the researcher intends to use to collect and analyse research data (Burns and Bush, 2002). It is the strategy adopted by the researcher to combine different research components logically. According to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2009), a research design is the researcher's detailed plan outlining how research questions will be answered (p.139)

When choosing a research design, a researcher has several choices depending on the researcher's research types. According to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2009), there is three research method available for researchers as follows:

(i) Mono-method research

Mono Method research is when the researcher collects either quantitative and qualitative data rather than collecting both types of data. Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2009) stated researcher might choose to collect either quantitative or qualitative data from synthesizing research philosophy, philosophical choice and research strategy (p.143). However, Bryman and Bell (2015) argued that the researcher could also use the mono-method to present an opposing view to existing mono-method research.

(ii) Mixed-methods research

Mixed method research involves collecting quantitative and qualitative data and using quantitative and qualitative research methods for research, data collection, and data analysis (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009, p.147). Bryman and Bell (2015) argued that researchers could overcome each data type's disadvantages by using

quantitative and qualitative research. Bryman and Bell (2015) also suggested that mixed-methods can fill gaps in research data and predict data gaps in advance.

(iii) Multi-method research

Multi-method research involves collecting and using quantitative and qualitative data, but the researcher usually emphasizes one type of data (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Furthermore, the researcher collects two kinds of data, but data analysis is based on one perspective.

4.2.1 Mixed Method Research

This research adopted a mixed-methods research design to facilitate quantitative and qualitative data collected from primary and secondary sources to investigate Basel regulation's potential impact on BCBs and their lending towards SME's. This research adopted a mixed-method research design because it examines Basel regulation's impact on Bangladeshi commercial banks and how Basel regulation affects BCBs' lending towards Bangladeshi SME's. The researcher used qualitative data gathered using interview techniques and quantitative data collected using BCB's annual report.

The primary data was collected using both structured and semi-structured interviews. This research adopts the interview method to collect primary data because the researcher considered interviewees' viewpoints as valuable and useful in written form, rather than a multiple-choice format such as survey, to understand Basel III's impact on BCBs and SME's. Although a semi-structured interview is most suitable for this type of research, to probe and form a constructive view from gathered data, the researcher could not conduct all semi-structured interviews because of access issue (please see limitation for further details). The existing literature provides some possible explanation of what might happen to banks' lending towards high-risk borrowers when the regulatory capital requirement goes up. Nevertheless, the impact of higher capital requirement on BCBs and their lending towards SME's is a unique context worthy of in-depth study because of the lack of existing research in the Bangladeshi context. Therefore, collecting primary data using the interview method was necessary to gain deep insight into reality.

Secondary data was collected from Bangladeshi commercial banks' annual reports because they are the most credible and easily accessible source of BCBs financial information showing the capital structure changes from year to year. The researcher collected secondary data from 36 Bangladeshi commercial banks from 2014 to 2017 to identify changes in banks' capital holdings and determine whether Bangladeshi commercial banks maintain required capital levels, as stated by Basel III. Therefore, Bangladeshi commercial banks' annual reports are the most reliable data source to investigate and identify the changes in commercial banks' capital structures.

4.2.2 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy is the researcher's viewpoint of how the researcher wants to collect, analyse and interpret research data. According to Patton (2002), research philosophy is "*examining the nature of knowledge itself, how it comes into being and is transmitted through language*" (p. 92). Different academics and authors have discussed a wide range of varying research philosophies. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009) stated four main research philosophies: positivism, interpretivism, realism, and pragmatic philosophical approach.

4.2.2.1 Interpretivism

Collins (2010) stated that interpretivism research philosophy is related to the idealistic philosophical position. The idealistic philosophical position is a diverse research approach that includes social constructivism, hermeneutics, and phenomenology. Interpretivism involves focusing on real facts and figures related to the research problems where researchers collect small samples to interpret the views of larger populations (Kasi, 2009). This research philosophy aims to identify and understand facts through the meaning research participants assigned to them rather than making a prediction (Walsham, 1993).

Although interpretivism tends to be a more honest and trustworthy research approach because of its higher validity level, Kasi (2009) argued that the interpretivism philosophical approach provides room for biasness to the researcher as the research data is deeply influenced by personal experience and individual belief.

4.2.2.2 Positivism

Positivism involves collecting numerical research data from an extensive research sample rather than focusing on research details. Moreover, positivism attempt to increase the researcher's understanding of the research subject by testing theories. According to Myers (2013), positivism is the leading philosophical approach in business research which presume reality is objectively given which adhere that reliable knowledge can be only gained through factual observation. Positivism assumes that different individuals interpret a given situation differently, and the key is to study the difference in participants' understanding of the subject.

The main advantage of this approach is that the researcher is independent of the research outcome which means it can be completely objective. This approach's primary purpose is to explain and predict while the interpretive approach emphasises understanding. Furthermore, in comparison to the interpretivism philosophical approach, positivism mostly relies upon individual participants self-experience while considering it a legitimate source of knowledge. However, positivism philosophical researches tend to be descriptive rather than anything in-depth.

4.2.2.3 Realism

Realism involves focusing on the reality and values that exist in the environment. There are two types of realism, i.e. direct and critical. Direct realism is also referred to as common sense realism. According to Trumpeter (2015), direct realism is based on the theory of perception, which argues that senses connect our awareness to the external world. On the other hand, critical realism is the theory and practice of science and evaluation (Roy, 2013)

4.2.2.4 Pragmatism

However, Creswell (2014) mentioned a fourth philosophical approach to research which Creswell (2014) stated most suitable for mixed-method research. The *pragmatic philosophical approach* involves employing the most appropriate research method according to the research problem rather than sticking to philosophical debate (Creswell, 2014). Morgan (2007) stated that pragmatism is not devoted to any specific research philosophy or reality. Still, pragmatism is most suitable for mixed-method research, where the researcher concludes using quantitative and qualitative research data. Therefore, the pragmatic approach grant researcher

freedom of choice to choose the most convenient methods, techniques or procedures most suitable for research needs and purposes (Creswell, 2014).

It was deemed necessary to collect BCBs financial data to unveil changes in BCBs capital structure caused by Basel III. Annual report analysis from 2014 to 2019 shows how many sampled BCBs complied with the regulatory capital requirement and their sources of raising money. Moreover, the annual report analysis also revealed why some banks failed to raise the required capital. The researcher also expects BCBs financial data analysis to answer whether Basel III improves banks' financial capability to serve the Bangladeshi SME sector compared to Basel II. Furthermore, this will also help the researcher reveal Basel III's impact on different generations of banks' financial performance. The researcher interviewed SME owners, banks managers, SME credit managers to collect qualitative data to identify how the bank managers and SME owners experience Basel III's impact on BCBs ability to lend to SME's. Furthermore, the researcher aims to determine whether SME's face any difficulties in accessing finance from banks due to new regulation or whether Basel III have influenced BCBs credit supply towards SME's in practice.

This research must adopt a research philosophy supporting and promoting the mixed-method study and facilitating quantitative and qualitative data. Therefore, this research will adopt a pragmatic philosophical approach because it encourages mix method research and offers the freedom to the researcher to choose a different method, techniques and procedure associated with mixed-method research

4.3 Data collection method

4.3.1 Primary data

There are several methods available for the researcher to collect primary data as follows

4.3.1.2 Interviews

Personal interviews have been considered the most efficient and effective method of collecting qualitative data (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2013). Kahn and Cannell(1957) defined an interview as a conversation between two or more people who have a purpose in mind. Kvale (1996) saw the interview method for collecting data as potentially an interchange of personal views between two or more individuals

who communicate or discuss a theme of common interest. James and Walsh(2018) argued that using the interview method for collecting primary data increases the reliability and validity of collected data. They stated that the interview facilitates researchers to collect further valid and reliable data, which helps researchers meet research objectives and efficiently answer research questions.

The interview is the primary source of primary qualitative data, and there are several advantages of using interviews as a method of collecting primary data. Firstly, Austin (1981) stated that a personal interview could overcome the low response rate associated with the questionnaire survey. Furthermore, Smith (1981) argued that an interview as a data collection method is most suitable for discovering interviewees' motives, attitudes, values, and beliefs. Secondly, it allows the researcher to assess the validity of interviewees' response by observing non-verbal indicators and body language, which is particularly useful while discussing sensitive issues (Gordon, 1975). Thirdly, Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Jackson(2013) stated that personal interviews could facilitate comparability by providing the researcher with an opportunity to ensure that each respondent answers each interview question. Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Jackson (2013) also argued that personal interviews ensure that interviewees do not receive any outside assistance while delivering a response. Lastly, Deegan and Blomquist (2006) stated that the most sophisticated way of gathering research data is to ask those relevant and related to the research area directly rather than using any other form of the data collection method.

Moreover, a personal interview has the highest response rate, making this data collection method particularly appealing to researchers. Kidder (1981) suggested that a personal interview has approximately 70% to 80% response rate because many potential respondents who are not confident enough to write down their opinion are likely to participate in a personal interview. Gordon (1975) further stressed the importance of a personal interview by stating that, during a personal interview, the researcher can motivate respondents to participate face to face who might not bother if a questionnaire was sent.

4.3.1.3 Semi-Structured interview

The semi-structured interview is the most common interview type used in qualitative research. In a semi-structured interview, the researcher sets an outline for the

interview topic to cover, but the interviewee determines the interview direction (Denzin and Lincoln, 2013). Semi-structured interviews are often preceded by observation and informal, unstructured interviews, allowing a researcher to develop a deep understanding of the research subject necessary to establish a meaningful semi-structured research question (Gullickson, 1995).

The semi-structured and structured interview method was selected as a means of collecting primary data. The researcher chose the semi-structured interview method because of three primary reasons:

The semi-structured interview method works well for exploring participants' perception and viewpoint, particularly for sensitive and complex issues. Furthermore, semi-structured allows researchers to probe for more information and facilitate clarification of respondents' answers (Louise Barriball and While, 1994).

The semi-structured interview provides the researchers with an opportunity to change the world, not the meaning. The method also acknowledges that not every word has the same meaning to each respondent. Every respondent doesn't use the same vocabulary to express their opinion. (Treece and Treece, 1986). As a result, this type of interview's validity and reliability depend on both how respondents convey the meaning of interview words and the importance of repeated words or vocabularies in each interview question (Denzin, 2009). From this point of view, Barriball and While(1994) stated semi-structured interviews ensure standardisation and facilitate comparability.

However, King (2004) argued that, in qualitative research, interview questions shouldn't be asked word by word in a preselected order. Instead, Eugenio (2009) suggested that the researcher use interview questions as a guide, list topics that the researcher intends to cover during the interview, and probe to elicit more critical details and follow-up from participants' responses. A semi-structured interview facilitates probing during the interview and provides an opportunity to cover the researcher's preselected research topic area.

4.3.1.4 Probing

According to Barriball and While(1994), the semi-structured interview provides a choice of wording to the researcher and facilitates probing. Probing is a crucial research tool that ensures reliability and validity of research data as follows

1. Probing allow clarification of issues raised during an interview by participants. (Hutchinson, Skodal and Wilson, 1992).
2. Provides researchers with an opportunity to explore sensitive issues. (Treece and Treece, 1986)
3. Probing can bring out valuable and complete data (Austin 1981).
4. It can enable clarification and inconsistencies on the respondent's behalf (Barriball and While, 1994).
5. Probing can help respondents recall their memories to facilitate data collection (Smith, 1992).
6. Probing can reduce the risk of socially desired answer by maximizing interaction between the respondent and the interviewer through establishing a sense of support (Patton, 2015).

4.3.1.5 Structured interview

Questions asked during structured interviews tend to control and elicit participants' responses quite tightly. The interviewer follows a set of questions in a predetermined order where participants have limited response categories (Denzin and Lincoln, 2013). A structured interview is particularly appropriate where the interviewer requires respondents to answer, and responses are generally shorter (Denzin and Lincoln, 2013). The questions asked in the structured interview tend to be the same set of questions to different respondents, such as job interviews where the same set of questions is posed to all job candidates for consistency.

Structured interviews are constructive for those situations where the researcher is under time pressure from interviewees for the interview duration. Furthermore, respondents said they are comfortable providing interview answers in writing rather than face-to-face. It was observed that the respondents think they can answer questions correctly if they write rather than speak. Moreover, some female respondents in this study preferred to provide written interview rather than face to

face interview. Some respondents offered to provide a written transcript even though the researcher had semi-structured interviews with them.

4.3.1.6 Interview process

The researcher travelled to Bangladesh for data collection. It took over eight weeks to conduct 47 interviews (41 bankers and 6 SME owners). However, this researcher uses 38 interview data and discards the remainder due to low data quality. The researcher used colleague and family connections to contact prospective interviewees before travelling to Bangladesh. Most bankers' structured interviews were taken through a personal contact who worked as a bridge between the researcher and the respondents. The remainder of the interviews were taken with the help of family members and other contacts in Bangladesh. Initially, some bankers refused to permit to record interview, although the researcher guaranteed their anonymity. Some of them refused to provide consent for recording because they were prohibited by their job contract and were required to take prior authorization from HR before disclosing banks' financial activities to outsiders. Although the researcher confirmed an informal, friendly conversation between two individuals, some respondents refused to provide face-to-face interviews and only agreed to written interviews. The researcher thinks they were uncomfortable doing face-to-face interviews because they were afraid that they might fail to answer appropriately, although the researcher supplied interview questionnaires in advance.

Semi-structured interviews lasted between 25 and 80 minutes (average 47-minute per consultation). It was evident that participants were more enthusiastic about probing when the interview took place outside the workplace than those taken in their workplace. It was probably because of work pressure and employers' monitoring system. Moreover, for the majority of the interviews that took place in participants' workplaces, participants preferred structured written interview rather than face to face semi-structured interviews. On the other hand, SME owners chose their business office for face-to-face interviews rather than outside. All SME owners were enthusiastic about probing and semi-structured interviews. This experience tells the researcher that bankers were more nervous about providing opinion compared to SME owners. One possible explanation behind this is bankers didn't want to be held responsible for their opinion. However, full confidentiality was guaranteed by the researcher, compared to SME owners who were more relaxed.

Structured interview technique was also used in situations where interviewee fixed time for an interview but failed to show up either because of their long working hours or for no stated reason, which happened several times (some of them must work past 10 pm). In those situations, the structured written interview technique was explicitly useful when the respondent wrote his or her opinion and sent it to the researcher either used email or collected the transcript in person. In those situations, the researcher sent the interview questionnaires' to respondents using email or handing it personally at their workplace. However, this process was very stressful and time-consuming as the researcher had to follow matters up almost every day. On average, it took over a week to get a written, structured interview transcript, and as a maximum, it took over 12 weeks from one respondent.

4.3.1.7 The participants

The 43 out of 47 interviews took place between October-December 2017, and one structured written interview was received during February 2018. Four out of 47 interviews were taken between September 2020 to October 2020 using WhatsApp voice call. The semi-structured interviews took place at different venues, which include respondents' home, workplace, business office, and one interview with an SME owner (J F International Ltd) took place at a family function. Hand-written notes were taken during some interviews as some respondents refused to be recorded. Those interviews were extended, and it took the researcher even longer to take notes. Some interviews were transcribed during the interview and saved using Microsoft Word. The documents were later uploaded to data analysis software. This study employed the NVivo 11 software for coding, which allowed the researcher to organize collected data efficiently and get a clear view of interviewees' response. Following is the list of participants whose interview was used in this research. To protect the identity and confidentiality promised to participants, the researcher assigned a nickname to each participant related to BCB rather than their names. However, SME owners real names were used in this research with their permission.

Bank Participants

Nickname	Designation	Bank	Specialisation	G	Age	Highest Degree
Halim	Executive Vice-President	A	Isalmi, SME, Commercial	M	51	MSC
Shardar	Assistant General Director	B	SME, Commercial	M	55	MBA
Alim	Assistant General Manager	C	SME, Commercial	M	49	BSC/ACCA/FCA

Abid	Assistant General Manager	D	SME, Commercial	M	49	MBA/ACCA/FCA
Anil	Assistant General Manager	E	Retail, SME, Commercial	M	55	MSC/ACA/FCA
Rahman	Assistant General Manager	F	Retail, SME, Commercial	M	39	MBA/ACCA/FCA
Abdul	Assistant Vice President	H	Commercial Banking	M	49	MSC/ACA/FCA
Khan	Assistant Vice President	I	Isalmi, SME, Commercial	M	57	BSC/ACCA/FCA
Shifum	Assistant Vice President	J	Retail, SME, Commercial	M	52	MBA
Ziad	Assistant Vice President	K	Isalmi, SME, Commercial	M	56	MBA
Rabbul	Assistant Vice President	L	Commercial, Foreign	M	41	MSC
Hamid	Assistant Vice President	M	Isalmi, SME, Commercial	M	44	MBA
Tasvir	Assistant Vice-president	N	Retail, SME, Commercial	M	51	MBA
Hasan	Executive officer (treasury)	O	Isalmi, SME, Commercial	M	36	MBA
MD	Executive Vice President	P	Islami, SME, Commercial	M	55	MSC
Islam	Executive Vice President	Q	SME, Commercial	M	45	MBA/ACA/FCA
Isha	Executive Vice President	R	Isalmi, SME, Commercial	F	39	MSC
Shoma	First Assistant Vice President	S	Retail, SME, Commercial	F	47	MSC
Mamun	Principal Officer	T	Retail, SME, Commercial	M	38	MSC
Muktadir	Principle Officer	U	SME, Commercial	M	41	MBA
Naim	Senior Assistant Manager	V	Commercial Banking	M	33	MBA
Hassan	Senior Executive Officer	W	Retail, SME, Commercial	M	43	MBA
Bulbul	Senior Executive Officer	X	SME	M	37	MSC
Mizan	Senior Executive officer	Y	SME, Commercial	M	47	MBA
Pritam	Senior Executive Officer	Z	Retail, SME, Commercial	M	38	MBA
Shama	Senior Executive officer	AA	SME, Commercial	F	29	MBA
Ullah	Senior Manager	AB	Islami ,Commercial	M	46	MSC
Ashiq	Senior Principle Officer	AC	Retail, SME, Commercial	M	35	MBA
Shujon	Executive Vice President	AD	SME, Commercial	M	43	MBA
Raihan	Assistant Vice President	AE	Specialised	M	52	MCOM
Dipu	Senior Executive Officer	AF	Retail, SME, Commercial	M	54	BSC/ACA
Parth	Assistant Vice-president	AG	Specialised	M	59	MSC/ACCA
	Male 29	90%				
	Female 3	10%				

Table 4.1: List of Bank participants

Following is a list of SME owners who participate in this study

SME Participants

Name	Position	Trading Name	Employees	Time	Age
Shamim Nakib	Owner	J F International	11	8Y	49
Kawsar Ahmed Adil	Owner	Godhuly Knitting Apparel Ltd.	21	4Y	29
Md Mukhlesur Rahman	Finance Director	Bashabo General Hospital Ltd	130	9Y	58
Md Mahfuzur	Owner	Egarosindur (Group)	190	18Y	39

Rahman		Limited			
Eng, Md. Mir Hossain	Owner	Radiant Group Ltd.	182	17Y	59
Baten Mia	Finance Director	Radiant Group Ltd.			43
Md. Alamgir	Finance Manager	Radiant Group Ltd.			34

Table 4.2: List of SME participants.

The percentage of male participant among interviewees is very high. Only 3 participants out of 39 interviewees were female. This was because of the low number of women in those banking positions and woman bankers' lack of willingness to complete face-to-face interviews. Moreover, most bankers had an MSC (Master of Science)/ MBA as their highest educational degree. In contrast, some had a Master degree and professional recognition, such as FCA (Fellow Chartered Accountant).

On the other hand, 100% of SME respondents were male. Although the number of women entrepreneurs is on the rise in Bangladesh, most of them are micro-business and financed by micro-credit schemes. The interviewed SME's have been in business between 4 to 18 years and employ 11 to 190 individuals. Therefore, these interview cover start-up to established SME's. The youngest SME participant was 29 year and the oldest participant was 59-year-old when this interview took place.

4.3.2 Secondary Data

While this study used the interview method for collecting primary data, secondary data was collected from Bangladeshi commercial banks' annual reports.

4.3.2.1 Archival research

The archival method is primarily used for organizational analysis using historical documents (Levine and Weber, 1981). The archival research method requires researchers to use secondary data sources to collect secondary data extracted from archived records (Hageman, 2008). The archival research method involves using a broad range of published documents; textual materials by or about an organization facilitates investigation into that organization (Ventresca and Mohr, 2002). In other words, archival research involves the study of historical documents which were created in the past that provides researchers access to historical data related to individuals, organizations or an event that took place in the distant past. (Ventresca and Mohr, 2002). However, in the existing literature, many scholars have suggested

using archival research methods, non-historical investigation of documents to supplement other research strategies (Levine and Weber, 1981; Yates, 1993; Giddens, 1981). Archival research allows the researcher to gain a sense of perspective regarding how changes in social, regulatory or historical conditions affect organizational character (Kieser, 1989). Zald (1993) stated that an archival study forms a basis to support the researcher's key research question and strengthen the research evidence base to supplement the research strategy.

4.3.2.2 Advantages and limitation of archival research

Historically, the archival research method was not a standard method used by academics for business or accounting research until Ball and Brown (1968) and Beaver (1968) used and popularized the archival research method in their groundbreaking research. Since then, the archival research method has become one of the dominant research methods used by scholars in accounting and business (Kothari, 2001; Koonce and Mercer, 2005). Hageman (2008) stated that the archival research method is handy for examining macro-level patterns to investigate social or economic trends and commonly analyse micro-level behaviour (Hageman, 2008). Furthermore, this analysis method is useful to those studies that examine the large scale of data to analyse an event's impact, such as the stock market's reaction to a new accounting standard (Hageman, 2008).

Despite the advantages of archival research methods, this method has its limitation, particularly related to the use of secondary numerical data to conclude. One of the archival research's significant weaknesses is that archival research often fails to test causal relationships (Hageman, 2008). Using archival research methods, the researcher can quickly identify data trends, but it is difficult to establish a connection, i.e. what causes them to change (Shadish, Cook and Campbell, 2002). Therefore, Shadish, Cook, and Campbell (2002) stated that archival research has relatively lower validity levels. It is difficult for researchers to establish an opinion between phenomena that is particularly true for non-experimental research designs cross-sectional studies.

Moreover, an inability to identify the relationship between variables may lead to *the endogeneity* of variables. For example, researchers may examine an independent variable's impact on the dependent variable by ignoring the independent variable's

antecedents (Kothari, 2001). Furthermore, Greene (1993) identified several archival research weaknesses, such as the dependency of secondary data source, especially if those data sets contain errors themselves.

Although archival research methods have limitations, it works well to examine data to identify a pattern or supplements the researcher's research strategy (Hageman, 2008). In this research, the researcher used archival research as a supplement to primary qualitative data research. Furthermore, auditors who certified truthfulness and quoted figures' fairness in sampled banks' annual report guaranteed the validity of collected archival data from sampled BCBs yearly financial report.

4.4 Sample selection

Choosing a study sample is vital for any research project because it is difficult, time-consuming, and costly to study the whole population (Marshall, 1996). Primary qualitative data was collected from two sources: bankers and SME owners. Bankers provide insight into banks' activities because of Basel III, whereas SME owners provided their experience and expectation when they made a loan application to BCB. For archival research, the researcher collected data from 36 BCB's published annual reports from their websites.

4.5 Sampling methods

Morse and Niehaus (2009) stated that the sampling method enhances and maximizes research efficiency and validity regardless of the research method employed. Taking their suggestion into account, the researcher used three sampling techniques to collect research data.

4.5.1 Purposeful sampling

Purposeful sampling is the most common sampling strategy in qualitative research to identify and select the most knowledgeable samples for a limited sample size (Patton, 2002). This method involves identifying and selecting individuals to form the population with knowledge or interest in a specific phenomenon (Cresswell and Clark, 2011). Purposeful sampling was employed explicitly in this research to select bankers to interview because BCB's head office implemented Basel III, and branch level bankers have very little or no knowledge about it. This was suggested by the

researcher's contact who works for Bangladesh Central Bank, and the researcher has also experienced it in the field.

4.5.2 Snowball sampling

Vogt and Johnson(2011) defined snowball sampling as a technique that researchers use to find research subjects. One research subject provides the second subject's name in a snowball sampling technique, which also provides the third subject's name. Snowball sampling assumes a link between the primary sample and the target population, and the snowball technique uses those links to refer to a circle of acquaintance (Breg,1988). Vogt and Johnson (2011) stated that the snowball technique enables the researcher to access a hidden population who are reluctant to participate in formal studies due to their activities in society. Although many have considered snowball sampling as a strategy to aid sampling vulnerable research subjects, many social studies have used snowball sampling to engage with hard to reach populations (Saunders, 1979; Faugier and Sargeant, 1997).

Although the researcher's original plan was to use purposeful sampling to collect primary data, snowball sampling also identified itself as very useful. The Snowball sampling technique was explicitly used to reach some participants who would be challenging to achieve without recommendation.

4.5.3 Convenience sampling

Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling that relies upon data collection based upon the population's availability at the time of research (Cresswell and Clark, 2011). Although this sampling technique is generally used for primary data, the researcher found it useful for collecting secondary data. According to Bangladesh Bank (2016), 57 schedule banks operate under Bangladesh Central Bank's control and supervision. While selecting a sample for archival research, the researcher emphasized those BCBs whose annual report (2012-2019) and Basel disclosure information was up to date on their website and accessible. Therefore, convenience sampling was more appropriate for archival data collection.

4.6 Sample Size

The researcher emphasized BCBs'categories, i.e. state bank, private bank, private foreign bank, specialised bank etc. while selecting the sample population to ensure

variety. There are 57 scheduled banks in Bangladesh, and the researcher collected interview from 41 bankers from 40 different banks, representing 72% of the total population. The majority of the BCBs head offices are in Dhaka, the capital of Bangladesh, and as a result, all bankers' interviewees were held in Dhaka. This ensured quick communication and easy access. Selected bankers either work in BCBs' head offices or have experienced working in BCBs' specialised SME branches.

The researcher interviewed seven individuals from five different SME's of which one interview was a group interview with three individuals from the same company. The researcher emphasized employee number and the SME industry while choosing interview participants to ensure variety and determine whether enterprise size impacts SME's finance facility from BCBs.

For secondary data analysis, the researcher gathered five years of financial data (2014-2019) from 36 BCBs' annual reports and Basel disclosure which is available on their websites. However, comparing Basel III's impact on generation wise banks financial performance, the researcher used nine banks' financial data from 2012 to 2019. Although convenience sampling was used to select BCBs from listed banks, the researcher emphasized selecting banks from different categories, i.e. state bank, private bank, private foreign bank and specialised banks, to ensure variety. The researcher also considers the age of BCB as an essential performance indicator because the researcher assumes that older establishments should be in a better financial position than those established in recent years.

4.7 Data collection

The interviews were conducted from October-December 2017 and September-October 2020. A list of open-ended questions was used for the interviews (Appendix 3 and 4). Two sets of different questions were used to interview bankers and SME owners. Since the questionnaires were not dependent on each other, the researcher probed some of the responses and asked additional questions for a clear explanation. When an interviewee raised an interesting point, the researcher asked further question for a clear answer which provided a chance to probe deeper. The interview questions were designed to help the researcher to gain a deep understanding of Basel III related issues and their potential impact on SME's. As

qualitative data collection through interviews represents the central part of the data source, most interview questions were designed as open-ended. The interview questions cover general changes influenced by Basel III in banks' policies and how they affect SME's. Furthermore, interview questions ask respondents general perception of Basel III and its impact on banks and SME's.

The researcher provided a consent form to the interviewee for details and sought their permission to use the interviewee's opinion for this study. Key issues were noted during the interview and the reflection or the interviewees were pointed out in a separate diary, including the interviewee's general reaction, body language, etc., where appropriate.

According to Hageman(2008), archival data can exist everywhere where one can find information. Some of the familiar sources of archival data are public records published by the government, a report published by research and other service organization or even stories published by corporations. For this archival research, the researcher collected 36 BCB's annual report (2012-2019) from their website.

4.8 Interview data analysis process

This study applies McCracken's (1988) five-step analysis using NVivo 11 for analyzing interview data. The first step involves reading each interview transcripts several times to understand the content and identify essential comments. The first step also involves sorting important information from unimportant contents in the transcripts. In the second step, each interview transcripts was manually loaded into NVivo 11 for qualitative data analysis. The second step also involves developing descriptive and interpretive categories based on evidence collected in the interview transcripts and combining it with the literature review and a theoretical framework. Although the initial coding process started with free coding, it gradually moved to a tree-shaped coding scheme. In the third stage, the researcher skimmed through all codes to identify and develop a pattern between codes. The fourth stage involves developing basic themes by examining the respondent's comments, allowing NVivo to code specific passage or sentences from each interview to one or more code. The final step involves examining and identifying predominant themes that can be used as an answer to the research questions and the basis for discussion.

4.9 Validity and reliability of interviews

According to Eastbay Smith (1991), validity depends on the extent to which the researcher granted full access to the knowledge and meaning of the respondent's opinion. Newton (2010) stated that an interview's validity depends on the extent to which participants' views were truly reflected. To increase the reliability of the interview data, the researcher followed two steps. After completing semi-structured face-to-face interviews, the researcher re-played participants' recorded interviews and asked them whether they wanted to edit any part of their talks (some respondents refused to listen). Secondly, the researcher also asked whether interviewees would like a transcribed version of their English interviews for their reference (provided within a week). The above two steps allowed the researcher to confirm whether respondents accepted or rejected and whether interview transcripts are the true reflection of their opinions and views.

Sekaran (2000) defined reliability as the consistency of a technique in measuring a concept that is supposed to measure. The lack of standardization in a semi-structured interview may be a concern for reliability which is connected to the issue of biasness (Robson, 1993). Although the researcher cannot always control circumstances during an interview, the interviewer's friendly conversation to break the ice, a professional approach and polite manner helped secure the validity and reliability of collected data (Barriball & While, 1994). Informal contact (with some of the respondents) also created a friendly environment during the interview. Furthermore, the respondent's data (i.e. genders and age and personal observation during the interview) also enhances the interview's validity and reliability.

4.10 Language barrier

The relationship between willingness to participate in a research interview and language barrier has been widely acknowledged in the research literature (Word 1977, Henley 1979). Marshall and While (1994) further investigated the challenges of conducting interviews with participants whose second language is English. Marshall and While (1994) stated that participants who have significant English difficulties are traditionally excluded from research studies due to their language difficulties. Still, they might have a unique contribution to research findings because they might have

different needs, views, and perceptions of the research topic, which might differ from others in the sample group.

To ensure respondents' comfort, the interviewer offered respondents two language options; Bengali and English. All respondents requested the interviewer to conduct their interview in Bengali. The interviewer has sent a copy of the translated transcript to respondents and asked them to review whether they wanted to change anything to ensure the collected data's reliability and validity. Furthermore, the respondents confirmed the validity and reliability of written, structured interviews because they demonstrated those interview transcripts were written by themselves.

4.11 Archival data analysis

Archival data collected from Bangladeshi BCBs annual reports were analyzed using five steps. The archival analysis aims to identify how Bangladeshi BCBs are dealing with increased capital requirement and whether they are capable of raising new capital to maintain the required capital level? Step one involved defining a problem and identifying what to look for in the annual report. Step two involved deciding what to measure and how to measure. The researcher followed BB's guideline to the minimum capital requirement to learn what to measure and how to measure capital calculation. Based on the policy, the researcher used different heading in the excel sheet and input formulas. Step three was involved in collecting financial data for archival research. The financial data were collected from BCBs annual reports available in sampled banks' Website. Step four involved analyzing data. Data collected from the annual report was transferred to Excel sheets separately.

Two different sets of financial data were collected to fulfil two purposes. The first sets of financial data (2014 to 2019) were collected to analyse Basel III's impact on BCBs capital structure to identify how efficiently BCBs are meeting the regulatory capital requirement and their chosen method of raising money. It also enables the researcher to analyse which categories of banks, .i.e. state banks, private banks, efficiently raise money to meet the minimum regulatory capital. Furthermore, those financial data also provided an opportunity to investigate further why some BCBs failed to raise the required capital. The second sets of data (2012-2019) were collected for ratio analysis and to draw a financial performance comparison on

different banks based on their age. It allows the researcher to understand Basel III's potential impact on different generations of banks' financial performances.

Step five involved interpreting results from analyzed data. The researcher used ratio analysis to interpret the result data.

4.12 Ethical consideration

Interviewees have explained this study's purpose and asked to confirm their willingness to participate in this study. Informed consent was sought from participants by using an interview consent form. Interviewees were asked to sign a consent form before the interview took place. Moreover, interviewees were informed that they could ask any question during the interview and complete freedom to withdraw in the future if required. Interviewees were also given a letter from UWS to confirm the interviewer's identity and data collection intention. Anonymity (interviewee's name and bank's name as requested by interviewees) was guaranteed, and the researcher has assigned a fictional given character to each interviewee from the bank.

After completing each interview, great care was taken to ensure confidentiality. The researcher ensured that none of the recorded media/transcribed transcripts was left in a public place. The raw data is stored in a password protected pen drive stored in a safe place. All raw files and transcribed transcripts will be kept for the next five years and destroyed to ensure the respondents' anonymity.

4.13 Conclusion

There are three primary research elements in research: the theoretical framework, the data collection methodology, and data collection using those methods. The methodology chapter serves as a link between the theoretical framework and research analysis. This chapter explains primary data collection methodology using the interview method and secondary data collection methodology using archival research method. Analyzing preliminary data was also discussed and the archival research process involving collecting BCBs' annual reports was explained.

Chapter 5: Analysis

This chapter aims to discuss the first three research question. The most distinguishing changes of Basel III is related to banks capital and risk management requirement. Therefore, the research questions were based on Basel III and Basel III's impact on capital structure, risk management, and SME lending. This chapter follows a logical flow of the following three headings:

The impact of Basel III on BCBs capital structure.

The impact of Basel III on BCBs risk-management structure.

The impact of Basel III on BCBs lending to SME's.

5.1 The impact of Basel III on BCBs capital structure

Bank capital structure fundamentally symbolizes the bank's choice of finance, i.e. it indicates what percentages of share capital, deposits, debt e.t.c. to finance its balance sheet. Bank regulators have an express interest in the bank's capital structure because it's related to banks' financial stability and affects banks' ability to withstand economic shocks (Greenbaum, Thakor and Boot, 2019). Banks' risks due to their lending-related activities can jeopardize banks' continued access to funding and reduce capacity to absorb shocks. Therefore, grater capital ensures banks ability to endure these shocks.

Why do banks choose the capital structure they do, and why regulators impose capital requirements; it is vital to know what makes an optimal capital structure to maximise banks value. Banks are subject to two kinds of regulatory capital requirements, e.g. capital requirement and reserve requirement. Capital requirements indicate the fraction of equity to banks' funding mix in the capital and are shown in the bank balance sheet's liability side. Therefore, an increase in capital requirement by regulators will see the liability side increase. On the other hand, a reserve requirement is a liquidity requirement that requires banks to hold as cash. Regulators/national supervisors may require banks to have additional money as a capital buffer to increase banks financial strength. Thus, the reserve requirement will be on the left-hand side of the balance sheet as cash. Therefore, an increase in

regulatory requirement sees an increase in the liability side, which is needed to be offset by asset equally to balance the banks' balance sheet.

5.1.2 Changes in capital structure by Basel III

Basel III followed a similar approach as Basel II in calculating capital requirement, which means banks' capital requirement goes up or down based on banks' risk-based activities, i.e. RWA. Besides higher capital requirement, Basel III also introduced changes in capital components. Basel III Tier 1 capital, also known as going concern capital, contains high-quality capitals such as fully paid-up share capital, statutory reserve, general reserve, retained earnings, etc. Tier 2 capital includes resources such as general provision, asset revaluation reserve, subordinated bonds, etc. According to the Basel III rules, common equity tier 1 (CET 1) capital must be at least 4.5% of total capital.

Moreover, banks are required to raise and maintain a capital conservation buffer (CCB) of 2.5%, comprised of CET 1 on top of a minimum capital requirement of 10%. BCBs need to gradually raise additional CCB 2.5% from 2016 to 2019 and maintain minimum Tier 1 capital of at least 6% of RWA from 2017. Although the above figures may seem small to many, they can differentiate between maintaining the required minimum capital and operating with a capital surplus.

Respondents believe that Basel III's above capital structure changes represent a significant change in banks' capital holding. For example, Basel II required banks to maintain 8% of RWA as the capital, of which 50% is equally divided between Tier 1 and Tier 2. Basel III requires banks to maintain 6% Tier 1 and 4% Tier 2 of minimum 10% capital and an additional 2.5% of CET 1 as CCB. So, why may some bank find it hard or even fail to maintain the above capital guidelines? The answer is Tier 1 capital consist of the finest capital which banks' can generate either by selling equity or by making more profits. However, making more profit is related to RWA, i.e. increase in profit most likely will increase banks' RWA and issuing too many equities sends a negative signal to the market. Nevertheless, Basel III represented a significant change in capital requirement and structure when Bangladeshi commercial banks moved to Basel III from Basel II in 2015.

The majority of the respondents sees these changes in the capital structure as positive and stated that this change would strengthen BCBs' capital structures and

loss-absorbing capacities. Mr Alim, the assistant general manager of C bank, noted that the changes addressed by Basel III in capital structure would strengthen banks capability to absorb losses

“Basel III affect[s] our capital structure by increasing Risk-weighted asset [minimum capital requirement] up to 12.50% & leverage ratio of 3% based on Tier 1 capital as a percentage to the total exposure of the banks. It is assumed that these changes will strengthen the bank’s capital structure to absorb losses during financial stress”.

Another respondent Mr Hassan, the executive treasury officer of W bank, stated Basel III capital requirement would help banks minimise their risk-exposures by maintaining a higher capital level.

“The Basel III philosophy aims to take on the same principle as Basel II, meaning that the banks need more capital for activities that generate higher risks. Basel III proposed that banks must maintain a higher level of capital to deal with potential losses and banks need to function at a level that minimizes risk exposure. Consequently, to control banks’ risk-taking, Basel III stated that banks need to maintain their core capital based on their Risk-Weighted Assets. What that means for banks is that their capital requirement depends on their risk exposure”.

Both respondents saw increased capital requirement under Basel III as a positive influence toward establishing a stable financial industry. However, they also mentioned that the new regulatory capital requirement should control banks risk-taking. They saw banks capital level as a controlling factor to banks risk-taking. They stated that banks are most likely to hold their risk exposure to reduce banks' minimum regulatory capital requirement.

5.1.3 Method of raising capital

Most Bangladeshi commercial banks have been meeting the increased capital requirement by using retained earnings, new share issue, and subordinated debt. Retained earnings are the percentages of the net profits that are not paid to shareholders as dividends but owned by the company for reinvesting in the core business. Subordinated debt is a type of debt, security, or loan with a lower priority in claiming assets or earning. As a result, if borrowers' defaults in repaying

subordinated debt, creditors who own subordinated debt can only claim their money once other senior credits have been paid in full.

Financial statement analysis revealed that to satisfy the Basel III Tier 1 capital requirement, BCBs used the right share issue and retained earnings. However, both raising capital methods are upsetting for shareholders because many BCBs had retained earnings and paid shareholders bonus shares as a dividend rather than a cash dividend that many shareholders prefer. Moreover, the right share issue and bonus shares are not particularly preferred by shareholders because it reduces their existing investment values. One respondent, Mr MD, explained why shareholder does not like right share

“Right share is not preferable to many existing shareholders. Currently, we have BDT 7500 Crore as capital and in the last couple of years, we paid a 20% cash dividend to our shareholders. If we issue the right share 1:1, our paid-up capital will be BDT 15000 Crore. However, this will reduce dividend payment to 10% or less which will negatively impact investors' confidence.

This finding suggests a prevalent culture of meeting Basel III regulatory capital requirement using retained earnings. This method represents a potential danger for banks' long-term futures. As banks are using more net profits to transfer to retained earnings to meet the capital requirement, shareholders receive no/less cash dividend or bonus share. Generally, bonus shares are like ordinary shares given to shareholders instead of dividend (The Economic Times, 2018). Many banks issue bonus share as dividend to transfer their net profits to retained earnings or encourage retail participation, or simply to increase their equity base (The Economic Times, 2018). However, from an investor's point of view, bonus shares are the same as making a narrower slice of the same pie. Like the pie size doesn't change by the number of times it is sliced, bonus shares may increase the number of shareholdings, but they also reduce individual share values. Therefore, there is no logical reason to prefer bonus shares over cash dividends. As a result, many investors prefer cash dividends rather than bonus share. Respondents pointed out that issuing bonus share instead of cash dividend to increase retained earnings to meet the Tier 1 capital requirement may destroy investors' confidence in banks.

It is evident from the 29 BCBs financial statement analysis that most Bangladeshi commercial banks use subordinated bonds (SCBs are excluded) to meet the Tier 2 capital requirement. However, subordinated bonds are a short-term solution, and banks need to pay them back in future either as cash or in the form of equity. Moreover, only 16% (four banks) of sampled BCBs did not issue any subordinated debt to increase regulatory capital. The remaining 84% of BCBs have issued subordinated debts at least once from 2014 - 2019 to meet Basel III capital requirement.

Figure 5.1: BCBs using subordinated debt to raise capital (2014-2019)

Further analysis of 29 PCBs/FCBs financial statements revealed that only 13 BCBs out of 29 issued subordinated bonds in 2014. This number dramatically increased from 13 to 25 in 2019. This sharp increase in the number of PCBs using subordinated debt suggests that using subordinated debt to increase regulatory capital requirement is a significant source for PCBs to meet Basel III capital requirement. The following table shows the state of subordinated debt used by sampled banks from 2014 to 2015.

Bank Name	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
AB Bank Ltd	2500	6500	6500	6000	6800	6500
Al-Arafah Islami Bank Ltd	3000	3000	3000	3000	4200	4200
Bank Al Falah Ltd	0	0	0	0	0	0
Commerce Bank Ltd	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bank Asia Ltd	4500	3315	3197	8093	9200	9560

BRAC Bank Ltd	3000	3000	3000	0	4500	4500
Citibank N.A	0	3000	3000	3000	3000	3000
Dhaka Bank Ltd	1200	0	0	3000	3000	4250
Dutch-Bangla Bank Ltd	4658	4402	3700	6550	7660	8562
Eastern Bank Ltd	2500	2500	2500	2500	2500	1900
EXIM Bank Ltd	0	2500	2500	6500	7800	8520
First Security Islami Bank Ltd	2382	1882	1382	5382	6385	6385
ICB Islamic Bank Ltd.	0	0	0	0	0	0
IFIC Bank Ltd	0	0	3500	5274	6452	7546
Islami Bank Bangladesh Ltd	3000	3000	3000	5000	6500	8600
Jamuna Bank Ltd	0	2000	0	5000	5000	7000
Meghna Bank Ltd	0	0	0	0	4569	4569
Mutual Trust Bank Ltd	1000	4875	4250	6159	7214	6812
NCC Bank Ltd	0	1280	1024	2750	3950	4650
National Bank Ltd	0	0	0	0	0	0
One Bank Ltd	Nil	1760	5320	4880	5890	6520
Premier Bank Ltd	2600	3000	5200	5400	5900	4300
Prime Bank Ltd	0	2600	2500	4880	5600	6100
Pubali Bank Ltd	0	0	0	5000	5000	5000
Shahjalal Bank Ltd	0	0	0	4000	5600	6700
Social Islami Bank Ltd	0	3000	3000	5440	6550	6100
Southeast Bank Ltd	3000	3000	7400	6800	8300	7200
Standard Bank Ltd	0	2000	2000	5600	6800	5700
UCBL	2000	6600	6200	8300	9800	8200
Bank issued Subordinated bonds	13	20	21	24	25	25

Table 5.2 List of BCBs issued subordinated bonds, Figures in BDT millions (Source: Annual report)

The researcher asked respondents whether BCBs can use perpetual bonds to substitute for the subordinated bond. Perpetual bonds are types of bonds with no maturity date. Therefore, it may be treated as equity rather than debt. One respondent said that they do not have any plan to issue perpetual bonds right now because Bangladesh Central Bank did not provide any direction regarding perpetual bonds to raise capital. But one respondent said if Bangladesh Central Bank asks them to issue the perpetual bond, he is doubtful whether the perpetual bonds can help them raise money. Mr MD, the Executive Vice President of P bank, stated that because of the weak Bangladeshi bond market, it is uncertain how the Bangladeshi bond market might react if Bangladesh Bank instructs BCBs' to issue perpetual bonds to raise money in the future. Mr MD stated

“Bangladeshi bond market is not that strong. Even if Bangladesh Bank allows us to issue perpetual bond [to raise capital], we don’t know how Bangladeshi financial market is going to react.”

Subordinated debt to raise money poses a potential risk for BCBs because banks and other institutional investors are the leading buyers of these types of bonds. As a result, a credit default in one bank can spread throughout the industry.

5.1.4 Difficulties in raising capital

Although Bangladeshi commercial banks need to increase their capital gradually year by year, yet it is still difficult for many banks to raise and meet Basel III minimum capital requirement timeline. One respondent stated that some BCBs are struggling to raise new capital to achieve the required Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), which might be difficult for many banks to accomplish during the implementation stage. Capital Adequacy Ratio, also known as Capital to RWA Ratio (CRAR), indicates banks’ capital compared to its total RWA (Bangladesh Bank, 2014). Therefore, higher CAR indicates better loss-absorbing capability. Respondents have expressed their express concern regarding BCBs failure to raise minimum capital. Mr MD think some BCBs are already struggling to raise new money and this list most likely to expand with time.

“Yes, for many banks which I will not name, it [raising capital] is getting challenging to meet Basel III 12.5% capital requirement even though they don’t have to do it in one go. [...] We have raised 11.42% [CAR rate] of our capital where our required [CAR] rate was 11.25%. It will increase next year again by .62%.”

A similar opinion was expressed by another respondent Mr Rabbul who thinks that even though his bank meets minimum capital requirement timelines, many banks are falling behind to raise minimum capital according to the guideline provided by Bangladesh Bank.

“After adopting Basel III regulations, we are not in capital shortfall, but many banks may struggle during the implementation stage. Weak share market and low investors confidence in banks generating profits made this situation even worst.”

However, some respondents expressed optimism and stated that most banks would raise and meet Basel III minimum capital requirement. They said BCBs are struggling, but eventually, most BCBs will meet or exceed the minimum capital requirement. Mr Naim stated

“Basel III has given importance ongoing concern capital as well as the quality of capital rather quantity, and almost all the private commercial banks are keeping capital above the regulatory requirement with a favourable mix in core capital.”

Another respondent Ms Shoma, the first assistant vice president of S bank, predict that PCBs will not have any problem to meet Basel III capital requirement due to PCBs strong financial position.

“After adopting Basel III [...], our bank has not been in capital shortfall and, to my best knowledge, private commercial banks are in an excellent financial position to meet minimum capital requirement.”

Respondents have mixed opinion about BCBs capability to meet minimum capital requirement. The difference in opinion may have caused by the financial position of the bank they work for. Financial analysis on Bangladeshi commercial banks annual report revealed that several SCBs and PCBs failed to meet required capital ratios or have a negative capital balance which suggests that some commercial

Figure 5.3: Regulatory capital compliant/default rate from 2014 to 2019

banks are struggling to raise capital as required and failing to maintain the minimum capital requirement. The annual report analysis is conducted on 36 Bangladeshi commercial banks from 2014 to 2018. According to their annual report from 2014 to

2017, it is evident that 4 out of 36 commercial banks either failed to maintain Basel II regulatory capital requirement or had a negative capital balance or both in 2014.

Bank Name	Total RWA Asset	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Eligible Capital	Minnum Regulatory Capital	Capital Surplus/Shortages	CAR 8% (Basel II)	Tier 1 Capital to total capital
State Banks								
Bangladesh Krishi Bank	126791	-5288	3610	-1678	10143	-11821	-1.32%	-4.17%
BASIC Bank Limited	92364	-26854	622	-26232	7389	-33621	-28.40%	-29.07%
Private Commercial Banks								
Commerce Bank Limited	24284	1236	176	1412	1943	-531	5.81%	5.09%
ICB Islamic Bank Ltd.	92303	-1018	311	-707	7384	-8091	-0.77%	-1.10%

Table 5.4: Banks who failed to comply with Basel II in 2014.

In 2015, the number of default increased by three to seven BCBS. Seven out of 36 BCBs failed to maintain minimum capital requirement as indicated by Basel III. Approximately 60% of capital defaulted banks were State-owned commercial bank (SCB), and 40% were Private Commercial Bank (PCB) (Table 5.3). The percentages of capital default under Basel III have gone up by 10% among SCB in 2015 compared to Basel II capital default in 2014.

	Total RWA Capital	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Eligible Capital	Regulatory Capital (10% of RWA or BDT 4,000 whichever Higher)	Capital Buffer (N/A)	Capital Surplus/Shortages	CAR (min 10%)	Tier 1 capital to total capital (5.50% min)
State Bank									
Agrani Bank Limited	264691	17479	7770	25249	26469	N/A	-1220	9.54%	6.6%
Bangladesh Krishi Bank	140045	-58096	3971	-54125	14005	N/A	-68130	-38.65%	-41.5%
Basic Bank Limited	112748	-9088	575	-8513	11275	N/A	-19787	-7.55%	-8.1%
Rupali Bank Limited	149640	9288	3410	12698	14964	N/A	-2266	8.49%	6.2%
Private Banks									
Commerce Bank Ltd	26197	1047	136	1183	2620	N/A	-1437	4.52%	4.0%
ICB Islamic Bank Ltd.	91885	-10438	256	-10183	9189	N/A	-19371	-11.08%	-11.4%
Premier Bank	98729	5693	3303	8996	9873	N/A	-877	9.11%	5.8%

Table 5.5: Banks who failed to maintain minimum capital in 2015.

In 2016, seven out of 36 BCBs failed to meet Basel III minimum capital requirement. The number of SCBs unable to maintain Basel III minimum regulatory capital requirement increased significantly by 12% to 72%, where capital default among PCBs declined to 28% to two. PCBs were more efficient in meeting Basel III minimum capital requirements compared to that of SCBs in 2016.

Figures in Millions

2016

Bank Name	RWA Assets	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Capital	Regulatory Capital (10% of RWA or BDT 4,000 whichever Higher) Surplus/Shortages	Capital Conservation Buffer .625%	Capital (min Surplus/Shortages	CAR + CCB 10.625% of RWA)	Tier 1 capital to RWA 5.50%
State Bank									
Agrani Bank Limited	266995	16915	9856	26771	26700	1669	-1597	10.03%	6.34%
Bangladesh Krishi Bank	135809	-63874	5479	-58395	13581	849	-72825	-43.00%	-47.03%
Basic Bank Limited	112019	-18591	630	-17961	11202	700	-29863	-16.03%	-16.60%
Rupali Bank Limited	176967	8908	2928	11836	17697	1106	-6967	6.69%	5.03%
Sonali Bank Limited	451930	33656	13032	46688	45193	2825	-1330	10.33%	7.45%
Privet Commercial Bank									
Commerce Bank Limited	26719	338	122	460	2672	167	-2379	1.72%	1.27%
ICB Islamic Bank Ltd.	93529	-10711	196	-10515	9353	585	-20452	-11.24%	-11.45%

Table 5.6: List of BCBs that failed to meet Capital requirement in 2016

In 2017, the number of regulatory minimum capital default sharply increased to 9 BCBs out of 36 sampled BCB's. Among those nine default BCBs, 6 were SCBs, and 3 were PCB. The default number may be due to an increase in minimum capital requirement from 10.63% of RWA to 11.25% RWA.

Bank Name	Total RWA Assets	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Eligible Capital	Regulatory Capital (10% of RWA)	Capital Buffer 1.25%	Capital Surplus/Shortages	CAR + CCB(min 11.25% of RWA)	Tier 1 capital to total capital + Conv. Buffer (6% min)	Retained Profits
State bank										
Agrani Bank Limited	336788	20663	13819	34482	33679	4210	-3407	10.24%	6.14%	-1032
Janata Bank	443422	39819	4777	44596	44342	5543	-5289	10.06%	8.98%	9164
Bangladesh Krishi Bank	142609	-66131	6908	-59223	14261	1783	-75267	-41.53%	-46.37%	-78451
Basic Bank Limited	119712	-16582	749	-15833	11971	1496	-29301	-13.23%	-13.85%	26523
Rupali Bank Limited	199520	9967	3061	13028	19952	2494	-9418	6.53%	5.00%	731
Sonali Bank Limited	460756	37166	10517	47683	46076	5759	-4152	10.35%	8.07%	-1445
Privet Bank										
Commerce Bank Limited	30204	798	127	925	3020	378	-2473	3.06%	2.64%	112
ICB Islamic Bank Ltd.	94905	-11117	140	-10977	9491	1186	-21654	-11.57%	-11.71%	-17731
Southeast Bank Limited	311557	21165	12599	33764	31156	3894	-1286	10.84%	6.79%	2640

Table 5.7: List of BCBs that failed to meet Capital requirement in 2017

In 2018, the bank's failure to maintain the minimum capital requirement stays the same as in 2017. The number of capital default among SCBs declined by 10%, where the number of PCBs increases by 10%. It is important to mention that The Janata Bank, a well-known SCBs in Bangladesh, managed to raise money to maintain the minimum capital and moved out of the capital default list. Simultaneously, Shahjala Bank made it to the PCBs capital default list.

Figures in Millions

2018

Bank Name	Total RWA Assets	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Eligible Capital	Regulatory Capital (10% of RWA)	Capital Buffer 1.25%	Capital Surplus/ Shortage	CAR + CCB(min 11.25% of RWA)	Tier 1 capital to total capital +	Retained Profits
State bank										
Agrani Bank Limited	435621	19521	13526	33047	43562	5445	-15960	7.59%	4.48%	-1256
Bangladesh Krishi Bank	153245	-68219	6929	-61290	15325	1916	-78530	-39.99%	-44.52%	-8618
Basic Bank Limited	218562	-18527	821	-17706	21856	2732	-42294	-8.10%	-8.48%	23516
Rupali Bank Limited	243546	10564	3156	13720	24355	3044	-13679	5.63%	4.34%	521
Sonali Bank Limited	543218	42135	10115	52250	54322	6790	-8862	9.62%	7.76%	-12518
Private Bank										
Commerce Bank Ltd	34562	856	127	983	3456	432	-2905	2.84%	2.48%	137
ICB Islamic Bank Ltd.	94905	-87652	178	-87474	9491	1186	-98151	-92.17%	-92.36%	15321
Southeast Bank Ltd	365421	24156	12689	36845	36542	4568	-4265	10.08%	6.61%	2793
Shahjalal Bank Ltd	182364	12985	6689	19674	18236	2280	-842	10.79%	7.12%	856

Table 5.8: List of BCBs that failed to meet Capital requirement in 2018

In 2019, the number of capital default reduced to seven banks from nine banks. SCBs, which failed to maintain the minimum capital requirement, continued to do the same in 2019. However, the number of PCBs saw a sharp decline in 2019. Two PCBs who failed to raise minimum capital requirement since 2014 continued their journey to capital default in 2019.

Figures in Millions

2019

Bank Name	Total RWA Assets	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Eligible Capital	Regulatory Capital (10% of RWA)	Capital Buffer 1.25%	Capital Surplus/ Shortage	CAR + CCB(min 11.25% of RWA)	Tier 1 capital to total capital + Conv. Buffer (6% min)	Retained Profits
State bank										
Agrani Bank Limited	452136	25915	18216	44131	45214	5652	-6734	9.76%	5.73%	-1721
Bangladesh Krishi Bank	172156	-49512	6781	-42731	17216	2152	-62099	-24.82%	-28.76%	-1123
Basic Bank Limited	224891	-12541	1023	-11518	22489	2811	-36818	-5.12%	-5.58%	16987
Rupali Bank Limited	254153	13546	3721	17267	25415	3177	-11325	6.79%	5.33%	645
Sonali Bank Limited	558192	46218	12451	58669	55819	6977	-4128	10.51%	8.28%	-11541
Private Bank										
Commerce Bank Ltd	35215	932	152	1084	3522	440	-2878	3.08%	2.65%	32
ICB Islamic Bank Ltd	97521	-92154	231	-91923	9752	1219	-102894	-94.26%	-94.50%	13216

Table 5.9: List of BCBs that failed to meet Capital requirement in 2017

From the above analysis, it is evident that SCBs are struggling to maintain the minimum capital requirement. It doesn't seem very easy for them to raise money to support the required capital level. One of the primary reasons is that SCBs are dependent on the Bangladesh governments cash injection rather than public investments, where PCBs can raise money from the stock market and public investments.

Some respondents have expressed concern that it will be difficult for BCBs to raise minimum capital as per Basel III guideline. Simultaneously, some said BCBs, especially PCBs, are in an excellent financial position to raise money without any hurdle. It was evident from financial statement analysis from 2014 to 2017; several banks failed to meet Basel III capital requirement. Most interestingly, all SCBs could not meet the capital requirement in 2017, while only 3 PCBs out of 29 could not raise minimum capital in 2017. This suggests that PCBs are in better financial shape than SCBs, and most PCBs are meeting capital obligation while SCBs are struggling.

The above analysis shows that the number of regulatory capital default among SCBs is higher than PCBs. According to Kumar, Hossain, and Islam (2020), SCBs failed to maintain the minimum capital requirement because of high NPL among SCBs. When banks record a large number of loan as NPL, it affects their profit-generating capability negatively. Generally, banks generate money from the interest they charge on loans. When they cannot generate money from loan interest due to high NPL, they have less money available for lending and pay for their operating costs. Along with profitability, it also narrows down the scope of a new loan for potential borrowers to get a new loan from banks, especially for high-risk borrowers.

5.1.5 Present status of Capital adequacy ratio in BCBs

The capital adequacy ratio (CAR) is the capacity of banks available capital, which is expressed as a percentage of banks risk-weighted credit exposure. The minimum CAR requirement as per Basel III is 10.5%.

Figure 5.10: Position of CRAR across BCBs 2018 (Source: Bangladesh Bank, 2019)

According to Bangladesh Bank (2019), as of 2018, 47 out of 57 BCBs maintained 10% or higher in line with Basel III capital requirement. However, SCBs (State-owned Commercial Bank) kept only 2.02% CAR than the required 10.5%. Simultaneously, PCBs (Private Commercial Bank) maintained 12.24% on average, and FCB (Foreign Commercial Banks) kept 22.97% CAR, respectively. In 2019, the CAR of SCB increased dramatically to 8.5% due to capital injection from Bangladesh Government while PCB's CAR increased to 12.7% and FCBs to 28.7%, respectively (Table 5.11).

Figure 5.11: Position of CAR across BCBs 2019 (Source: Bangladesh Bank, 2019)

The foreign commercial banks continued to maintain the highest CAR while most SCBs banks failed to meet Basel III minimum capital requirement (Table .5.12)

According to Bangladesh Bank (2019), 47 out of 57 BCB maintained their CAR at 10% or higher per Basel III Pillar 1 requirement. In June 2019, the CAR of BCBs stood at 11.7% on average, which is 30 basis points and 80 Basis point higher

Figure 5.12: Level of CRAR maintained by the BCBs (Source: Bangladesh Bank, 2019)

compared to the ratio recorded at the end of March 2019 and June 2019 (figure 5.10). Most importantly, 30 out of 47 BCB's CAR were between the range of 10%-15% and their combined asset accounted for 59.4% of the Bangladeshi banking industry as of June 2019.

Furthermore, BCB's Tier-1 capital ratio trend was similar to CAR. Tire- capital ratio jumped to 8.1% in June 2019 from 7.7% of March 2019 and 7.6% of June 2018 compared to Basel III minimum Tire-1 capital requirement of 6% (figure 5.11).

Figure 5.13: Tier 1 capital ratio and overall CRAR of BCBs, (Source: Bangladesh Bank, 2019)

According to Bangladesh Bank (2019), 31 out of 57 banks maintained the minimum CCB of 2.5% as per Basel III regulatory requirement on a solo basis. The average percentage of CCB of BCB was 1.74% compared to the required 2.5%.

The above discussion suggests the followings

1. Basel III has made a significant change in Bangladeshi commercial banks' capital structure in terms of capital requirement as well as percentages of capital required in Tier 1 and Tier 2 capital;
2. The method used to raise capital may be upsetting shareholders because most banks are paying a bonus share as a dividend. Furthermore, subordinated bonds used by banks to increase their Tier 2 capital may create financial chaos in future if subordinated bond issuer failed to repay in future as most buyers of this types of bonds are other financial institution
3. Most BCBs are on track in meeting the capital requirement. However, SCBs are struggling to maintain the minimum capital requirement, and they have large NPL.
4. Most PCBs/FCBs are maintaining minimum capital requirement, and they have small NPL.

5. FCB's are ahead in maintaining Basel III capital requirement compared to SCBs and PCBs and have a healthy capital surplus.
6. SCB's failure to raise capital and capital deficit may be related to their massive number of non-performing loans, revealing their credit risk management policy weaknesses. This finding suggests that their inefficiency may cause SCB's difficulties to raise capital to manage credit risks rather than Basel III higher capital requirement; and
7. PCB's/FCB's are using an optimal capital structure using a combination of internal/external financing sources, which is most likely to improve commercial banks' performances

5.2 Basel III Risk-management framework and lending

BCBs have started to implement from January 2015 as advised by BB, the central bank of Bangladesh. The majority of Basel III reform in the risk management area is related to counterparty credit risk and reliance on external credit ratings. This suggests that Basel III concentrated on the existing risk monitoring process's technical side rather than introducing a completely new risk management structure and added new techniques with the current framework to enhance risk coverage. For example, Basel II, counterparty trading book only covered risk default of the counterparty (Bangladesh Bank, 2014). Basel III includes an additional capital charge specifically for Credit Value Adjustment (CVA) risk to capture market-to-market credit losses caused by the deterioration of the counterparty's creditworthiness (Bangladesh Bank, 2014). Furthermore, Basel III strengthens counterparty credit risk management by providing collateral, margin period of risk and specific credit risk management guidelines on counterparty credit risk assessment. In addition to the counterparty risk management process, the Basel III reform package also introduced risk management supervisory reviews changes.

5.2.1 Technical changes in the risk management framework

Basel III has made bank risk management more complex and demanding since the global financial crisis started in 2008. Since then, BCBS added frequent addition of various elements to the existing risk management framework, which made Basel III esoteric to most financial organisation. For greater understanding, figure 5.15 below illustrates each of the vital evolution.

Table: 5.14 Consolidated Basel III risk management framework. Source: Deloitte (2015).

5.2.1.2 Risk-based Capital

Basel III made the first enhancement to the definition of capital and minimum CAR requirement to manage risk better. Basel III requires banks to display not only higher capital but also a better quality capital base. Risk-based capital deals with credit, market and operational risk. Risk-based capital is increased by a minimum of 4.5% CAR on top of the existing minimum Tier 1 CAR of 6% capital. Furthermore, Basel III introduced two additional capital buffers, Capital Conservation Buffer 2.5% of RWA and Countercyclical Buffer (set by national supervisor).

Under new risk-based capital requirements, banks with significantly higher OTC derivatives should be more impacted due to higher risk-based capital requirements because of their OTC activities. On the other hand, banks that have substantially lower over the counter derivatives in their banking books and rely mostly on fund maturity or rate transformation will see the less risk-based capital requirement and benefit from capital adequacy.

Only a few respondents have basic knowledge of derivative products. Respondents stated that BCBs do not offer OTC derivative products because there is no market for them. Mr Parth said that BCBs were unaffected during the last financial crisis because BCBs was not involved in the derivatives market.

“Bangladeshi capital market is still at a nascent development stage, and there is no OTC derivative market yet. It is one reason why the Bangladeshi banking industry stood strong while the global banking system collapsed during the last credit crunch.”

Mr Shujon further added no OTC derivative market in Bangladesh due to a lack of high profile investors.

“OTC derivatives market is essential to develop a strong capital market, but BCBs don’t offer the derivative product. As a developing nation, Bangladesh does not have enough investors with a bulk amount of fund where a strong derivative market requires a significant number of investors as well as a significant amount of cash input.”

It is observed that banks having significant exposure to OTC derivatives are mostly affected by Basel III RBC. However, as per respondents, BCB’s do not offer OTC derivatives and, as a consequence, have less RBC requirement.

5.2.1.3 Non-risk-based Capital (NRBC)

Under Basel II, many banks have fabricated extreme leverage while maintaining a seemingly healthy RBC ratio. According to BCBS (2016), this excessive leverage ratio by banks formed a vicious circle of losses and reduced credit availability in the real economy. As a result, BCBS introduced a leverage ratio in Basel III to minimise such a risk in the future. NRBC is designed to capture both on and off-balance sheet exposures by applying accounting measures and currently set at a minimum of 3%.

One respondent, Mr Abid, stated that most BCBs (except specialised banks) are subject to off-balance sheet risk exposure

“We are exposed to huge off-balance sheet item like any other BCBs. Most of these off-balance sheet exposures are due to a huge number of import/export L/C's and credit guarantees, especially in the garment sector.”

The NRBC leverage ratio is susceptible to the financial organisation's business model, i.e. highly leveraged financial organisation will be impacted more compared to less leveraged financial organisation. According to Deloitte (2015), banks with high debt to equity ratio and maturity transformation in their books are most likely to be impacted by the NRBC requirement

5.2.1.4 Short-term liquidity

Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR) has been anticipated as a very significant measure of liquidity for banks globally (Deloitte, 2015). LCR requires banks to hold readily available and high-quality liquid assets easily converted to cash on short notice to funds banks. Banks that are significantly exposed to individual customers such as SME or have high run-off factors to cash deposits may positively impact the LCR level. It is expected that PCBs most likely to have high LCR compared to specialised banks such as SME banks because of their highly liquid asset-based. As per Basel III requirement, banks need to keep 70% LCR by 2016 and 100% LCR by 2019.

5.2.1.5 Long-term liquidity

While LCR promotes elasticity in banks liquidity in the short-term, net stable funding ratio (NSFR) is complimentary to LCR and ensure a longer funding resilience. NSFR limit the degree of maturity mismatch by providing that banks fund long-term liabilities with long-term assets. NFSR is for one year, and during this period, banks need to ensure that they have stable funding for their investments. Thus, it openly impacts banks maturity alteration task and automatically decreases profits and increase banks funding costs for liabilities.

Furthermore, in addition to banks capital and liquidity management, Basel III introduced a set of supplementary requirements which form the risk management framework and contribute to the shaping of banks risk management strategy. The risk management framework work around the risk-based capital and liquidity

requirement as protection from potential threats which may arise from banks daily activities. The risk management framework work as follows around banks capital and liquidity requirement

5.2.1.6 Capital Adequacy Assessment Process framework (ICAAP Framework)

The severity of the last financial shock unveiled the depth of inadequate and low-quality capital in the banking sector. Banks were forced to develop their capital base when it was most challenging to raise adequate quality capital. Moreover, growing high-quality capital does not appropriately cover all risks, which leave weaknesses in banks risks identification and assessment process. Basel III saw closing these gaps in risk management as paramount importance and raising banks' elasticity during stress period by improving the ICAAP framework. According to BCBS (2016), a useful ICAAP framework includes a clear assessment of the risk to capital, risk governance, and risk escalation process, translating to effective risk management strategy and a practical risk limit system.

Basel III Pillar 1 capital adequacy is designed to confine operational, market and credit risk. However, as a financial organisation, the bank is also significantly exposed to risks, arises from its strategic decision, compliance level, and business model. Basel regulators have implemented. Pillar 2 consider risks that are not included in Pillar 1. Under Basel III, banks must develop an inclusive ICAAP framework to measure their capital allotment's overall sufficiency based on the critical risks that their banks business model is open to. Mr Raihan, the assistant Vice-president of AE bank, stated that their ICAAP framework is integrated with his banks business strategy.

“We have developed a capital planning strategy To implement the Basel III ICAAP framework. ICAAP is aligned with our overall strategic business planning to identify and mitigate risks around our core capital and risks that arise from the strategic decision-making process. Capital planning is a continuing development process reviewed regularly by the risk manager, and amendments are made as necessary.”

Another participant Mr Dipu, a senior executive of bank AF, stated that they had tested their ICAAP framework in different scenarios before applying it into their business model to ensure adequate protection from strategic risk.

“It took us over four years to develop ICAAP. During this time, we have tested our loss absorption capability in different worst-case stress scenarios to ensure that ICAAP is aligned with our business strategy rather than one-time compliance exercise as per Bangladesh Bank’s guidance.”

Most BCBs have implemented the ICAAP framework as per regulatory requirement. Bangladesh Bank regularly monitors the ICAAP report to ensure that the ICAAP framework is compliant with BCB’s strategy. Senior Executive officer of AH bank, Mr Aziz, added

“Bangladesh Bank regularly reviews and evaluates AF banks’ ICAAP report and their strategies to ensure the ICAAP framework is compliant with the CAR requirement as per Basel III requirement. ICAAP is important for banks because it emphasizes having a dialogue between the regulator and banks, rather than being simply a one-sided compliance framework.”

The first respondent stated that they use the ICAAP framework as a strategic decision-making tool. The second respondent said that the ICAAP framework prepares them for the worst-case stress scenario. The third respondent viewed the ICAAP framework as an essential compliance framework as well as an opportunity to increase communication between the regulator and the bank

5.2.1.7 Risk data aggregation and risk reporting

Basel III also enhanced banks superiority of governance and procedures concerning risk data management. Lack of data integration to senior management, especially when they need it most, can deteriorate crisis (Deloitte, 2015). Under Basel III rules, risk data management must be considered and deal with within the financial organisation's contingency plans. As the risk data aggregation and risk reporting processes are closely related to Basel III's other dimensions such as governance, risk data aggregation, and risk reporting, banks must critically ensure that risks are managed efficiently throughout the organisation.

5.2.1.8 Risk governance

An effective and efficient risk management framework requires strong corporate governance (BCBS, 2016). Basel III issued detailed guidelines on the board and

senior management's roles and responsibilities and suggested that it is codified in the Banking Act. Effective corporate governance is the key to an efficient risk management framework. The ICAAP framework, risk data aggregation and risk reporting, and other critical dimensions of the risk management framework are expected to discuss and approve by corporate governance. Therefore, banks need an effective and efficient corporate governance to ensure that banks integrated risk management framework deliver quality, on time and relevant risk reporting to the senior management through risk data management and the ICAAP framework.

5.2.1.9 Stress testing and scenario analysis

To enhance risk management practice in banks, almost all previous Basel regulations developed by BCBS emphasised banks' need to define, implement, run and analyse robust stress testing and scenario analysis (Deloitte, 2015). The idea behind stress testing and scenario analysis is to check and ensure banks financial strengths and capability to absorb shocks in different scenarios. BCBs need to submit their stress testing and scenario analysis report twice a year to BB. One of the respondents, Mr Raihan, added

“In a stress test scenario, we assume a serious macroeconomic downturn for at least three years’ duration. The CET1 capital ratio in the stress test provides a point of departure for AE bank’s board of directors for assessing AE bank’s capital needs. Although the ICAAP is a “bottom-up” stress test, we also conduct annual “top-down” stress tests on AE banks capital in different risk scenarios using our model.”

Mr Raihan further added

“[...] AE bank scheduled to do stress testing and scenario analysis twice a year (June and December) and send a detailed report to BB.”

It is understood that Basel III want to increase banking industries resilience and accountability by introducing different risk measures and requirements. According to Mr Raihan, risk management is not just a framework but a part of banks' strategic decision-making tool to fetch real-time risk management data to banks' upper management lever. Assistant General Director of B bank stated that B banks'

capital position is governed by risk management within the bank. Therefore, to maintain a better capital position, effective risk management policies are essential. As per respondents opinion, BCBs adopted Stress testing and scenario analysis as strategic decision-making tools rather than a risk-management feature.

To ensure a safe credit policy, BB has introduced a new benchmark for sound risk management practice and increased its supervision of banks to ensure that banks follow benchmark standards and are compliant with the Basel III risk management framework. Therefore, to develop a safe credit policy, efficient risk management is necessary. Executive Vice President of P bank Mr MD said that Basel risk management policies helped them develop a safe credit policy.

“Risk management policies that Basel III places are to ensure that banks have a safe credit policy. We are not implementing Basel III risk management framework to develop [our] credit policy but to develop our credit policy, and we are implementing Basel III risk management framework.”

Mr Dipu acknowledged strong risk management is vital to protect banks capital

“Good capital position reflects a bank's risk resilience capacity while banks' capital position depends on better risk management. So, indirectly Basel III regulation has emphasized maintaining better risk management system as a safeguard to banks capital.” -

Basel III introduced new technical components in the existing risk-management framework so that banks can identify risk factors in advance. However, as per respondents, BCBs embraced these changes and implemented them into their strategic decision-making process to develop a safe and secure credit policy. The decline in NPL among PCB also suggests that BCB starts to benefit from the Basel III risk management framework. According to Bangladesh Bank (2014), Basel III has made the following technical changes in the existing risk management framework by introducing the following policies:

- (a) Basel III has enhanced credit risk management by including an additional capital charge specifically for Credit Value Adjustment (CVA) risk to capture market-to-market credit losses caused by the deterioration of the counterparty's creditworthiness to improves the credit risk management system;

- (b) Basel III has enhanced liquidity risk management by making liquidity coverage ratio and net stable funding ratio as mandatory to prescribed level;
- (c) Basel III has improved foreign exchange risk by increasing the higher capital requirement for higher net foreign exchange position;
- (d) On top of the operational risk capital requirement, Basel III has introduced strict internal control policies so that banks can keep operational risk under control; and
- (e) Basel III has regulated interest rate risk by using capital as a shield against trading book amount.

5.2.2 Structural changes in the risk management framework

Basel III introduced several structural changes in its existing risk management framework. Bangladeshi commercial banks have established a separate risk management division, according to Basel III guideline, which was a risk management unit previously. This risk management division oversees six core risk areas, i.e. credit/investment risk, internal control and compliance risk, money laundering risk, asset-liability management risk, foreign exchange risk, and information technology risk (Bangladesh Bank, 2014).

Figure 5.15: Risk management in the bank (source: www.combank.net)

5.2.2.1 Risk management division (RMD)

RMD is the operational unit of risk management in a previously known bank known as the risk management unit. RMD should have a separate desk for each core risk, and the executive risk management committee directly reports to the chief risk officer that is also the head of RMD. The respondents have seen a separate risk management division as a significant structural change in risk governance. Senior Executive officer of Z bank, Mr Pritam, stated

“Basel III focuses on to reduce systematic risks associated with banks’ operations. Recently, we have formed a separate management level risk management division to monitor and identify risks associated with six-core risk areas [...] to identify and monitor risks [...] and report to the executive risk management committee.”

A senior executive of R bank, Mr Isha, said

“[...] we have established a separate risk management division (RMD). [...] RMD reports to the executive risk Management Committee. RMD [is responsible for] identify, monitor and mitigate six core risk areas. Each core risk area has a separate risk management desk and follows specific procedures to ensure that systematic risks are identified and monitored.”

A similar response was received from the vice-president of A bank

“A bank used to have a risk management unit. In 2015, we established an Independent Risk Management Division (RMD) designed as per the guidelines provided by Bangladesh Bank DOS Circular Letter No. 13 (Sep 2015). RMD activities cover banking operation from top to bottom under Chief Risk Officer (CRO).”

All respondents agreed that they have a new risk management division to oversee the risk management process. They viewed these recent changes as positive because a separate RMD made the risk management process most effective. Before RMD, Bangladeshi commercial banks only had a risk management unit to control banks’ risk management system. New RMD combined six core risk management team under one division. It is evident from the above analysis that respondents have seen establishing a separate risk management division to oversee risk management procedure from a risk management unit as a significant structural change in the risk management framework.

5.2.2.2 Board risk committee (BRC)

Board members comprise BRC. RMD present and communicate the findings of ICAAP, stress testing report, risk appetite statement report to the BRC. The senior executive officer of X bank stated that they follow a top-down method for risk mitigation. BRC provides strategic direction to RMD, and the management level risk management team implement those directions from the board-level committee.

“P bank sets risk appetite, and risk responsiveness of the bank [and] provide strategic direction [...]. On the other hand, the management-level risk management committee is responsible for implementing risk policies and procedures in line with the strategic direction and risk appetite specified by the board.”

5.2.2.3 Asset Liability Committee (ALCO)

Commercial banks use the Asset Liability Committee (ALCO) to oversee banks' risk exposures related to asset, liability, and liquidity. RMD identify and monitor risk exposures and pass to Asset Liability Committee (ALCO). ALCO prepare and implement action plans to mitigate risks identified by RMD. Executive Vice President of P bank, Mr MD, stated that

“ ALCO receive reports from risk management division and assesses risks related to assets, liabilities, and liquidities. You can say ALCO is like an antivirus in our banking system, which continuously assesses SIBL's risk exposure.”

The above discussion indicates that Basel III increased the quality of banks risk-based capital and improved safeguarding by introducing strict risk management policies and risk governance. Respondents stated, a full risk management division to oversee six core areas a significant change in their existing risk management framework. Respondents also expect that the integration of risk management strategy with strategic decision making and other risk reporting also improved communication and supervision between BCBs and national supervisor BB.

5.2.2.4 Risk management structure and risk appetite

Institute of International Finance (2011) defined risk appetite as different types of risks and their aggregate levels which financial organizations assume within their controlling capacity to achieve their strategic objectives and business plans. Senior Supervisors Group (SSG) have a similar but more robust definition of risk appetite. It

defined risk appetite as the level and types of risk financial organizations exposed to and assume that those risk types and risk-taking levels are within their risk exposures' limit and business activities, considering their business objectives and obligations to stakeholders (Senior Supervisors Group, 2010). Therefore, risk appetite is different types of risk and their associated risk level that an organization assumes it can control to achieve its goals and objectives.

Respondents stated that Basel III had introduced different risk parameters for critical risk evaluation to ensure banks' risk appetite is kept under control. These parameters include assessing risk at portfolio and industry level, self-assessment risk report, the introduction of risk appetite report, etc. Basel III has emphasized controlling risk appetite to minimize banking losses and to increase banks' profitability. Senior Assistant Manager of V bank Mr Naim states that

“Basel III framework has introduced new concepts like risk appetite in portfolio level, industry level, etc., as well as [procedures] to identify [banks'] key risk indicators, [guidelines]. It prepares action plans for those [identified risks] and introduced new risk parameters for liquidity. It helps banks to [make] better [risk] projection and management of their inherent and unforeseen risks.”

Some respondent's stated that risk appetite control is an integrated process in banks' risk management strategy and is controlled by using those risk management procedures/guidelines to make better risk prevention. Moreover, it was pointed out that the RMD overseeing banks six core risk area is vital for monitoring and controlling BCBs risk appetite. According to the X bank's assistant manager Mr Bulbul, X bank took a structured approach toward controlling risk appetite. It combined management and governance to ensure that the risk appetite of core risk areas is set to a level aligned with his bank's pre-set risk exposure level.

“A sound risk management strategy needs an implementation of risk appetite strategy. A risk appetite strategy is a [combined] structured approach to governance, management, measurement, monitoring and control of risks. [.....] Therefore, in line with Basel III risk management policies and Y banks overall [risk] strategies and objectives, we set our risk appetite that specifies risk tolerance limit, capacity and overall readiness to take the risk.”

Furthermore, Basel III has introduced a risk review process by the RMD for each risk parameter to ensure that identified risk factors are dealt with immediately to control risk appetite and provide a rapid response to identified risks. The assistant vice-president of N bank addressed this issue as follows

“To control banks risk appetite against each [risk] parameter, multiple review process has been introduced by Basel III such as preparation of risk appetite statement and regular review of those states by the RMD. Furthermore, multiple system analysis processes introduced by Basel III To set a standard risk appetite control system. Examples are trend analysis, Bangladesh Central Bank benchmark, and international banking benchmark for further risk analysis.”

The above respondents saw controlling risk appetite as an integrated process in the risk management framework to control banks’ risk-taking. Moreover, respondents view different risk parameter and risk handling procedures introduced by Basel III as positive to control their banks’ risk-taking.

The existing literature argued that losses reduce banks’ profitability, and most bank losses result from non-performing loans (Keeton and Morris,1987; Haneef et al., 2012). Therefore, to control non-performing loans, banks must control their risk appetite. One of the earliest studies examined the relationship between banks’ risk appetite and profitability conducted by Keeton and Morris (1987). They analysed losses data from 2,470 insured commercial banks in the USA from 1979 to 1985. Using non-performing loans net of charges as the primary measure of the losses, they found that US commercial banks with higher risk appetite recorded higher non-performing loan losses. Keeton and Morris (1987) suggested that risk appetite and non-performing loan losses are related. To reduce the number of non-performing loans, they indicated that banks control their risk appetite. Several studies which followed Keeton and Morris (1987) have proposed either similar or other explanation behind non-performing losses. Ahmed (2006) reported that NPLs in Bangladesh is influenced by three major factors, i.e. loan credit terms, banks’ risks preference and microeconomic shocks. Haneef et al. (2012) suggested that banks’ risk management system's weaknesses give rise to the number of non-performing loans and reduced banks’ profitability. Therefore, a comprehensive risk management system is necessary to ensure a structured risk appetite framework to reduce bank losses.

Although respondents said that Basel III's improvements in their existing risk management system help them make better lending decisions by reducing credit risk related to lending, recent reports suggest an increase in NPL. There were considerable irregularities in distributing loans which led to a rise in NPL, which put pressure on banks' profit and capital (Mallick, 2018). From 2014 to 2017, six state banks have distributed BDT 1407 billion as a loan, and BDT 373 billion (29.25%) of the total amount was recorded as default. Simultaneously, private banks have distributed BDT 6030 billion as a loan, and BDT 294 Billion (4.87%) was marked as default (Mallick, 2018).

Figure 5.16: Historical NPL of Bangladeshi Banks (World Bank)

This evidence suggests that private commercial banks could minimize their NPL while state banks failed to safeguard or failed to identify potential credit risk associated with their lending.

Figure 5.17: Net NPL rate of different BCBs (Sarker et al., 2017).

Therefore, it can be argued that this higher NPL rate of state bank may be more associated with state banks' operational errors rather than risk management fault.

5.2.3 The NPL situation among BCBs

NPLs originate from uncertainty and corruption, i.e. authorising a loan to unworthy parties. Both uncertainty and corruption have a detrimental effect on the Bangladeshi banking sector's growth (Kumar, Hossain and Islam, 2020). Research suggests that higher NPL in the Bangladeshi banking sector is due to political instability, corruption, poor governance (Banerjee et al., 2017)(Alam, Haq, & Kader, 2015). According to the published data, BCBs reported a 9.92% gross NPL ratio in 2016, 10.13% in 2017 and 10.78% in 2018 (Table 5.16). The lowest NPL was recorded

between 2016 to 2018 was April 2016, and the highest was in October 2018.

Figure 5.18: Gross NPL ratio from 2016 - 2018, Source: (Kumar, Hossain and Islam, 2020)

Furthermore, the gross NPL was higher among SCB compared to PCB. In 2015, the gross NPL among SCBs was 21.80%, and PCBs was 8.090%. Since 2015, the NPL of SCBs gradually increased to 28.24% in April 2018, while PCBs gross NPL stood to almost the same at 6.01% (table 5.15).

Figure 5.19: SCB gross NPL 2015-2018. (Source: Kumar, Hossain and Islam, 2020)

Figure 5.20: PCB Gross NPL 2015-2018 (Source: Kumar, Hossain and Islam, 2020)

As of Mar 2018, FCBs reported gross NPL to 7.01%, which decreased by .03% compared to the previous quarter. FCBs reported an all-time high NPL of 9.56% in Mar 2017 and a record low of 7.01% in Mar 2018 from 2015-2018 (figure: 5.19).

Figure 5.21: The FCBs gross NPL 2015-2018. (Source: Kumar, Hossain and Islam, 2020)

Separating NPLs according to the bank's types from the first quarter of 2018 to the fourth quarter of 2019 shows, both PCBs and FCBs had NPL greater than 5% of total outstanding loans while SCBs had a massive NPL excess of 30% of total outstanding loans (Table 5.10). While Development Finance Institutions (DFI) NPL continued to fall from 33.12% in June 2014 to 17.80% in June 2019. While DFIs share of NPL as a percentage of total NPL continued to fall, SCBs NPL percentages continued to rise from 23.23% in June 2014 to 31.60% in June 2019.

Figure 5.22: Gross NPL by banks type 2014-2019 (Source: Khatun and Saadat, 2020).

Such high percentages of the continued increase in NPL in SCB's year by year suggest that NPL is a problem related to SCBs rather than PCBs, FCBs or DFIs.

The first reason provided by the participants for the high NPL in the Bangladeshi banking sector was poor management and corruption. According to MR Khan

“Poor management, along with corruption, has contributed to the highest level of NPL in BCs, especially among SCB. Although SCBs have established lending norms, SCBs have been awarding loan based on political ground and personal relationship. Although general creditworthiness assessments are present in those SCBs, routine assessment of the potential risks associated with the borrower does not carry out by them”.

Raihan further supported these perceptions by stating that

“SCBs judge creditworthiness mainly by political worthiness. Consequently, having a good political connection is perceived to be the only requirement to obtain a large loan from SCB's. In addition to that, it seems that the government tends to fund loss-making state-owned enterprises using SCBs have pushed this NPL situation among SCBs even further.”

One banker Mr Parth claimed policymakers are responsible for SCBs NPL situation

“The severity of high NPL among SCBs has been underestimated by the Bangladeshi policymakers. Although stakeholders have expressed their concern and low confidence on SCBs regarding the current NPL situation in the Bangladeshi banking industry, the policymakers have done a little to tackle NPL growth in SCBs.”

Another participant, Mr Shujon, stated illiteracy is one of the reasons behind NPL

“We received a huge number of a loan application from start-ups. Many of those applicants are micro/small business owner and financially illiterate. The majority of them have no general knowledge of how interests are charged and how they will pay back loan interest if their business venture fails to generate any income.”

One participant added that banker’s lack of attention also contributes to the NPL. Mr Dipu stated that

“Bangladeshi banking sector is a target-oriented industry. Our credit assessment department receives hundreds of credit application every day. To achieve the weekly target, sometimes bankers do not analyse and fine-tune the loan applications. As a result, loans are granted to a less credit-worthy person or potential clients are denied access to credit.”

It is evident from the above discussion; participants think the NPL situation is worst among SCBs for several reasons. Following findings are drawn based on participants responses

1. The common causes of NPL are choosing the noncreditworthy loan applicant. SCBs judges’ credit applications merit based on political influence rather than general credit assessment norms by Basel regulation. It is evident that SCBs deliberately fail to recognise the actual borrower and intentionally lend to unfit borrower due to political pressure/moral hazard problem.
2. Micro/small business customers become defaulter because of their lack of knowledge of financial products. Although they do not have any lousy loan default intention, they default because of a lack of financial literacy.
3. The aggressive, corrupt, and target-oriented banking industry indirectly contribute to the increase of NPL. The bankers do not check loan application

appropriately due to pressure to achieve their target, and as a result, loans are authorised to those who are not creditworthy.

This finding suggests that the SCBs have a culture to assign loans to those loan applicants with political backup. Corruption while judging creditworthiness among BCB's seems to be a significant contributing factor towards high NPL in Bangladesh. The NPL negatively affects banks' day-to-day operation and profits because BCBs need to keep surplus provision next to the defaulted loan, which unswervingly reduces their earnings.

5.2.4 Application of agency theory

Since banks are the most critical financial intermediaries worldwide, governing and monitoring banks activities and performances receive significant attention from the public and bank regulators. (Stankeviciene et al., 2012). Therefore, any disturbance in the banking sector could primarily affect the Bangladeshi economy as a whole. By principle, the BB is the de facto authority in the Bangladeshi banking sector, the supervisory agent delegated by the people of Bangladesh and the government to supervise and implement monetary policies to regulate the Bangladeshi banking sector. Information asymmetry and lack of supervision often lead to managerial opportunism. Therefore, the effectiveness of Bangladesh Bank's governance depends on the monitoring system's efficiency to identify and mitigate opportunistic behaviour of BCBs. However, Kamal et al. (2007) argued that to ensure the independence of BB as a national banking supervisor and to ensure good governance in the Bangladeshi banking industry, the critical challenge is to provide the autonomy of BB from political influence as well as a robust legal endorsement for the national supervisor. Although BB, as an agent, gradually implemented corporate governance's best practice in the Bangladeshi banking section to reduce systematic risk to minimise opportunistic managerial behaviour, they are still not free from the Bangladesh government's political influence. Political forces on BB by the Bangladesh government was observed in a recent series of financial loan scam by Hallmark group by BDT 400 billion, Basic bank loan scam by BDT 450 billion where the loan was given to without proper documentation. BB, as the national supervisor, allowed them to trade as a bank as of now. These are just a few examples that help the vast NPL situation grow further.

Furthermore, BB has lost its independence since the Bangladesh Ministry of Finance established its banking division (Islam, 2017). Therefore, the BB has freedom as an institution but don't have full independence in creating monetary policy. Due to the lack of autonomy in formulating the monetary policy and political pressure, the BB as a supervisory agent sometimes fails to prevent the poor performance by the BCBs and systematic risks that give rise to the loan default culture and financial frauds.

Bangladesh banking industry is regulated by the Banking Companies Act 1991 and regulated by Bangladesh Bank. However, both the Ministry of Finance (MoF) and BB supervises SCBs and Specialised Development Banks. On the other hand, the Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission are responsible for monitoring and overseeing Corporate Governance (CG) guidelines for all listed companies in Bangladesh, including banks. Therefore, there are plural supervisory authorities that regulate the Bangladeshi banking industry. Moreover, BCBs are not free from the prototype of the family business. According to Suzuki and Hasan (2018), there is a loophole in appointing independent directors in the bank's board of directors. They observed that the sponsor director and the executive director's relatives or peer circle nominate most PCBs independent the MoF appoints SCBs independent directors. Suzuki and Hasan (2018) suggested that this conflict of interest lead to weak management in credit risk management resulting in high NPL and other financial fraud.

The CG code was developed to protect shareholders interest from opportunistic managerial behaviour through a governance mechanism system (Suzuki and Hasan, 2018). Moreover, CG is expected to improve BCBs financial performances. However, studies find that CG has no significant impact on enhancing BCBs financial performance. Islam et al. (2015) studied the effect of CG on BCBs financial performance. They found that CG does not always guarantee better economic performance in BCBs. The recent increasing trend of NPL accumulated by BCBs and financial fraud also support this finding. Although Basel III prescribed higher capital requirement for better financial stability and a risk management framework to reduce financial fraud, it was evident that loans are authorised based on political connection and personal relationship rather than necessary documentation. These moral hazard problems among BCBs, especially in SCBs,

contribute to the Bangladeshi banking industry's high NPL rate. Respondents stated that due to the ineffective supervision by BB, political influence and moral hazard problem contributing to the high growth of NPL number in the Bangladeshi banking industry. One respondent, the CEO of AF bank, Mr Dipu, stated

“Basel III emphasises on protecting banks risk-based capital by improving and strengthening banks risk management structure. But the effectiveness of the risk management framework depends on BCBs willingness to follow guidelines and corruption within the industry, especially the moral hazard problem among SCB’s.”

Another respondent, Mr Raihan, stated

“A strong risk management strategy means nothing if the board committee introduces policies but do not enforce them throughout the organisation. A well-structured capital and risk management policies do not work in practice if lending is based on political connection rather than banks lending checklists.”

Both participants agreed that a comprehensive risk-management policy does not work in practice if guidelines are not followed at the operational level. So the non-compliance in risk-management procedures are due to political influence and ineffectiveness of the national supervisor, the Bangladesh central bank.

As the principle, society delegates the task to supervise the Bangladeshi banking industry to the Bangladesh government, who, in turn, empowers the commission to BB, a specialised agent. Therefore, society is the principle, and the Bangladesh government is the Principle agent. Thus, BB is the agent of the principal-agent: the Bangladesh government's context. This double delegation creates information asymmetry between the principal and agent relationship. Therefore, both principle and principle agent have imperfect information about their agent's actions, in this context, the financial supervisor.

Given that the financial supervisor has the specialised knowledge to supervise the Bangladeshi banking industry, society can't monitor both agents' complete performance. Furthermore, the agent has a duty of confidence. As a result, the agent cannot disclose any information obtained from their supervisory activities to the main principle: society. Therefore, due to the duty of confidence and information

asymmetry, the principal-agent can pursue their self-interest and maximise principle agents own goal. Moreover, financial supervisors may also work for their interest by accepting influence from the party who powerfully control their career- the politicians who are the principal agent in this context. According to Dijkstra 2010, this situation might result in regulatory forbearance, i.e. bureaucratic self-capture. Regulatory tolerance was observed in the Bangladeshi banking industry. As the financial supervisor, BB allowed several BCBs to keep operating despite noncompliance with the regulation in authorising the loan, resulting in huge NPL and financial fraud in Bangladeshi banking history.

5.2.5 Impact of risk management on lending

Lending is the primary source of credit risk in any financial organization. Although other credit risk sources to banks such as banking book or trading book activities, lending remains the primary source of credit risk and significant income sources. Credit risk management's success depends on the level of risk management policies and procedures in place (Zeller, 2001). According to Zeller (2001), an effective credit risk management system (CRS) minimises non-performing loans and identifies potential credit risk related to the lending proposal. CRS gathers borrowers' information for lenders, identifies warning signals requiring lenders' attention, and helps lenders resolve emerging credit problems, making credit risk management necessary for lenders. When respondents were asked about Basel III's risk management framework's impact on their lending, it was noted that respondents agreed Basel III risk management policies reduced the number of non-performing loans, improved the lending decision process, and helped them make better lending decisions. However, this wasn't the case for SCBs

AGM of C bank, Mr Alim, stated that an integrated risk assessment process has made it easier for his bank to reduce NPL and make better lending decisions based on the risk assessment process.

“Every lending decision goes through credit risk assessment [...]. This assessment process starts with the relationship manager and final approval from the Credit Review Team at the head office. Under our current credit risk management checklist, credit risk assessment made it easy for us to take a better lending decision

and reduces non-performing loans by identifying an early sign of credit default during the assessment stage.”

Mr Alim is the AGM of a well-known SCB. The researcher contacted Mr Alim again in September 2020 regarding his statement of the NPL situation. However, he refused to comment on why SCBs have high NPL if the risk-management system helps them make better lending decisions.

Executive Vice President of P Bank Mr MD, whose bank has an excellent default rate of below 5%, further added that Basel III forced banks to develop a safe lending checklist by monitoring credit assessment through RMD.

“As you know, the bank takes a deposit and lends to the customer to make money, making lending an important part of banks’ daily activities. [Credit] Risk management checklists that Basel III places are to ensure that banks have a safe credit [lending] policy which RMD monitors.”

Executive vice-president of Q bank, Mr Islam, also support Mr MD by adding

“[Credit] Risk management structure [guidance’s] keep banks risk appetite under control by selecting borrowers who have an excellent rating or previous credit history and to take better lending/investment decisions.”

Senior Executive of Y Bank Mr Mizan stated that the Credit Risk Management Unit (CRMU) oversee credit processing in Y bank. CRMU monitor and aid local SME/Corporate lending unit by advising on the prospects of loan applications, such as the probability of default of a loan application received by the SME/Corporate lending unit. This CRMU and local lending team's alignment helped them make a better lending judgment and reduce NPL.

“CRMU monitor finance authorization within the company alongside with corporate/SME team. They closely monitor finance applications and advice on their future merit to control C Bank’s risk appetite and credit risk exposure under control. This alignment together helps C Bank to take a good lending decision and reduce non-performing loans.”

Although Mr Mizan said that CMRU helped them to take a better lending decision and also helping them to reduce NPL, Y bank is one of the largest specialised state

banks that has a massive number of NPL and default rate above 33.9% in 2018/2019 financial year.

If risk management strategy helps banks make better lending decisions to reduce their NPL, do Bangladeshi SCB have such a high NPL? Respondents blamed corruption, moral hazard problem and ineffective supervisory action. One respondent, Mr Aziz, stated

“[...] Basel III emphasises on protecting banks risk-based capital by improving and strengthening banks risk management structure. But the effectiveness of the risk management framework depends on BCBs willingness to follow guidelines and corruption within the industry, especially the moral hazard problem among SCB’s.”

Mr Raihan stated

“A strong risk management strategy means nothing if the board committee introduces policies but do not enforce them throughout the organisation. Well-structured capital and risk management policies do not work in practice if lending is based on political connection rather than banks lending checklists.”

Mr Shujon further added

“PCBs and FCBs are doing a fantastic job in implementing Basel III. Most PCB/FCBs are compliant with Basel III capital, liquidity and risk management requirement. As a national regulator, BB supposes to supervise and take action against non-compliance, but they are not free from political influence. “

From the above analysis, it is evident that an effective risk management structure is vital to reduce NPL and credit default. Still, effective risk management cannot work in practice if BCBs cannot free themselves from corruption, moral hazard, and adequate supervision from the national supervisor. Respondents from SCB think that the risk-management policies are helping them to take better lending decision, but SCBs are the ones who have huge NPL. Other respondents blamed moral hazard, corruption and lack of supervision rather than weaknesses in the risk management framework.

The above findings regarding the relationship between credit risk management and non-performing loans are in line with the initial results in this area by Morton (2003).

Morton (2003) argued that non-performing loans are caused by weak credit evaluation criteria, ineffective risk acceptance policies and erroneous financial indicators. Morton (2003) suggested that effective and robust risk management policies can improve banks' financial performances by reducing non-performing loans. Furthermore, Haneef et al. (2012) also found that banks' risk management system's weaknesses increased non-performing loans and reduced banks' profitability. This finding suggests that Basel III credit risk management guidelines enabled Bangladeshi commercial banks to reduce NPL and increase their profitability. This evidence also indicates that private commercial banks are more efficient in lowering NPL with Basel III credit risk management guidelines. The relevant comparison here is with state-owned banks in Bangladesh based on the NPL data published by Bangladesh bank (Mallick, 2018).

Although BCBs have implemented Basel III credit risk management policies to ensure safe lending, it is evident that some BCBs are using credit risk management policies as a shield to meet their RWA capital requirement. Several respondents stated that they are concerned that banks may use safe lending as an excuse to lend only to well-rated borrowers to meet their RWA capital requirements. If this is true, lending to high-risk borrowers, significantly SME's, may impact their ability to receive banks' financial assistance. Though Basel III intends to improve credit risk management structure so that banks can take better lending decisions, many banks may use those policies to reduce their risk-weighted assets by lending to high rated borrowers only. Mr Ullah, Senior manager of AB bank, stated

“BCBs may change their lending policies slightly because of Basel III as the banks now will be interested in investing in clients who have a good rating, especially in the SME sector.”

Mr Rahman, the vice-president of F Bank, said Basel III risk management guideline is yet to reflect their lending policies.

“BCBs want to increase profit by lending money.[...] the lending policy of F bank is in line with Basel requirement, but credit rating may play an important role in deciding credit eligibility for a certain client.”

Both respondents stated credit rating plays a vital role in SME lending. The first participant specifically said that banks would be interested in lending to high rated clients, especially in the SME sector. It seems that Basel III has enhanced BCBs' credit risk management policies and provided an opportunity for banks to build a safe credit policy. However, it also created a regulatory loophole that banks may use to deny financial assistance to relatively risky borrowers to reduce their RWA capital requirement. Respondents think that credit risk management policies introduced by Basel III have had a significant impact on lowering Bangladeshi commercial banks' non-performing loans by introducing structural and procedural changes in the risk management framework. Respondents have seen this change as positive, which is also expected to control banks' risk appetite. This finding is also related to the results from existing literature where researchers have also found that controlling risk appetite minimizes losses and maximizes profits by reducing non-performing loans. However, some respondents are concerned that banks may use this opportunity to lend to high rated borrowers to meet their RWA capital requirement.

5.3 Basel III and SME lending

The impact of higher regulatory capital imposed by Basel III can significantly influence SME financing. It was suggested that higher regulatory capital requirement work as a bottleneck to SME lending (Admati et al., 2013). Admati et al., (2013) stated that liquidity shouldn't be confused with capital, and higher capital requirement should not tie up resources which banks could use for lending. Admati et al. (2013) argued that higher capital requirement leads to a higher cost of capital, and banks pass this additional higher cost to borrowers. Therefore, larger corporations may cope with increased finance cost; SME's which are already struggling to raise finance may find it challenging to pay a higher price for their finance.

5.3.1 Interest rate

Typically, larger corporations pay 11% to 16.5% interest for their term loans, whereas banks charge the SME's between 9% and 18% as interest depending on which industry they operate (Bangladesh Bank, 2018). BB has made it compulsory for banks and other financial institutions to charge SME's and agricultural credits at low interest. However, SME's still pays more interest for their loans than corporate lenders (Dhaka Tribune, 2017).

Historically, Bangladeshi commercial banks have always charged higher interest in loans to small enterprises before adopting Basel III. According to BB's historical interest rate data, interest rates for small enterprises lending in 2014 were between 12.5% and 23.75%, whereas medium and large enterprises were charged 12.5% to 18%.

Figure 5.23: Historical SME lending highest interest rate (source BB)

However, interest rates gradually declined from 2014 to 2018 for both small and medium/large enterprises. According to Bangladesh Bank historical loan data, small enterprises were charged between 9% and 18%, whereas medium/large enterprises were charged between 8.5% and 16.5% in 2018

Figure 5.24: Historical SME lending lowest interest rate (source: Bangladesh Bank)

The historical interest rate for lending to small enterprise suggests that BCBs consider lending to small enterprises as high-risk. As a result, BCBs always charged high interest in SME lending.

Miles, Yang and Marcheggiano (2012) suggested that Basel III's capital restriction may result in higher financing costs for SME's. They indicated that capital requirement could bottleneck banks' lending streams. Banks can't lend SME's without increasing their RWA capital requirement, limiting lending scopes to SME's and rising cost of finance is most likely to be paid by borrowers. Although the above analysis found evidence that SME lending is most likely to result in higher RWA for banks, it was evident that Bangladeshi banks have reduced their SME lending interest rate.

5.3.2 Credit rating

SME ratings' objective is different from corporate ratings because SME credit rating passes information to lender or borrowers, creates awareness to SME entrepreneurs, and advises them on overcoming their inability to improve their financial situation over time. Credit rating helps SMEs to increase their confidence and require less time for the lending decision. High-rated SMEs enjoy the benefit of higher credit rating by having access to low-interest-rate lending, which provides a substantial financial service to SMEs. The excellent rating also enables SMEs to increase their organisational efficiency by ensuring access to finance and attracting talented employees. Moreover, the rating makes the lending process more manageable for banks to take a lending decision quickly. Without a credit rating, SMEs get the loan after all the bank process after getting lending assurance from the borrowers, i.e. after assessing collateral values. This lengthy process hampers the lending process and obstacle SMEs organic growth. An excellent credit rating also increases SMEs negotiation power to reduce the interest rate.

In Bangladesh, credit rating can cost SME's between BDT 10,000 to BDT 70,000 (\$130-\$850) (excluding vat) depending on their loan amount (different loan amount requires different levels of credit rating). Moreover, SME's need to pay 80% to 90% of their initial credit rating cost as a subscription fee each year if they want to continue their ratings (Emerging Credit Rating, 2018). There are several credit rating agencies currently working in Bangladesh that does both corporate and SME credit

ratings. Credit rating starts with checking SME's business documents such as an annual report, daily accounts and visiting SME's premises to ensure its physical presence. Credit rating agencies then further analyse SME's business position, including operational efficiency, financial risk analysis, management capabilities, etc. (Emerging Credit Rating, 2018). Thus, when banks receive SME's loan application, they have all documents ready, making the lending process more straightforward. Although credit rating represents an extra cost for SME's, respondents saw credit rating beneficial for both banks and SME's. Mr Ziad, the assistant vice-president of K bank, stated that credit rating is useful for both parties.

“Basel III bought all SME's under credit rating system, which not only helping SME's to understand their business position but also helped us to offer risk-based finance towards SME's based on their rating.”

Another respondent, Mr Kamal, stated that credit rating helps them understand SME's business need better.

“[...] previously, banks had to deal with information asymmetry, especially with small businesses' finance assessment. SME credit rating enabled SME's to organize their supporting documents for banks to get a better understanding of their business needs.”

Mr Shifum also supported the above respondent and added that credit rating reduced lending decision time.

“It is true that the cost of getting finance has increased for SME. Expenses such as documentation and credit rating fees for an extra cost, but if you look at the positive side that credit-rated SME's all necessary documents ready for loan application weren't the case previously. This process not only helps them to keep their record organize but also helped us to make a swift decision on [their] loan application.”

It is noticeable that respondents think credit rating reduces their workload and loan processing time by ensuring that SME's have required bank loan documents before loan application. Respondents stated that credit rating benefits include risk-based lending, quick decision, and easy understanding of SMEs finance needs. However, the last respondents mention an opposing side of credit rating, which is increase cost

for SME's. Credit rating requires a yearly subscription which cost between \$130 to \$1000 on top of regular finance costs. The above suggests banks are mostly benefiting from credit rating rather than SME who need to bear the cost.

Respondents were also asked about unrated SME's. They said unrated SME's could seek financial assistance from banks. Still, unrated SME's pay extra cost on top of their usual finance cost and some banks advise them to seek finance as unrated SME because of the lower risk weight assigned to unrated SME compared to poor rated SME. The executive vice-president of P bank, Mr MD, stated-

“Unrated SME's can have access to lending, but they must pay a higher price for it. Usually, an unrated SME pays BDT 50p for every BDT 100 given as a loan plus their usual interest charge.”

Besides higher interest costs, unrated SMEs have difficulties finding loans. The L bank's executive vice-president, Mr Rabbul, said they usually do not offer to lend to low-rated SMEs but prefer unrated status compared to low-rated SMEs.

“If an SME has a poor credit rating, we don't normally offer them loans. However, in some exceptional cases, we might still offer them finance [...] we advise them not to credit rate because unrated SME's have risk weight from 75% to 100% [comparing to SME 5 or SME 6 [120% to 150%].”

Credit rating increased borrowing costs for SMEs. But respondents think that credit rating reduced decision time and improved banks lending process by ensuring that their lending applications are organised so that banks have everything they need to make their lending decisions effectively. Moreover, credit rating also helps SMEs to understand their weaknesses and how to overcome them. It is understood that banks prefer higher credit rating when it comes to SME lending. Bank charge higher interest rate for poor/unrated SME's and bankers also suggest low rated SMEs apply for a loan as unrated to benefit from less RWA capital requirement. This process also indicates that banks are desperate to earn money using the credit rating process by lending to those who are not worthy of a loan.

5.3.3 Impact of a credit rating on SME lending

Banks often find SME lending too expensive than the return rate due to the higher cost involved in assessing SME's creditworthiness and the increased operating cost

involved in the lending process. Furthermore, many banks also see SME's as too risky and prone to loan default. Basel III introduced mandatory credit rating assessment for SME lending to reduce the cost and time required for banks to assess SMEs loan applications and assess SMEs' riskiness. Basel III's credit assessment process is supposed to make SME lending profitable for banks by reducing the cost and time related to SME lending application. Credit assessment agencies help mitigate information asymmetry between banks and SMEs by providing a proper rating to SMEs. SMEs credit rating assessment also suggests how SMEs can arrange their quantitative data and give a clear idea of weakness along with a recovery plan. Therefore, credit rating can play a vital role by observing SMEs' creditworthiness and helping SMEs by suggesting the proper guideline.

One of the respondents, Mr Ullah, stated that Bangladeshi commercial banks might not be interested in investing in low-rated SMEs because of the high-risk weight associated with low-rated SMEs.

“Most of the SME businesses in our country are not that much-documented, and book of accounts are not maintained properly. As a result, lending to unrated /bad rated (SME 4, SME 5, SME 6) SMEs should increase the RWA / CAR of the banks adversely. In this case, banks may reduce SME lending, especially during Basel III implementation stage.”

According to Mr Ullah, bad credit rated or unrated SME's may suffer because of their credit rating. He thinks it will cost banks more RWA to offset loans given to them, and due to higher RWA, banks may become very selective and demand very high-value collateral for loans to low rated SME's to minimise their RWA. Mr Ullah's opinion suggests that banks may prefer to lend to high rated SME's and turn down loan application from low rated and unrated SME to comply with Basel III requirements. Another banker Mr Ziad also suggests that banks may be interested in lending to high rated SME's

“It [Basel III] positively changed our policy towards SME's. Basel III bought all SME's under a credit rating system which not only helped SME's to understand their business position but also helped us to offer risk-based finance towards SME's based on their ratings. Lending to high rated SME's also requires less RWA capital,

and as a result, many banks are interested in lending high rated SME's to keep their RWA to a minimum.”

According to Mr Ziad, many BCBs are interested in lending to high rated SME's to reduce their RWA, suggesting that low-rated SME or small enterprises may fall behind when seeking finance from banks. Furthermore, one respondent said that banks might prefer to lend to high rated SME's compared to corporations because of the low-risk weight assigned to high rated SME. Mr Alim stated-

“Risk-based pricing is a parameter where interest rate, as well as risk weight of a loan, depends on SMEs credit rating. Although it is not established, it is assumed that banks prefer to lend SME's [high rated SME's] compared to corporate [low rated] lending for two reasons. Firstly, SME lending is guaranteed by high-value collateral, which reduces the probability of future non-performing loan. Secondly, high rated SME lending reduces risk-weighted assets, which translated to reduced minimum capital requirement.”

It is observed that respondents think BCBs may abuse SME's credit rating system for their benefit to minimise RWA minimum capital requirement. One participant even said that banks might prefer to lend high rated SME's compared to low rated corporations. Therefore, it is understood that BCBs sees two essential requirements SMEs need to have for easy access to finance. Firstly, SME's need to have a good credit rating so that banks require less RWA capital for SME lending. Secondly, SME's need to provide high-value collateral so that banks can offset their RWA capital requirement using collateral value.

Basell II assigned a fixed risk weight of 75% to all SME lending which seemed unfair compared to corporate borrowing, which was a minimum of 20%. BCBS (2011) stated Basel III introduced various risk weight based on credit rating so that SMEs receive fair treatment from the bank under Basel III. However, it is evident BCBs are using credit rating based risk weight to reduce their RWA capital requirement.

5.3.4 Risk-based capital requirement and SME lending

According to the “Guidelines on Risk-Based Capital Adequacy”, BB (2014) stated that all Bangladeshi schedule banks should use the Standardised Approach for calculating credit risk. In the Standardised Approach, SME's with higher credit rating

will be assigned less risk weight, and lower credit risk weight generates less credit risk capital requirement. On the other hand, low rated SMEs are given a higher risk weight than the highest rated SME's. However, unrated SME's were assigned lower risk weight than SME's, which have a lower or poor credit rating. The following table shows Bangladesh Banks' credit rating and their relevant risk weight for SME credit risk calculation.

Exposure Type	Bangladesh Bank's Rating Grade	Risk-Weights (%)
Corporate	1	20
	2	50
	3,4	100
	5,6	150
	Unrated	125
SME	SME1	20
	SME2	40
	SME3	60
	SME4	80
	SME5	120
	SME6	150
	Unrated (small Enterprise < BDT 3.00m)	75
	Unrated (small Enterprise having >_BDT3.00m & Medium Enterprise)	100

Table 5.25: SME's risk weight Source: Bangladesh Bank (2014).

According to Bangladesh Bank's published corporate/SME lending risk weight (Table: 5.19), SME's will be assigned a risk weight from 20% to 150% based on their credit rating. However, unrated SME's can still seek finance. Yet, they will be assigned 75% risk weight for small enterprises with less than BDT three million (\$37K) yearly turnovers and 100% risk weight for unrated SME's that have over BDT 3 million annual turnovers. The above table suggests that it is better to have no credit rating than a bad credit rating. On the other hand, corporate loans have been assigned a risk weight between 20% to 150% risk weights based on the credit rating. According to Basel III, banks can set 75% risk weight to the small enterprise with less than BDT 3 million yearly turnovers. Banks' retail portfolio is diverse, and no outstanding loan exceeds BDT 100 million (\$1M) (Bangladesh Bank, 2014).

Consequently, the above risk weight has a massive impact on banks' capital requirement to offset SME loans.

For example, XYZ enterprise has a good credit rating (SME 1) which attracts 20% risk weight for credit RWA capital charge. XYZ enterprise seeks BDT 100,000 from ABC bank. The credit RWA for XYZ enterprise is BDT 20,000. However, when SME lending is secure by eligible collateral, banks calculate the net credit risk exposure amount by valuing collateral values and subtracting it from the initial lending amount to find banks' net exposure amount. If the new exposure amount is positive, the counterparty's risk weight is applied to the credit RWA exposure amount for collateral backed up SME lending. For example, if XYZ provides an asset as collateral valued at BDT 70,000 for his BDT 100,000 loan, the credit RWA of ABC bank for lending to XYZ is BDT 6,000 $\{(100,000-70,000) \times 20\%$. Similar loan to SME's under Basel II would have RWA exposure of BDT 22,500 $\{(100,000-70,000) \times 75\%$. This calculation suggests that credit rating is important. Still, SME's can improve their chance of getting finance from the bank if they provide high-value collateral, reducing banks' RWA exposure. Furthermore, it was evident that SME's credit rating-based risk weight can also reduce bank RWA capital requirement compared to Basel II.

Under Basel III, the way banks treat SMEs depends on the banks' approach, i.e. standardised or IRB approach. The risk-based capital adequacy guideline, published by BB, stated that BCBs must adopt the standardised approach for calculating risk-based minimum capital (Bangladesh Bank, 2014). The standardised approach requires banks to classify their risks exposures under different categories, i.e. retail/corporate and established a risk weight based on SMEs' credit rating by external credit rating agencies. For both approaches, banks must always use the risk-weight function introduced by Basel III for calculating their risk-based capital requirement.

According to Basel III, banks' risk-based capital requirement for lending depends on borrower's credit ratings and collateral values. Therefore, as per Basel III, riskier borrowers are most likely to experience the most damaging effect of risk-based capital requirement because lending to riskier borrowers demands higher risk-based regulatory capital (Bonino et al., 2011; Schizas, 2011; OECD, 2012). Moreover, it was argued that higher regulatory capital requirement might also negatively impact

banks' ability to lend, especially to SME, because lending to SMEs is considered high risk (BarbaNavaretti, Calzolari and Pozzolo, 2015). Firstly, the risk-based capital requirement can work as a bottleneck to banks' capital as banks can't lend to SME's without increasing their risk-based capital requirements (see the formula in section 2.3.5.1), which limits banks' lending scopes to SME's (Admati et al., 2010). Secondly, lending to high-risk borrowers increases banks' minimum capital requirement, discouraging banks from lending SME's.

As mentioned in the literature review chapter, lack of high-value collateral, lack of credit history, and lack of proper documentation negatively impact Bangladeshi SME's access to finance and credit ratings. As credit rating and collateral values are the critical indicators for banks risk-based capital requirement for SME lending, respondents were asked what impact Basel III risk-based capital requirement has on banks' borrowing towards SME's. Responses from 28 interviewees are divided into three categories. 32% think Basel III risk-based minimum capital requirement has had a minimum or no influence in their lending towards SME's. Out of nine participants who said the risk-based capital requirement has minimal effect on their lending, seven participants were from SCB, two participants from state specialised banks. The majority of the respondents (61%) think that Basel III risk-based capital requirement significantly impacts their SME lending portfolios. Seventeen participants said risk-based capital requirement negatively moved their SME lending portfolios, twelve of them were from PCB and five participants were from FCB. Only 7% have said that due to Basel III risk-based capital requirement, they saw minor changes in their lending towards SME's.

Figure 5.26: Participants perception of risk-based capital and SME lending

Mr Rahman, the AGM of a well-known SCB F bank, stated that Basel III risk-based capital has little impact on their SME lending.

“Basel framework has [had] little impact on the lending criterion in SME lending in F bank. The actual merit of a lending application is judged based on collateral provided by the borrower. Hence, those SMEs seeking bank finance and can provide high-value collateral, accepted by F bank. For SME’s who has a lower credit rating, their collateral value must 75% or above their lending amount. In this way, we keep a balance between SME lending and risk-based capital charge.”

Another respondent Mr Anil, the AGM of E bank, also supports Mr Rahman’s view

“In reality, SME lending requirement remained almost the same as before. Collateral values determine the fate of an SME loan application. Poor credit-rated SME’s have a higher chance of a loan if they provide high-value collateral that exceeds their borrowings”.

Mr Abid, who is the AGM of D bank, stated

“SME lending must be backed up by high-value collateral. Credit rating is necessary to fulfil lending requirements, but good collateral is mandatory. We prefer high collateral values compared to high credit rating because SME lending backed by high collateral values reduces loan default probability”.

The above three respondents from SCB saw collateral value as the driving factor in SME lending compared to credit rating because they think high-value collateral reduces the chance of loan default. However, SCBs have the highest loan default rate among BCBs. Although SCB respondents stated high collateral value could secure lending to SMEs, it was evident previously that SBS authorised loans based on political connections rather than credit rating or collateral value. Hence, risk-based capital requirement and risk management strategies may have little impact on SCBs SME lending.

Unlike SCBs, PCBs and FCBs respondents said Basel III changed their SME lending requirements and process. According to BCBS (2010), SMEs credit ratings reduce credit default probability and reduce banks’ risk-based capital requirement because of various risk weight. Therefore, BCBs are interested in lending to SME’s, which

have a higher credit rating to continue SME financing and reduce their risk-based capital requirement at the same time.

According to Mr Pritam, the senior executive of M Bank, SME loans are assessed based on SME credit rating and collateral value. SME's with a lower credit rating, banks are reluctant to lend because of low/unrated SME's increased risk-based capital for banks.

“SME loan applications are assessed based on collateral quality and credit rating. [...] Banks are also less interested in lending unrated or low rated SME lending because it increases their risk-weighted assets.”

.Another respondent, Mr Islam, stated

“[...] lending to low rated SME/corporate borrowers generates higher risk-based capital for banks. Risk-based capital discourages banks from lending to poor rated SME's. However, Basel III takes account of collateral value while calculating risk exposure; many banks will consider poor rated SME's loan application as long they provide high-value collateral to secure their lending.”

Mr Raihan further added

“Using collateral to minimise risk-based capital for SME lending stays the same in Basel III compared to Basel II. Banks may use this opportunity to curtail risk base capital related to SME lending by selecting well-rated SME's.”

So it is clear that both SCB/PCBs see collateral value is one of the critical factors for SME lending. Previously, Basel II assigned a fixed risk weight of 75% to SME's, but Basel III introduced different risk weight from 20% to 150%. Basel III also offers banks an opportunity to reduce their risk-based capital requirement, i.e. risk exposures taking account of SMEs credit rating. However, SME's with low credit rating can still increase their prospects for loans by providing high-value collateral. This may be why respondents from PCBs/FCBs stated that they prefer higher credit ratings to keep risk-based regulatory capital to a minimum because SME lending's collateral requirement remains the same as Basel II.

From the above discussion, it is evident that Basel III has made a change to their SME lending requirement. SCBs prefer high-value collateral compared to credit

rating, while PCB/FCB prefer higher credit rating and collateral value to reduce their risk-based capital requirement. Moreover, SCB participants said risk-based capital requirement did not bring any changes to their SME lending. Consequently, SCBs preference for high-value collateral over credit rating may answer why most SCBs are failing to meet Basel III minimum capital requirement since they started to implement Basel III. Therefore, these lending changes to SME's may be favourable for only some SMEs, specifically those with excellent credit rating and can provide high-value collateral. Low rated, or unrated SME's still have access to lending but can provide high-value collateral.

The possible reason behind PCBs/FCBs preference to lend to good rated SME's may be related to the risk-based capital requirement. SME lending is high-risk, costly and more prone to credit default (Liang et al., 2017). Thus, there are two possible reasons why PCBs/FCBs are more willing to lend high rated SMEs than low rated SME. Firstly, PCBs/FCBs want to reduce the risk of lending default. Secondly, PCBs/FCBs wish to keep their risk-based capital requirement to a minimum level by including high-rated SMEs in their lending portfolio. That's is why most PCBs/FCBs has a capital adequacy ratio of over 10%, and SCBs have below 9% (Please see NPL section at the beginning of this chapter).

Recently, BB has ordered all BCBs to keep SME lending interest rate to a single digit (The Independent, 2018). It means that banks have to change bellow 10% loan interest to all SME lending. The reduction in interest rate may sound fair to SMEs, but it also negatively affects their finance access. Previously, banks compensated low rated SMEs by charging a higher interest rate and high-value collateral. As banks can't change over double-digit interest rate to SME lending under new rules, it is most likely to turn down low rated SMEs finance application.

In the existing literature, it was found that when regulatory capital requirement goes up, banks shift their investment from high-risk but higher-return to low-risk but lower return investment to substitute capital increase (Bernanke and Lown,1991; Berger and Udell, 1994; Naceur and Roulet, 2017). The above findings match with Admati et al. (2010), who stated higher regulatory capital adversely affects banks' lending conditions to SME's. Furthermore, BarbaNavaretti, Calzolari and Pozzolo, (2015) said that higher regulatory capital negatively impacts SME lending by banks because

of the higher risk weight associated with SME lending. Beck, Clerc and Rochet (2015) also suggested that market friction most likely to create a significant gap in banks' capital structure, which could have a reasonable impact on banks' lending to SMEs because of Basel III higher capital requirement. Consequently, banks may move to low-risk borrowing to keep their RWA to a minimum. As a result, BCBs may invest in high rated SME, especially during the implementation stage.

5.3.5 Basel III and SME's access to credits

It is said that SME's are the backbone of the Bangladeshi economy. The SME sector plays an excellent role in alleviating poverty in the country by providing employment opportunities to millions of unemployed Bangladeshis (Alauddin and Chowdhury, 2015). Like any other developing country, SME's limited access to finance is the critical constraint to this sector's growth. It is estimated that about 6.0 million SME's currently active in Bangladesh contributes to 25% of total GDP, employing approximately 31 million people and providing 75% of total household income in Bangladesh (Alauddin and Chowdhury, 2015). It was also estimated that SME's accounted for 80% to 85% of industrial employment and 23% of total employment in Bangladesh (Chowdhury, 2008). Undoubtedly, SME's plays a vital role in Bangladeshi economic development.

Bangladeshi SMEs mainly relies upon three primary formal sources of finance to cater to the financing needs (Alauddin and Chowdhury, 2015). They are commercial banks, NGOs (micro-finance) and the stock market. Although SMEs, as a start-up enterprise, usually are self-funded, they gradually moved to other formal sources for their financial needs. SMEs also relied upon informal sources such as co-operative societies and private lending. SMEs are financed in bank loan, over-draft, leasing, hire purchase agreement and venture capital. Throughout all stages of SME's life cycle, SME's require access to appropriate finance sources for their creation, survival and growth. Although SMEs access to formal finance source somewhat recovered from the last financial crisis, the current Covid-19 pandemic situation mostly hit hard them again.

While interviewing SME entrepreneurs, participants start-ups were self-funded, which they either inherited or took a loan from their family members. Gradually, their businesses have grown up, and banks' financial assistance has become their

primary external sources of finance after internal source. However, one participant (Sahmim Nakib) stated that he usually does not seek finance from banks for more extensive financial assistance because of the high-value collateral demanded by the bank as a deposit that he does not have.

“Normally, I don’t go to the bank for a loan because it is hard for me to get a large amount of loan from the bank. Banks also require a land asset as collateral which I don’t have, and entail extra expense such as processing fees, legal fees which I don’t need to spend in other sources that I’m currently using.” Nakib (Owner/manager of J F International, M, 52 Y, 11 employees).

Mr Nakib added that he uses either private lender or co-operative society for his business’s financial needs. Private lenders are those who have idle money, and they lend it for short and long-term. Typically, a personal lender charges interest higher than the bank deposit rate but lower than banks’ lending interest rate. According to Mr Nakib, private lending is an excellent finance source because a private lender earns more return on his money than what he would have made from a bank deposit, and the borrower pays less interest than what he would have paid for a bank loan. Small business owner Mr Nakib stated

“Personal lenders are those people who have money and willing to lend you in high interest. [...] For example, if a private investor has BDT 1Crore in the bank, he gets 4% to a maximum of 6% interest on his money. But if he lends me, I will give him 12% to 13%, where I normally pay 16% to 22%. [...] I’m paying less interest comparing to banks, and less documentation is needed to get this loan.”- Nakib (Owner/manager of J F International, M, 52 Y, 11 employees).

Mr Rahman is the finance director and shareholder of Bashabo General Hospital & Diagnostic Centre (BGH) at Dhaka. Nine years ago, Mr Rahman and his partners established BGH and raised their capital using private equity. They have also used to hire purchase to acquire their medical instruments.

“We didn’t need any bank finance because partners’ self-funding covered our capital needs”. - Rahman (Finance Director/Shareholder, BGH, M, 58 Y, 130 employees).

Although Mr Rahman and his partners didn't seek finance at the beginning of their business establishment because they didn't need it, many SME's don't seek any finance during start-up because they knew they would be denied finance. Md. Mahfuz, founder/CEO of Egaroshindur (Group) Ltd, established his poultry firm 18 years ago with only five thousand BDT (approximately \$55). The initial capital was given to him by his father as a loan. He didn't seek any finance from the bank because it was difficult for start-ups to get a bank loan without collateral deposit and nearly impossible in the rural area. However, he received financial assistance from micro-finance organizations at a high-interest rate and provided his father's livestock as collateral.

"It was nearly impossible to get a start-up loan at that time even if you have provided collateral because of the uncertainty [associated with his business] and remoteness of location [business location]. The only institutional finance I could get at that time was micro-credit in exchange for my father's live-stock as collateral. "- Rahman, (Founder of Egarosindur (Group) Limited, M, 39 Y, 190 employees).

Although it is impossible to conclude that Bangladeshi start-ups start with self-funding, all participants stated that their start-up business was funded by their self-fund, friends, and family and gradually moved to other formal funding sources. Difficulties in gaining access to bank funding without proven financial and operating history, self-funding is the only option available to them.

5.3.6 SME loan type

There are two types of loans available to SME's in Bangladeshi as follows:

5.3.6.1 Term loan

The amount of SME Term loan depends on the quality of collateral provided to banks by the borrowers. Depending on banks' policy and SME's credit rating, BCBs typically offer 75% to 200% of the collateral value as a loan. However, the agreed loan amount is given in two phases to the borrower, i.e. term loan (long-term) and cash credit loan (short-term). 70% of the total loan amount is provided as a term loan usually used for business expansion to meet long-term working capital needs, i.e. to purchase equipment and 30% as cash credit to meet daily financial needs, i.e. creditors' payment. Borrowers need to pay term loan every month within a fixed time

limit. Cash credit loans can be withdrawn using a bank card/cheque and are charged daily interest by the banks.

5.3.6.2 Short-term loan

Sometime SME's need short-term cash, and this type of loan is normally for six months to up to three-year duration. The loan amount for short-term loan amount normally from BDT 500,000 (\$5K) to BDT 500,000,0 (\$50K). Most BCBs offer collateral-free short-term SME loan up to BDT 500,000. Respondents suggest that short-term loan application success depends on SME owner's personal relationship with the bank, previous credit history, and business size. Instant loans can be processed within a short time (typically within a few hours to a day) and do not require any collateral as a guarantee.

5.3.7 Personal relationship banking

Personal relationship banking is a strategy used by many banks to build up customer loyalty and offer different products from a single point of service (The daily star, 2018). In personal relationship banking, customers can take advantage of personal relationships with banks by obtaining more favourable loan terms/rates. Berger and Udell (2000) found that access to finance is more difficult for SME's than larger firms due to information asymmetry. As a result, SME's need to develop a close relationship with banks to know more SME information. However, the "small bank advantage" hypothesis suggests that smaller banks are more efficient in serving SME's than larger banks due to their simple organisational structure and advantages in soft processing information (Berger et al., 2005). Cole et al. (2004) stated that larger banks prefer to lend SME's based on problematic financial details compared to smaller banks. Berger and Udell (2002) think larger banks prefer to lend based on inappropriate financial information because of agency issues within their organisational structure.

Although the above empirical evidence shows that it is relatively more straightforward for SME's to gain finance access by building a personal relationship with banks, this research found that access to finance through relationship banking is still difficult for small enterprises. Respondents were asked about relationship banking. Respondents stated that they have a good relationship with their bank. Yet, only medium-sized enterprise owners/managers were confident that they would be

granted an instant loan before finishing their current payback based on their previous history and personal relationship with their bank. Mr Hossain stated

“[...] I have been with my bank for the last 17 years. As a good customer, it is relatively easy for me to get finance from banks. [...] If I need a smaller amount, such as BDT 20 lack (\$21K) [...], I don't have to provide any documentation. It is only possible because of the trust I have in our relationship.” – Hossain (Owner/manager, Radiant Group, M, 59Y, 182 employees).

Adil, a small business owner, has been granted a short-term loan based on his family's relationship with his bank's manager.

“Short-term small bank loan depends on your relationship with the bank. I have a good relationship with my bank as my father, and my uncles have financial ties with the same bank. However, in Bangladesh, relationship banking is essential [for small businesses to get a loan.]” - Adil (Owner/manager, Godhuly Knitting Apparel, M, 29Y, 21 employees).

Mr Adil also added that he had been granted a short-term loan for his business while taking a long-term loan from the same bank.

“My local bank manager knows my whole family and myself. Recently, I needed a BDT 500,000 for my business purpose. My bank authorised it in a couple of hours. All I needed a cheque guarantee from my father.” - Adil (Owner/manager, Godhuly Knitting Apparel, M, 29Y, 21 employees).

While the above respondents said they could get a short-term loan from their bank, this isn't true for everyone because of their credit history or a good relationship with their bank. Mr Nakib stated he must rely upon his credit card facility or usual informal credit sources such as personal lenders for short-term financial needs.

“I have a good relationship with my bank, but they won't authorise me a short-term loan without collateral. Therefore, I use my business credit card or ask a private lender for money.”- Nakib (Owner/manager of J F International, M, 52 Y, 11 employees).

The above analysis shows that for SME's who have an excellent personal relationship with the bank, it is relatively more straightforward for them to get a short-

term loan if they have an established credit history. While relationship lending is somewhat easier for medium-sized SME's than small-sized SME's, it was also evident that relationship lending is still complicated for small entrepreneurs. It was also apparent that medium-sized SME's, who have a good relationship with their bank, enjoy collateral-free short-term loans from banks. Though some respondents stated that short-term loans depend on established credit history and personal relationship with banks, it doesn't seem to work in practice for small enterprises that still need to provide collateral for short-term loans. Therefore, one can conclude that BCBs prefer medium-sized SME's and established credit history for collateral-free short-term lending.

5.3.8 SME loan application process

SME's term loan application process starts with a credit rating by external credit rating agencies. Along with credit rating, SME's need to submit their business documents such as trade licence, VAT/TIN (Taxpayer Identification Number), CIB (Credit Information Bureau) report etc., along with collateral deposit documents. Once the bank receives the above documents, they assess the value of the collateral. After an initial assessment, if SME's fulfil the bank's loan requirement, it offers a loan based on collateral value. Banks provide from 75% to 200% of the collateral value as a loan based on the quality of the collateral provided.

On the other hand, SME's need to submit a trade licence, VAT/TIN (Taxpayer Identification Number), CIB (Credit Information Bureau) report for a short-term loan. Collateral requirement depends on lending amount as well as SME's circumstances. It was evident that 40% of the respondents' first loan application was

Figure 5.27: First-time loan application rejection

rejected by the bank while the bank accepted 40% of respondents' first loan application. The remaining 20% never applied for the bank's loan. Although the sample size is too small to reach any constructive conclusion, it indicates the rejection rate among Bangladeshi SME's by BCBs.

5.3.9 SME's cost of finance - the moral hazard problem

From April 2020, SME loan interest rates became a single-digit interest rate for a secured loan as instructed by BB. Previously, BCBs used to charge from 13% to 21% for SME loan. Although a reduction in interest rate is favourable for SME's, respondents stated the cost of finance related to SME lending is very high. Following is Mr Adil's lending experience from the bank.

Mr Adil owns a small enterprise with only 19 employees. According to the contractor's specifications, Mr Adil does contract jobs that include knitting fabrics using cotton, dyeing, and cutting materials. In 2019, he was granted BDT 15 million (approximately \$155k) as a loan from his bank for buying new knitting equipment. Based on Mr Adil's experience, BDT 15 million loans from the bank cost him BDT 1.1 million (approximately \$11k), which is 7.3% of his initial loan amount. This loan cost excludes interest cost but includes surveyor cost, legal cost (both non-refundable), cost of credit rating, insurance cost, and other documentation costs. He spent BDT 500,000 (approximately \$5.5K) to fulfil the lending requirement and BDT 600,000 (roughly \$6.5K) as a bribe to the different layers of bank management. Although the

respondent claimed his family has a good relationship with the bank, he provided high-value collateral. Yet, he had to bribe bank management for BDT 15 million SME loan.

“Total cost of my loan was BDT 11 Lac (\$1.2K) for BDT 15 million. I’ve paid the surveyor’s cost, legal cost (both non-refundable), credit rating cost, insurance cost for my factory and machinery, BDT 500,000 and the remaining BDT 600,000 I’ve paid to bank management as a bribe so that they sanction my loan. However, I had good CIB report, SME 2 credit rating as well as providing high-value collateral as a deposit.” - Adil (Owner/manager, Godhuly Knitting Apparel, M, 29Y, 21 employees).

It is evident, although Mr Adil had a good credit rating, an excellent personal relationship with the bank’s management and provided high-value collateral as a deposit, he had to bribe the bank’s management for his SME loan. Other respondents have also mentioned a similar cost of getting a loan from banks apart from bribery. One respondent also expressed concern regarding the time banks take to process a loan. He said that it could take up to four months for banks to process a loan application.

“Nowadays, seeking finance from bank became too much bureaucratic. Sometimes it takes up to 4 months for the bank to respond to an application which means I will finish my construction 4 to 6 month late. This cost me money as I need to pay my construction workers’ wages although I don’t have any work for them.” - Baten (Finance Director, Radiant Group, M, 43 Y, 182 employees).

Although many respondents have mentioned that Basel III risk management policies were able to cut down loan application time and speed up the loan decision making process, SME owners have experienced delays rather than quick decisions, as stated previously. Furthermore, bankers said that the Basel III risk management framework most likely to reduce credit risk in lending. Evidence suggests that the moral hazard problem among bank management is high. Moreover, SME entrepreneurs getting a loan from the bank indicates that having a high credit rating and high collateral value is not enough for some bank, as Mr Adil had to bribe bank management for his loan. Lastly, although some bankers said that Basel III risk management framework policies helped them reduce loan application and lending decision-making processes, SME’s are still experiencing long waiting time for a loan.

Chapter 6 Empirical Analysis

This chapter aims to answer the last question based on empirical analysis. The empirical data was collected from 36 BCBs annual report, and the date ranges are from 2012 to 2019. This section analysed sampled BCBs capital shortfall and dividend policies using financial data from their annual report. Furthermore, three generations of nine banks were selected randomly out of 36 sampled banks to analyse the impact of Basel regulation on BCBs financial performances. Nine banks financial data were obtained from their annual report.

6.1 Capital shortfall

According to The Daily Star (2017), the Bangladeshi banking system's total capital was estimated at BDT 844.24 billion in the first quarter of 2017. Although some state/private commercial banks are struggling to maintain minimum capital requirements, the Bangladeshi banking sector's total capital surplus was estimated to BDT 23.3 billion during the first quarter of 2017 against a total capital shortfall of BDT 119.3 billion (Murtuza, 2020). In the first quarter of 2018, the Bangladeshi banking sector's capital shortfall was BDT 147.6 billion against the capital surplus of BDT 31.2 billion (Murtuza, 2020). However, in 2019, the total capital surplus increased to BDT 38.6 billion against a capital shortfall of BDT 160.01 billion (Murtuza, 2020).

Figure 6.1: Sampled BCB's compliance with Basel III capital requirement. (Source: self-created)

Although most PCBs/FCBs complied with the regulatory capital requirement, only a few SCBs suffered from capital shortfall since BCBs started implementing Basel III. However, the number of SCBs that failed to maintain minimum capital requirement increased gradually from 2014 to 2019. The financial statement analysis of 36 BCB out of 58 BCB revealed four BCBs was unable to meet the Basel II minimum capital requirement in 2014. Two out of four banks that failed to meet Basel III minimum capital requirement were SCBs. In 2015, the number of non-compliant SCBs doubled to four and further increased by one to five in 2016. In 2017, the capital shortages continued among existing SCB, and this number has gone up by one SCB from six to seven SCBs. However, in 2018 the number of capital default among SCBs decreased by one to six from seven SCB. The number of capital default among SCBs remained the same in 2019.

On the other hand, the number of non-compliant PCBs was a minimum of two banks to a maximum of four banks from 2014 to 2019. However, two out of four banks continually defaulted from 2014 to 2019. The number of non-compliant regulatory capital among SCBs increased to four in 2018 and fell to two PCBs in 2019. This comparison between SCBs and other banks shows that Basel III has a different financial impact on SCBs and PCBs. Moreover, none of the FCBs out of 36 sampled BCBs failed to raise the required capital, which tells that FCBs are in a solid financial position compared to SCB/PCB.

6.2 Dividend policy

According to Basel III, banks' CET 1 capital must be 4.5% of total RWA and total Tier 1 capital must be at least 6% of the total risk-weighted asset. Furthermore, banks need to raise CCB every year to 2.5% by 2019, which must also be made of CET 1. Therefore, to increase Tier 1 capital, BCBs must increase their reserve funds, such as retained earnings and issue new shares. However, using retained earnings or issuing new equity to raise CET 1 capital is non-preferable by shareholders.

As the company owners, shareholders have one common goal: to maximize profits in both the short and long-run. So, how might banks' capital and shareholders goal be related? As mentioned earlier, the amount of money bank' need to keep as capital depends on total RWA and banks' RWA exposure depends on the riskiness of banks' operations. Therefore, banks' capital requirements go up or down with

banks' total RWA. For example, if lending goes up, banks RWA goes up, and as a result, banks need to increase their Tier 1 capital. According to Basel III, CET1 must be 4.5% of the total RWA. Therefore, banks need to issue new share to increase their Tier 1 equity capital or transfer profits to retained earnings to fulfil Basel III requirement. However, shareholders do not want banks to issue new shares because the bonus share dilutes their investment values.

Figure 6.2: Sampled banks dividend payment from 2014 to 2019

The financial statement analysis evident that 24 out of 29 banks paid a dividend in the form of cash/bonus share in 2014, whereas five banks didn't pay any dividend in 2014 (Figure 5.25). In 2015, 6 out of 29 banks didn't pay a dividend, which increased by 13 and 16 bank to 19 and 22 banks in 2016 and 2017. The number of non-dividend paying banks increased by 2 in 2018 and dramatically decreased by 14 banks to 10 banks in 2019. Further financial statement analysis also revealed that most BCBs made a profit from 2015 to 2019 (except SCBs), but only a few, mostly FCBs, offered dividend to their shareholders. Instead of paying out cash dividend to shareholders, most PCBs either paid no dividend or paid bonus share as dividends and used profits to fulfil the CET1 requirement. Seven SCBs out of sampled 36 BCBs were excluded from the above analysis because they are 100% owned by the Bangladesh government. The above indicates how banks are meeting the CET1 capital requirement.

6.3 Financial ratio analysis

Financial ratios have been used to measure a company's financial performance and compare financial data from financial statements to reveal its economic performance. Financial ratios have been used to measure the financial performances and their relationship with Basel III implementation. This section is based on nine (9) BCB's data for the period from 2012 to 2019. Nine (9) banks are selected randomly from thirty-six (36) sampled banks and are divided into three age group based on their established date. The following bank's financial data were gathered from their financial statement and used for financial ratio analysis

Before 1991	1991-1999	1999-2010
1st Generation Banks	2nd Generation Banks	3rd Generation Banks
City Bank	Bank Asia	BRAC Bank
Islami Bank	Dhaka Bank	Premier Bank
AB Bank	NCC Bank	EXIM Bank

The following ratios have been calculated to perform financial analysis to examine whether implementing Basel III demonstrate better financial performances.

Ratios	Formula	comments
Profitability Ratio		
Return on Assets	$ROA = \text{Net Profits after Tax} / \text{Total Assets}$.	Higher ROA point to healthier financial performance/asset utilisation.
Return on Equity	$ROE = \text{Net Profits after Tax} / \text{Owners' Equity}$.	Higher ROE indicates better financial performance. However, it may also mean higher leverage.
Return on Deposits	$ROD = \text{Net Profits After Tax} / \text{Total Deposits}$.	An upper ROD ratio indicates enhanced lending utilisation.
Liquidity Ratios		
Cash and Bank balance to deposit	$CBBDD = \text{Cash and balances at the central bank and other banks or financial}$	A higher ratio indicates better liquidity.

	institutions / Total Deposits.	
Efficiency Ratios		
Assets Turnover	$AT = \text{Total Revenue} / \text{Total Assets.}$	A higher AT ratio indicates better asset utilisation.
Operating Efficiency	$OE = \text{Total Operating Expenses} / \text{Total Operating revenue.}$	Low OE indicates the bank is efficiently generating more operating income by reducing expenses.
Solvency Ratios		
Debt to Total Assets	$DTA = \text{Total Debt} / \text{Total Assets.}$	Higher DTA is an indication of banks financial leverage.

Table 6.3: Ratios for financial analysis

6.4 Financial performance of different generation banks

A statistical tool such as mean and standard deviation provides an opportunity for the objective measure of opinion and a basis for comparison. A lower standard deviation value indicates that most numbers are close to the average, while a high standard deviation value suggests that the numbers are spread out. The financial performances of three generations of banks are as follows

Ratio	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Profitability Ratio				
Return on Asset (%) (ROA)	1.19	0.51	0.5	2.37
Return on Equity (ROE) (%)	13.56	5.97	4.25	28.65
Net Profit Margin (%) (NPM)	20.63	6.45	8.91	31.69
Liquidity Ratio				
Cash & Bank Balance to Deposit %	14.37	3.21	10.26	21.63
Efficiency Ratio				
Asset Utilization (%) (AE)	5.67	1.14	3.85	9.14
Operating Efficiency (%) (OE)	48.82	6.32	35.74	59.7
Solvency Ratio				
Debt to Total Asset (%) (DTA)	90.87	2.64	84.57	93.98

Table 6.4: Financial ratios of the 1st generation Banks (2012-2019).

Ratio	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Profitability Ratios				
Return on Asset (%)	1.36	0.65	0.38	2.95
Return on Equity (%)	12.74	4.86	4.29	25.35
Net Profit Margin (%)	24.21	7.86	8.68	41.8
Liquidity Ratios				
Cash & Bank Balance to Deposit (%)	11.01	3.88	8.51	21.56
Efficiency Ratio				
Asset Utilization (%)	5.4	0.89	4.3	7.87
Operating Efficiency (%)	40.96	7.22	27.74	55.98
Solvency Ratio				
Debt to Total Asset (%)	89.44	1.71	84.81	91.56

Table 6.5: Financial ratios of the 2nd generation Banks (2012-2019).

Ratio	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Profitability Ratios				
Return on Asset (%)	1.29	0.61	0.31	3.21
Return on Equity (%)	15.9	7.13	5.32	38.8
Net Profit Margin (%)	21.95	8.15	4.96	42.25
Liquidity Ratios				
Cash & Bank Balance to Deposit (%)	14.94	6.23	7.48	28.07
Efficiency Ratio				
Asset Utilization (%)	5.87	1.16	4.14	8.12
Operating Efficiency (%)	45.08	6.28	32.4	54.88
Solvency Ratio				
Debt to Total Asset (%)	91.91	1.13	89.4	94.15

Table 6.6: Financial ratio of 3rd generation banks (2012-2019).

6.4.1 Discussion

A mixed performance is evident among the selected generation of banks in terms of profitability ratio. It is observed that second-generation banks could generate more Return on Asset (ROA) and Net profit margin (NPM) than other generations. However, third-generation banks outperformed other peer groups in terms of Return on Equity (ROE). Therefore, it is fair to conclude that the first generation banks are not as near other peer groups in terms of profitability. For liquidity position

measurement, cash in hand and bank balance to deposit ratio was considered. It was evident that third-generation banks have a better liquidity position and held better solidity than other groups.

Ratio	Mean (2012-2019)		
Profitability Ratio	1st Generation	2nd Generation	3rd Generation
Return on Asset (%)	1.19	1.36	1.29
Return on Equity (%)	13.56	12.74	15.9
Net Profit Margin (%)	20.63	24.21	21.95
Liquidity Ratio			
Cash & Bank Balance to Deposit (%)	14.37	11.01	14.94
Efficiency Ratio			
Asset Utilization (%)	5.67	5.4	5.87
Operating Efficiency (%)	48.82	40.96	45.08
Solvency Ratio			
Debt to Total Asset (%)	90.87	89.44	91.91

Table 6.7: Comparison of Mean between the different generations of banks.

Asset Utilisation (AU) rate and Operating Efficiency (OE) have been considered for efficiency measurement. Although the gap between all generations of banks in terms of AU is not significant, second-generation banks have been able to use their assets more efficiently than other banks. It was also observed that the second and third generation banks had outperformed the first generation banks to achieve OE. Furthermore, the third generation banks achieved significant operational efficiency compared to other banks' generation. In terms of financial solvency ratio, it is observed that all ages of banks have almost similar solvency ratio. However, the second generation banks have demonstrated slightly better solvency compared to other generations.

6.5 Basel standard implementation in banks (2012-2019)

Basel Standard Requirements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Capital to Risk Weighted Asset Ratio (CAR)	11.48	1.8	7	15.42
Tier 1/Core Capital Ratio	8.71	1.13	4.86	10.16
Liquidity Coverage Ratio (2015-2018)	135.59	25.69	101.17	163.22

Net Stable Funding Ratio (2015-2018)	105.45	5.1	100.15	113.35
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Table 6.8: Basel III requirement statistics for first-generation banks (2012 -2019)

Basel Standard Requirements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Capital to Risk Weighted Asset Ratio (CRAR)	12.42	1.22	10.18	15.1
Tier 1/Core Capital Ratio	10.03	1.09	7.82	12.41
Liquidity Coverage Ratio (2015-2018)	129	25.15	103.67	180.99
Net Stable Funding Ratio (2015-2018)	106.4	8.6	95.03	120.56

Table 6.9: Basel III requirement statistics for second-generation banks (2012 -2019)

Basel Standards Requirements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Capital to Risk Weighted Asset Ratio (CRAR)	12.11	1.59	8.11	14.89
Tier 1/Core Capital Ratio	8.92	1.34	6.53	11.94
Liquidity Coverage Ratio (2015-2018)	119.3	11.53	104.29	142.19
Net Stable Funding Ratio (2015-2018)	113.8	4.53	105.92	121.66

Table 6.10: Basel III requirement statistics for third-generation banks (2012 -2019)

6.5.1 Discussion

The comparison of Basel standard implementation among three generations of banks revealed that the second and third generations of banks were better in every aspect of implementing Basel standard than the first generation of banks.

Basel Standard Requirements	Mean		
	First Generation	Second Generation	Third Generation
Capital to Risk Weighted Asset Ratio (CRAR)	11.48	12.42	12.11
Tier 1/Core Capital Ratio	8.71	10.03	8.92

Liquidity Coverage Ratio (2015-2018)	135.59	128.96	119.29
Net Stable Funding Ratio (2015-2018)	105.45	106.39	113.79

Table 6.11: Comparison of mean of Basel III implementation standard

From the mean output of CRAR, It is observed that second and third generation banks are better off in increasing the main component of Basel III compared to the first generation of banks. It is also evident that the second generation of banks is holding a better capital adequacy position than the third generation of banks. Moreover, the second generation of banks has also held a better position compared to others when compared Tier 1 to Core Capital ratio, which was challenging for all banks during the implementation stage. The first, second and third-generation banks Tier1/Core Capital Ratio is 8.71%, 10.03% and 8.92%. It means that the second generation banks have raised their Tier 1 capital significantly compared to other generation banks.

Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR) and Net Stable Funding Ratio (NSFR) are two newly introduced major component in Basel III. The LCR promotes the short-term resilience of banks' liquidity profile and ensures that a bank holds enough liquid assets to survive a period of liquidity stress. Higher LCR indicates a better liquidity profile. The NFSR, on the other hand, ensure that a bank has enough stable funding sources to mitigate future funding crisis. Like LCR, a higher percentage of NFSR indicate better financial stability in the long-term. In terms of LCR, the first-generation and second-generation banks have a better liquidity profile than third-generation banks. However, third-generation banks have demonstrated higher NFSR compared to first and second-generation banks. It means that both first and second-generation banks have better liquidity performance in the short-run. In contrast, third-generation banks held more excellent funding stability than other banks in the long-term.

Chapter 7 Conclusion

As mentioned earlier, Basel III was an immediate response from the Basel Committee on Banking supervision to the last financial crisis. Weaknesses in banks' risk management system and reckless trading by larger banks led the global economy to the last financial crisis. Basel III aims to ensure that banks can manage similar financial distress by themselves without harming the global economy like the last time. To ensure that banks are well backed up by capital, Basel III has increased minimum capital requirement and introduced reforms to enhance banks' risk management system, corporate governance, liquidity and increased supervisory review. The purpose of this research is to find out how Basel III made changes to Bangladeshi commercial banks' capital structures and how those changes affect banks' lending towards SME's.

An increase in capital requirement has put pressure on banks to minimize their RWA by reducing lending to high-risk borrowers. Although, Basel III made it easy for SME's which have the higher credit rating to receive financial assistance from banks but SME's which have lower credit rating and can't provide high-quality collateral is falling behind. However, indeed, SME's access to finance was already a problem in many countries, including Bangladesh, even before the Basel III introduction and implementation. SME's in Bangladesh have lower cash-flow; a high proportion of them have higher intangible assets than tangible assets; thus, they can't provide high-value collateral and consequently have a higher probability of default.

7.1 Summary of result

RQ 1 – How does Basel III affect the capital structure of Bangladeshi commercial banks?

Basel III proposed a similar risk-based approach as Basel II while calculating minimum capital requirement for banks. Basel III's view changes in capital structure represent a significant change in BCBs' capital holding. The majority of the respondents sees these changes in the capital structure as positive and stated that this change would strengthen BCBs' capital structures and loss-absorbing capacities. Although respondents positively welcomed changes in the capital

requirement, they are concern about the method used by BCBs to raise capital. To increase Tier 1 capital, BCBs are using retained earnings and the right shares. However, both ways are not preferable by shareholders because an increase in retained earnings reduces dividend payment, and the right share issue reduces investors' existing investment values.

On the other hand, BCBs are raising Tier 2 capital, mainly using subordinated bonds. Respondents expressed different opinions while asked whether BCBs can raise the required money to meet the minimum capital requirement. It was observed that some respondents think BCBs may struggle during the implementation stage, but they are capable of raising minimum regulatory capital. However, some respondents stated that most PCBs/FCBs are capable of raising new money, but it may be difficult for SCBs to raise money apart from government cash injection. Further investigation on 36 BCBs financial statement analysis revealed that some SCBs were already struggling to meet the Basel II minimum capital requirement. In 2017, all sampled SCBs had capital deficiencies under Basel III. A recent report from Bangladesh Bank also suggests that FCB CAR were the highest among other BCBs and all SCB failed to raise the required minimum capital in 2019.

RQ 2 - How does Basel III improve banks risk management systems, and how it impacts banks' lending?

Basel III introduced new risk management policies and guidance to enhance banks' existing risk management frameworks. Respondents stated that Basel III introduced both structural and procedural changes into the existing risk management framework. It was observed that Basel III prescribed both technical and structural changes to strengthen banks' risk management strategy. Technical changes indicate that new changes are based around banks risk-based capital and liquidity measure. As per the respondent's opinion, technical changes strengthen banks risk management strategy because recent changes are integrated with banks' overall strategic planning to identify, monitor, and mitigate risks.

Furthermore, it was also evident that BCBs implemented a risk management benchmark regularly reviewed by Bangladesh Bank to ensure Basel III compliance. According to respondents, BCBs established a separate risk management division,

board risk committee and asset-liability committee. Respondents recognized the Basel III risk management framework as positive to control banks' risk appetite. They think different risk parameter and risk handling procedures introduced by Basel III positively influence their banks' risk-taking and help commercial banks reduce non-performing loans by controlling banks' risk appetite. The above statement by respondents was further analysed in the BCBs NPL situation. It was observed that respondents think Basel III risk management policies have helped them to build a safe credit policy by controlling banks' risk appetite and risk-taking. Respondents also said credit risk management guidelines by Basel III help them make better lending decisions and reduce non-performing loans. However, It was evident that PCBs/FCBs were able to reduce their NPL where all SCBs failed to control their NPL due to corruption in the credit granting process.

RQ 3- Does Basel III influence Bangladeshi commercial banks' lending decision to SME's? Did Basel III affect Bangladeshi SME's accessibility to credits?

Basel III introduced a new credit rating and different risk weight on SME lending based on SME's credit rating. Basel III has indeed made it easy for SME's to access credits. Still, respondents said Based III had made access to credit easy for those SME's which have satisfactory credit ratings and can provide high-value collateral. However, SME's with lower credit ratings or can't offer high-value collateral; respondents said they are most likely to be refused by the bank. SME owners also supported this finding. They said it is relatively easy for SME's to get a loan if they can provide high-value collateral. Banks also prioritise those who have good credit ratings and good collateral compared to low credit ratings and less valuable collateral. Moreover, Basel III has increased SME's cost of getting finance from banks, and SME owners pointed out that they had had to bribe cash for finance although they had good credit ratings and secured their loans using high-value collateral.

RQ 4 – Whether the different generation of banks who implemented the Basel III standard have better financial performance?

It was observed from 36 BCBs financial statement analysis from 2014 to 2019 that SCBs continued to fail to raise capital from 2014. The number of capital shortfalls

among SCB increased gradually over the year. Moreover, the higher minimum capital requirement also altered the PCBs/FCBs dividend policy. It was observed a sharp increase in the number of zero dividends-paying banks from 2015 to 2018. Lastly, the performance gap among different generations of BCBs who successfully implemented Basel III standards from 2016 to 2019 has been measured in the last part of the financial analysis chapter. The analysis clearly shows that newly established banks are way ahead in almost all Basel standards than first-generation banks. Furthermore, it was observed that the first and second generation of banks has better financial performances than ratios used to analyse their financial performance.

7.2 Research contribution

7.2.1 Contribution to general knowledge

This research contributes to banking regulation literature, mainly to understand the impact of banking regulation on developing countries' SME's. Although SME's worldwide have difficulties accessing finance, SME's in the developing and emerging economies suffer major problems accessing finance compared to developed countries' SME's. The majority of the previous studies on Basel III's impact on commercial banks and their lending towards SME's are country-specific. None of the previous research has been carried out in the Bangladeshi context (to the researcher's best knowledge). Developing countries with different economic, social, and political characteristics compared to developed countries and country-specific research can provide valuable and detailed insights into a problem specific to that country that may not apply to other countries. Therefore, analysis of this kind is vital to understand and gain a deep insight into the problem caused by global banking regulation to a Bangladeshi sector that contributes 25% to GDP and rolls the wheel of economic growth.

7.2.2 Contribution to practice

The researcher chooses Bangladesh for this study for two reasons. Firstly, Bangladesh has made remarkable progress in reducing poverty using sustainable economic growth (World Bank, 2018). Continuous economic growth has also enabled Bangladesh to reach the lower-middle-income country in 2015 and the

United Nation's least developed country in 2018. It is expected by officials that Bangladesh will graduate from the least developed country list by 2024. Therefore, sustainable economic growth is vital for Bangladesh to reach its goals by 2024. Secondly, SME's contribute 25% to the national GDP, which only considers manufacturing SME's (Abdin, 2017). Infact, SME's contribution to GDP can go up significantly if service-based SME's contributions are taken into consideration. According to Abdin (2017), service-based SME's contribute 56.34% to GDP, making SME's the most significant contributors to GDP.

Therefore, SME's plays a more significant role in Bangladesh's journey to the developed countries list. This study's findings can help both financial regulators and Bangladeshi governments formulate strategies on how to move forward by maintaining a sustainable economy by facilitating SME growth.

7.3 Implications and recommendations

Basel III's implication is to protect banks from the future financial crisis by raising the capital required to ensure that the banking industry stands on a solid capital backup, increased liquidity requirement, and enhanced risk management to control banks' risk takings and risk appetite. This section provides the implication and recommendation for future research.

7.3.1 Implication of research finding

The findings indicate that some BCBs are struggling to maintain the Basel III capital requirement. Most Bangladeshi state banks struggle to raise capital due to lower profitability resulting from higher losses caused by huge NPL. In addition to this, higher risk weight and high-value collateral demand by banks make it difficult for Bangladeshi SME's to access bank finance. Bank finance is the primary source for SME's and to many SME's banks are the only source of finance. Furthermore, this research reveals that collateral plays the lead role between getting finance and not getting any financial help from the bank. Therefore, any SME's that cannot provide high-value collateral are denied finance, making it almost impossible for start-ups to receive financial assistance from the bank. This motivates small enterprises to seek finance from micro-credit companies at higher interest rates than a bank for finance.

Rather than reducing SME's risk weight which is introduced to facilitate both banks and SME's, it would be more beneficial for SME's to get less restricted access to finance. This research's main observation indicates that banks are less willing to finance SME's with low credit rating and insufficient collateral. Both low credit rating and low-value collateral require more RWA for banks. Moreover, this research also observed that some BCBs' has failed to maintain the level of capital needed from 2014 to 2019. The number of banks failing to comply with banks regulation has increased since 2014. Thus, it is logical to assume that the number of non-compliant banks will increase by 2019. Therefore, if banks struggle to raise capital, they will most likely reduce their high-risk assets to minimise capital requirement, jeopardising SME's access to finance further.

This study may inspire commercial banks to facilitate SME lending by raising the bar of collateral-free loan to small enterprises to ensure that small enterprises do not die at the start-up stage. Furthermore, the Bangladesh government can use these research findings to remove barriers to SME's access to finance so that SME's can contribute more to the growing GDP and drive Bangladesh to the least developed countries list by 2024.

7.4 Recommendations

The following recommendations may be useful to the regulators, national supervisors, commercial banks, and Bangladesh's government based on the research findings.

In the past, the central bank of Bangladesh has attempted to facilitate SME financing using target lending. In 2010, Bangladesh Bank directives stated that BCB's must assign 40% of their total SME lending to small enterprises, 15% to woman entrepreneur and the remaining 45% for service and manufacturing SME's (Bangladesh Bank, 2010). However, the current Bangladesh central bank's directive state that the BCBs lending portfolio must contain at least 20% of SME lending and gradually increase to 25% by 2021 (The daily star (2017)). However, this directive seems to be inadequate compared to the demand for SME finance. Moreover, BCBs can manipulate the above order by lending to SME's, which have had higher credit rating and can provide high-value collateral, which is also evident in the result

chapter. Therefore, this study recommends increasing Bangladesh Bank's directives to 30% by 2021 and 40% of total SME lending to classify according to SME's credit rating. For example, 30% of 40% of banks' lending portfolios assigned to small enterprises must be set to SME 1, 20% must contain SME 2 and so on. It should prevent banks from lending only high-rated small enterprises and ensuring equal distribution of credits according to small enterprises credit rating. So that low rated SME's have better access to bank finance. Furthermore, this study recommends that at least 2% of banks' lending portfolios must contain collateral-free loans to small enterprises and micro-enterprises to facilitate their working capital needs. It should ensure that all SME's have an equal chance of getting finance from banks, especially small enterprises.

However, proposed directives for SME lending to 30% possess a problem for banks given that many BCBs are struggling to raise capital, particularly Tier 1 capital. SME's are already considered high-risk, and collateral-free lending will most likely generate a higher capital charge for banks and put pressure on Tier 1 capital given that a significant number of BCBs are already struggling to meet Basel III minimum capital requirement. One possible way for banks to increase Tier 1 capital is to reduce dependency on incomes from lending and generate revenues from other sources. Generally, interest income from lending is the primary source of income for banks. However, lending also generates the regulatory capital charge for banks. Therefore, if banks can generate revenue from other sources, it will most likely reduce banks' dependency on lending and increase lending to SME's. Furthermore, a new profit-generating source can also help BCB's to meet Basel III capital requirement. Therefore, this research proposes the following recommendations for generating profits from new services:

Almost all Bangladeshi private commercial banks charge a maintenance fee for the current account without additional benefit. In this situation, banks have two choices to make. Firstly, banks can continue to charge a maintenance fee for a bank account, but they need to increase their customer base. Attracting financial societies such as co-operative society can be a great way to gain a new customer. Banks can attract financial institutions by offering them special fixed deposit rate, and in exchange, economic society can promote and influence their members to open an

account with the bank. Secondly, banks can provide different current account types and combine benefits such as breakdown/mobile/home insurance cover, cashback facilities on purchase for a monthly fee (currently half-yearly or annually). Banks can also combine services such as car breakdown cover, mobile insurance etc., with their current account for a price which can be an excellent source of new income for BCBs to increase Tier 1 capital. Although the above ideas to gain more current account customers are well known in Europe, they are relatively new in Bangladesh and attract customers' attention.

Furthermore, to ensure future incomes, BCBs can provide free account services to graduates with extra benefits such as free overdraft facilities. When graduates get involved in employment, they can continue to use this account for a fee. This will serve two purposes. It will most likely gain new customers and generate more income for banks. Simultaneously, it should improve banks' liquidity by ensuring that banks' customers leave a certain amount in their accounts to avoid bank charges and stay with the bank for longer to obtain services offered by the bank.

This research indicates that a lack of valuable collateral is a significant hindrance to SME credit expansion. Although collateral-free credit schema has been utilised in the Bangladeshi agricultural sector, manufacturing and service-based SME sectors are far from this benefit. Rather than using fixed assets such as land and buildings, this study recommends using assets bought by SME's using bank finance, such as machinery, for term loan collateral; and personal/group guarantee as collateral for the working capital loan. It will benefit SME's by providing new equipment they need and reducing banks' risk exposures by taking collateral.

Currently, funds from Bangladesh Bank, World Bank and Asian Development Bank are channelled through SME refinance scheme. However, the refinance scheme by Bangladesh Bank gives SME's manufacturing and service sectors the highest priority among the refinancing, as mentioned earlier funds. Therefore, the researcher recommends that all refinancing plan prioritise the manufacturing and service sectors finance because they have a significant contribution to GDP compared to other industries. Moreover, small enterprises must prioritise medium enterprises in refinancing scheme as it was evident in this research that small enterprises suffer

most while seeking finance compared to medium enterprises because of their size and lack of past market history.

There is a huge difference in interest charges between women entrepreneur loan, industrial loan and loan to SME's. Loans to woman entrepreneur currently stand at 9%, while general SME loan interest is charged between 14% to 20%, and industrial loan interest from 9% to 13%. The commercial banks in Bangladesh have been abided by a government directive to bring down the interest rate on lending to a single digit (The Independent, 2018). However, the reduced interest rate has been applied to industrial and capital loans only, leaving SME loan interest rate as high as 20%. Therefore, I recommend that SME loan interest be reduced to a single digit so that Bangladeshi SME's have an equal opportunity to bank finance.

Lastly, the Bangladesh government can play a vital role in keeping the interest cost down for SME's, especially for small enterprises, by introducing new legislation that banks' cannot charge high interest if SME's can provide valuable collateral. Moreover, the Bangladesh government can protect small enterprises' interests by offering incentives to banks for collateral-free lending, given that a large percentage of GDP comes from the SME sector.

7.5 Limitation of the study

This study's limitation includes a lack of comparability between bankers working in different categories of commercial banks and their views on the impact of Basel III on commercial banks. It was evident that foreign banks branches and jointly owned (Bangladesh and foreign country such as Dutch-Bangla bank) banks are doing well in maintaining Basel III required capital level and making profits compared to Bangladeshi private and state-owned commercial banks (see appendix 10). Further research in this area regarding what makes foreign and jointly owned banks perform better than local and state-owned commercial banks would be attractive.

The second limitation regards the accessibility to the respondents selected for this study. It was difficult for the researcher to access respondents and access to potential respondents was a significant barrier to data collection. Researcher experienced that bankers who work in the head office or related to Basel

implementation team have a good knowledge regarding Basel III. However, bankers who work at the branch level have little or no experience with Basel III. The researcher took over 47 bankers' interviews. However, due to the interview data quality, the researcher picked 32 out of 47 bankers interviews for this research. Moreover, some respondents refused to provide an interview because they admitted that they lack knowledge in the research area.

Timekeeping was another major issue faced by researchers during the data collection stage. Researchers had to reschedule some interviews because participants failed to show up in pre-agreed time or did not meet at their office either because they had to work long hours or were engaged in unexpected meetings. Moreover, bank participants have mentioned that their employers are forbidden to speak to the press or pass any information regarding their operational activities to the third party without prior approval from human resource. The researcher wasn't aware of this organizational culture as participants did not mention it when the researcher contacted them before going to Bangladesh. As a result, most respondents refused to consent to the recording and requested to be anonymous. Several prospective participants declined to take part, although the interviewer guaranteed their anonymity.

The short timeline is another limitation of this study. It was difficult to fix an interview within this short timeline because of the respondents' irregularity in keeping promises. Furthermore, the number of bankers' interviewees was constrained by participants' availability and accessibility, which might have injected some bias but gathering in-depth knowledge about the topic was more attractive to the researcher. In addition to the above limitation, the researcher realized that pre-agreed time has little value in Bangladeshi culture as people tend to be late. This is considered normal in Bangladesh, which was evident during the data collection stage as most interviewees arrived well after the scheduled starting times.

The researcher planned to collect data using questionnaires to ensure data triangulation. However, pandemic and personal finance prevent the researcher from travelling to Bangladesh.

7.6 Further research

Due to the lack of research on Basel III's impact on the banking industry and their potential impact on SME's in general in South-Asian countries, especially in the Bangladeshi background, there are many potential possibilities for further research on both banks and SME's.

Firstly, future research might explore how Basel III modified banks' risk-taking behaviour towards small enterprises due to higher capital requirement when the BCBs will fully implement Basel III by 2019. The researcher particularly finds this research attractive because research suggests that the higher capital requirement attracts low-risk banks. Some respondents predicted that low risk-taking might encourage the BCBs' to offer loans to those SME's, which has a higher credit rating. Although some respondents denied such an approach by the banks', further research in this area should unveil the true nature of the impact of an increase in the capital requirement by the BCBs on their risk profile. Therefore, future research in this area should investigate the real effects of Basel III higher capital requirement on BCB's risk-taking after full implementation of Basel III in the Bangladeshi context.

Secondly, at the current Basel III implementation stage, many researchers suggested that SME's, tiny enterprises, will suffer from credit crunch due to Basel III's higher capital requirement. However, their predictions are primarily based on assumption and historical data rather than field research. Historically, it is evident that when regulators increase capital requirement, banks tend to avoid high-risk investment. However, when BCB's will implement Basel III entirely by 2019, Basel III's impact on SME lending during the implementation stage may change compared to the post-implementation location due to credit rating-based risk-weight assigned to SME's by Basel III. Nonetheless, there is enough evidence to infer that the Basel Accords might significantly decrease access to finance and increase SMEs' lending rates in the analysed timeframe. As a result, further research should be performed on Basel III's economic impact on BCB's financial stability and the causal link between the reduction of SME credit provision and the Basel III accord in Bangladesh. Although Basel III might have played a significant role in reducing SME's credit supply from banks and increasing finance cost, e.g. interest rate for

SME's during the implementation stage, further research should be performed to find whether this continues to the post-implementation phase.

The decrease in SME credit provision and the Basel Accords. Therefore, further research should be performed on how Basel III's role might have been exacerbated for the Bangladeshi SMEs due to their generally frailer financial situation and to the collateral backed lending system.

Value maximization is a key performance indicator of a company's market performance to many shareholders. The impact of a regulatory change on banks market value can be an exciting research area for many researchers. Although the researcher was interested in the researcher in this area and considered the possibility of such research in this study, it was evident that gathering BCB's historical share price data is time-consuming and costly. Further analysis should be performed on the link between the regulatory changes and banks share price.

This study concentrated on the potential impact of Basel III on banks' capital structure and their lending towards SME's. This research found that the BCB's, especially state commercial banks, have a large number of NPL. Future research could investigate whether there is a link between a robust risk management system and NPL and whether the Basel III risk management framework improved BCB's NPL situation.

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Appendix 1 Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

To: Participants

Project Title: The impact of Basel III on Bangladeshi commercial bank and their lending towards SME's

Student researcher: Md. Rajib Hasan

Information for participants

Thank you for considering participating in this study which will take place on _____

This information sheet outlines the purpose of the study and provides a description of your involvement and rights as a participant if you agree to take part.

1. What is the research about?

The aim of this research is to identify the microeconomic impact of Basel III on Bangladeshi Commercial Banks capital and their lending towards Bangladeshi SME's. Considering the recent banking governance and risk management failure which results in the worst financial crisis to date, this research aims to provide a detailed and concrete analysis on the effect of Basel III on BPCB's and their lending behaviour towards SME's. This research also aims to analyse the effect of Basel III on BPCB's capital structure and existing risk management system and whether together they have any impact on BPCB's risk appetite level as well as on risk-taking which may influence BPCB's lending supply towards SME's.

This research will gather data using semi-structured interview which will be analysed later using software

2. Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. You do not have to take part if you do not want to. If you do decide to take part, I will ask you to sign a consent form which you can sign and return in advance of the interview or sign at the meeting.

3. What will my involvement be? I will use your opinion along with the participant's interview data to answer my research question

4. How do I withdraw from the study?

You can withdraw at any point of the study, without having to give a reason. If any questions during the interview make you feel uncomfortable, you do not have to answer them and you can withdraw from the group/interview at any time for any reason. Withdrawing from the study will have no effect on you. If you withdraw from the study we will not retain the information you have given thus far, unless you are happy for us to do so.

5. What will my information be used?

I will use the collected information for a research project.

6. Will my taking part and my data be kept confidential? Will it be anonymised?

The records from this study will be kept as confidential as possible. Only I and my supervisor will have access to the files and any audiotapes. Your data will be anonymised – your name will not be used in any reports or publications resulting from the study unless you authorise me to do so. All digital files, transcripts and summaries will be given codes and stored separately from any names or other direct identification of participants. Any hard copies of research information will be kept in locked files at all times.

7. What if I have a question or complaint?

If you have any questions regarding this study, please contact the researcher at

Md. Rajib Hasan

School of Business and Enterprise,

University of West of Scotland

Paisley

PA1 2BE, Scotland

██████████

████████████████████

If you have any concerns or complaints regarding the conduct of this research, please contact the UWS ethics committee via businessandenterpriseethics@uws.ac.

If you are happy to take part in this study, please sign the consent sheet attached.

Appendix 2 Consent form for interview

Consent form for interview

Research Title: The Impact of Basel on Bangladeshi commercial banks and their lending towards SME's

Researcher Student: Md. Rajib Hasan

Please tick the appropriate boxes	Yes	No
<i>Taking Part</i>		
I have read and understood the project information sheet dated		
I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the project.		
I agree to take part in the project. Taking part in the project will include being interviewed and recorded (audio or video) ^a		
I understand that my taking part is voluntary; I can withdraw from the study at any time and I do not have to give any reasons for why I no longer want to take part.		
<i>Use of the information I provide for this project only</i>		
I understand my personal details such as phone number and address will not be revealed to people outside the project.		
I understand that my words may be quoted in publications, reports, web pages, and other research outputs.		
<i>Please choose one of the following two options:</i>		
I would like my real name used in the above		
I would not like my real name to be used in the above.		
<i>Use of the information I provide beyond this project</i>		
I agree for the data I provide to be archived at ... ^b		
I understand that other genuine researchers will have access to this data only if they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the information as requested in this form.		
I understand that other genuine researchers may use my words in publications, reports, web pages, and other research outputs, only if they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the information as requested in this form.		
<i>So we can use the information you provide legally</i>		
I agree to assign the copyright I hold in any materials related to this project to [name of researcher].		

Name of participant
Signature
Date

Researcher Name
Signature
Date

Appendix 3 Interview Guide (Bank)

Dear Participant,

This questionnaire is designed to examine the impact of Basel III on Bangladeshi commercial banks and their lending to SME's. This study is being undertaken in fulfilment of the requirements for the award of a DBA. Degree. All the data supplied shall be used solely for the purpose of this study and will be treated with the utmost confidentiality. Please complete the questionnaire as honestly as you can.

Yours sincerely,

Md. Rajib Hasan

Part 1

- Name:
- Age:
- Business Name:
- Position:
- Educational Level

Part 2

1. What do you think of the appropriateness of Basel III on the Bangladeshi banking sector?
2. How does Basel III affect your banks' capital structure?
3. Can you tell me whether Basel III regulation influences your banks' ability/policy change towards Bangladeshi SME's?
4. Can you explain how Basel III improved your bank's risk management system and control bank's risk appetite? How it impacts your lending policies?
5. Did you change your lending pattern towards SME's due to Basel III?
6. What do you think of the real impact of Basel III on your bank?
7. What is the long-term impact of Basel III?

Appendix 4 Interview Guide (SME)

Dear Participant,

This questionnaire is designed to examine the impact of Basel III on Bangladeshi commercial banks and their lending to SME's. This study is being undertaken in fulfilment of the requirements for the award of a DBA. Degree. All the data supplied shall be used solely for the purpose of this study and will be treated with the utmost confidentiality. Please complete the questionnaire as honestly as you can.

Yours sincerely,

Md. Rajib Hasan

Part 1

- Name:
- Age:
- Business Name:
- Position:
- Years in business:
- Employee no:
- Educational Level

Part 2

1. What are your major finance sources?
2. How often do you seek finance from your finance sources?
3. Can you please explain your current financial relationship with your bank?
4. Did you receive any credit from your bank for business purpose? If yes when was that? Approximately amount.
5. Can you please tell me when the last time your credit application was rejected if any? and if yes why?
6. Do you need to provide a collateral deposit for a bank loan?
7. Do you know what Basel III is?
8. Bangladeshi commercial bank's start to implement Basel III from 2016 and they have till 2019 to finish the process. If you have applied for credits from the bank in 2016/17, have you noticed any change? i.e. interest rate, increase in the requirement, more documentation, or changes in banks' willingness to grant credit??
9. Any further comment on how this can be improved?

Appendix 5 Ethics Approval

25/03/2019

Dear Md Rajib Hasan,

Your application 8034: Impact of Basel III on Bangladeshi commercial bank and their lending towards SME's, submission 6458, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean

Appendix 6 Introductory Letter

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

17 November 2017

Md Rajib Hasan
10A MacDonald Road
London
E7 OHE

Paisley Campus
Paisley
PA1 2BE
Scotland

Tel 0141 848 3635 or 3037
Email pgr@uws.ac.uk

Dear Md Rajib

Banner ID: B00296014

I write to confirm your status as a full time postgraduate research student, enrolled on the Doctorate of Business Administration course at the Paisley Campus. Your request to conduct research out with the UK from 19th October 2017 to 7th December 2017 has been authorised by your Director of Studies, Dr Kieran James.

Yours sincerely

Nikita Mkangama
UWS Graduate School

The Graduate School

University of the West of Scotland is a registered Scottish charity. Charity number SC002520.

Appendix 7 Sample Interview 1(Bank)

- Name: MD
- Age: 55
- Business Name: Social Islamic Bank
- Position: Executive Vice-president
- Educational Level: MSC

1. What do you think of the appropriateness of Basel III in the Bangladeshi banking industry?

The appropriateness of Basel III is decided by Bangladesh bank and as per their decision, they have issued guidelines on how to implement Basel III in the decided timeline. However, from my point of view ordering all commercial banks in Bangladesh by Bangladesh central bank is justified due to vulnerability of Bangladeshi banking sector as well as intense competition to gain customer without considering banks risk exposure. For example, according to Bangladesh banks guidelines, we have established six risk management committee for six core risk indicated by Bangladesh bank. This six risk management committee constantly monitor and supervise our bank's core risk exposure. Furthermore, we have risk management committee at the management level. They report to board risk management committee which we named as All Risk Management Committee (ARMC). This ARMC meet once in a month and Bangladesh bank has provided guidelines to discuss on 55 areas of banking activities in the ARMC. In the meeting we normally discuss issues such as our top 10 borrowers analysis, foreign currency exposure analysis, investment concentration analysis, credit sector analysis. All information's are collected from our branch level and meeting outcomes are periodically implemented in the required sector. As a result of Basel III risk management framework, banks risk exposures are discussed regularly and supervision have increased to identify any risk.

2. How does Basel III affect your banks' capital structure?

Basel III not only increased capital requirements but also asked the bank to increase their high-quality capital. Currently, we are trying to safeguard our capital by issuing finance only to highly rated SME's and other corporate loans so out capital requirement stays minimum. However, in reality, approving finance to only good credit rating business is not enough to meet Bangladesh Bank's guidelines towards Basel III implementation. Meet Basel III capital requirement we have to issue bond

and right. Currently, we have already issued subordinate twice for BDT 500 Crore each and third subordinate bond of similar value is on its way for investors to buy.

2.1 Subordinate bond is redeemable is a short-term solution. What is your long term plan to meet Basel III capital requirement?

Currently, we don't have any perpetual long-term financial instrument to meet Basel III capital requirement. We didn't receive any clear instruction from Bangladesh banks regarding the perpetual bond. Furthermore, the Bangladeshi bond market is not that strong. Even if Bangladesh bank allows us to issue the perpetual bond, we don't know how market is going to react. Maybe you know that first perpetual bond was issued by Islami bank but investors thought it was like share and bought it. But right now in current situation people knows everything and bonds are not doing well. Therefore, the perpetual bond is risky.

Secondly, we can stop giving cash dividend to our shareholders and can offer them a bonus dividend.

Thirdly, we can offer customers the right share instead of a cash dividend. However, the right share is not preferable for many existing shareholders. Currently, we have BDT 7500C in capital and the last couple of years we have paid 20% dividend to our shareholders. If we issue right share 1:1, our paid-up capital will be BDT 15000C. However, this will reduce dividend payment to 10% or less which will negatively impact investors confidence on us.

2.3 So is it getting difficult for banks to raise capital to Basel III guidelines?

Yes for many banks which I will not name it is getting very difficult for banks to meet Basel III 12.5% capital requirement even though they don't have to do it in one go. However, SIBL is currently compliant with the guideline. We raised 11.42% of our capital where our required rate to meet was 11.25%. This will increase next year again by .62%. To meet this increased capital requirement we are issuing a third subordinate bond.

3. Can you tell me whether Basel III regulation influences your banks' ability/policy change towards Bangladeshi SME's?

Obliviously Basel III brought some procedural change in Social Islamic Bank's (SIBL) lending policy towards SME's. From 2013 to 2015 any loan above BDT 1C should be considered under risk-based pricing. Previously to approve an SME loan, external credit rating wasn't important and was optional. Previously, if SME's bad credit rating, they would receive risk-based pricing. Maybe you know that if the credit rating of a company came to D then we used to assign that business 125% risk weight and 75% for A and so on. If SME's didn't have credit rating, they could still get loans but bank used to charge them an additional amount on the top of

interest rate as a risk-based charge which was usually BDT .50 on every BDT 100 loan given. Before Basel III, we normally asked all the existing and new SME clients to do their credit ratings even though credit rating didn't influence our lending decision towards SME's.

However, since Basel III came in force, we are using external credit rating as a mandatory requirement for loan application which not only upgraded our capital requirements by assigning risk-based measure on SME lending but also improved SME lending process.

3.1 So what happens to those SME's who have a bad credit rating? Do you still offer them finance?

If a company have bad credit rating we don't normally offer them loans. However, in some exceptional cases, we might still offer them finance obviously they are high-risk loan and they pay a higher price. For example, if the credit rating of an SME is D, we would offer them 125% risk-weighted pricing. But previously while Basel II was in place we would have suggested businesses not to do credit rating in this situation and pay additional BDT .50 extra per BDT 100.

3.2 Do you think due to new credit rating regulation SME's cost of finance is increasing?

It is true that the cost of getting finance has increased for SME. Expenses such as documentation, credit rating fees etc is an extra cost for SME's. however, if you look at the positive side that although to do credit rating SME's need to spend extra BDT 25000 to 30000 but their need to keep their documentation right and ready. This not only helps them to keep their record organise but also helped us to take the swift decision on a loan application. However, I think Basel III have boosted the SME finance facility.

4. Can you explain how Basel III improved your bank's risk management system and control bank's risk appetite? How it impacts your lending policies?

As you already know we have six core risk those core risks are managed by ALCO (Asset Liability Committee). Also assess risk related to assets, liabilities and liquidities. You can say ALCO is like an antivirus in our banking system which continuously assesses SIBL's risk exposure. Furthermore, due to Basel III, Bangladesh bank has increased its regular supervision and inspection of our risk management framework. As a result, all bank is taking the necessary steps to pass Bangladesh banks assessments.

Bangladesh bank has provided us with risk management guidelines in accordance with Basel III to facilitate banks credit process. As you know the bank take deposit and lend it to the customer to make money. As a result, lending is an important part

of banks daily activities. Risk management policies that are placed by Basel III are to ensure that banks have a safe credit policy. We are not implementing Basel III risk management framework to develop credit policy but to develop our credit policy we are implementing Basel III risk management policy. Therefore, I think risk management framework in accordance with Basel III has developed our credit policy.

5. Did you change your lending pattern towards SME's due to Basel III?

I think there is a big difference in the Bangladesh central bank and developed countries central bank. If you look at developed countries central banks, they don't illustrate a concept for their bank. They introduce regulation and all banks are bound to follow it. In Bangladesh, Bangladesh Bank not only gives you a policy but also give you an illustrated guideline on how to implement them and why should we implement them. The major changes so far we have towards SME lending is risk-based pricing and credit rating in accordance with Basel III.

6. What do you think of the real impact of Basel III on your bank?

Basel III has impacted every corner of our bank. For example, even a few years ago employees could access different websites using banks computer, they could attach an external pen drive with the PC. Because of Basel III risk management framework, we have blocked all outgoing apart from some specific website as well as any external attachment to our PC. Due to the Basel III risk management framework, all those operational risks have come to light. This a major change for our ICT network. We not only implemented those risk management guidelines but we also made it our internal policy. This procedural change was possible by Basel III.

7. What is the long-term impact of Basel III?

I think capital maintenance will be difficult in the long run. If the Government or Bangladesh Bank don't introduce any further instrument for us to meet Basel III increased capital requirement, we have relied upon our internal profit generation and right share issue. As a result, we have to divide our internal generation ie. profit between shareholders and capital requirement. Therefore, our investment target and growth might get slow in the near future which is not good for countries economic growth.

Appendix 8 Sample Interview 2(Bank)

- Name: Hasan
- Age: 36
- Business Name: Islamic Bank Ltd
- Position: Executive office (treasury)
- Educational Level: MBA

1. What do you think of Basel III and its appropriateness for Bangladeshi commercial Banks?

Basel III is introduced by BCBS that followed the same path as Basel I and Basel II. Basel III was an immediate response to the recent financial crisis which triggered in 2008. The world's banking sector is currently implementing Basel III and in Bangladesh all commercial banks have already started implementing Basel III under direct supervision from Bangladesh Central bank. As far as my understanding goes, Basel III emphasised to strengthen tier 1 capital or in other words core capital.

2. How does Basel III affect your banks' capital structure?

Basel III brought a new addition to Basel II. Basel III added additional capital buffer on top of core capital which is capital conservation buffer and a countercyclical capital buffer. Bangladeshi commercial banks are required to hold an amount of capital equal to at least 8% of risk-weighted assets. Moreover, 4.5% of the risk-weighted assets should be of common equity tier 1 which contains the highest quality of bank capital. Furthermore, a capital conservation buffer and a countercyclical capital buffer are needed in addition to the 4.5% of common equity tier 1 which is 2.5% of their total risk exposure.

In Basel II, banks increased their capital by purchasing bonds but Basel III emphasised on core capital which is a bank's highest quality capital. Core capital consists of paid-up capital and reserves such as statutory reserve, general reserve etc. These reserve funds are made from a bank's profit. Therefore, to increase core capital, banks need to issue new equity to increase paid-up capital. Previously, in Basel II banks could increase their core capital by issuing bonds but Basel III sees bonds as supplementary capital rather than core capital. In addition to paid-up capital, to increase other core capital components, banks need to transfer their profits to increase their core capital which is most likely to put pressure on shareholders' return and may downgrade investors' confidence in the short run. Thus, if banks cannot increase their capital, they cannot issue new loans which means fewer profits for banks.

However, major Bangladeshi commercial banks already increased their capital to a higher level when they adopted Basel II although a capital requirement for Basel II was challenging for many commercial banks. I think those small commercial banks are most likely to struggle again. Even though profitability will reduce at first but this new capital requirement will improve banks capability of absorbing shocks in the long run. However, the only good thing is that banks don't have to increase it in one year and they have time till 2019 to fulfil this capital requirement. For example, my Bank increase core capital 1.5 in 2016 and in 2017 they will increase a further 1.25% and so on until 2019.

3. Can you tell me whether Basel III regulation influences your banks' ability/policy change towards Bangladeshi SME's?

Obviously, Basel III will force banks to change their lending policies towards SME's which we call border selection.

Int: Can you please explain to me how does this border selection work under new Basel III?

Under Basel III border selection is mainly based on rating. Under Basel II, banks didn't care about SME ratings and looked for good cash transactions as well as good quality collateral deposit. However, under Basel III SME's who would like to apply for a loan need to have good credit rating otherwise banks will charge them higher interest rate. As banks are considered as a high-risk investment, banks normally charge them higher interest rate and if they have to get ratings its another further pressure on SMEs. This reduced banks productivity and increase costs for SME's.

Int: who dose this SME rating?

There are many credit rating agencies in Bangladesh who get paid for rating. Banks also get SME financial information from CIB

4. Can you explain how Basel III improved your bank's risk management system and control bank's risk apatite? How it impacts your lending policies?

I think Basel III definitely improve banks risk management system and control banks risk apatite. Most commercial banks have high leverage. Majority of Bangladesh banks have more liability comparing to deposit. For example, my banks have over BDT 20000 corer liabilities which are mostly loans against their paid-up capital of BDT 7000 corer. So you can see my bank have very high leverage ratio. Therefore, Implementing Basel III will increase capital but it will also ensure banks, select high-quality borrowers, to decrease loan default. Most impotently, Basel III risk management framework increase monitoring and control which I think will reduce credit risk as well as operational risk. However, it is possible to influence credit rating nowadays but it's better to have some rating rather than no ratings.

5. Did you change your lending pattern towards SME's due to Basel III?

Banks are most likely to choose SME's who has a good credit rating, high-quality collateral and good transaction history but new or small business may fall behind and most likely it will be hard for them to get a loan from banks due to their short life and lack of previous history.

6. What do you think of the real impact of Basel III on your bank?

As you know one of the main reason for the last banking crisis was that banks created fake economy using derivatives. Developed countries banks sold one derivative 4 times even 6 times which created short time economic boosts. But in Bangladesh and other Asian countries were not involved in market derivatives. I think Basel III will prevent banks from doing these types of things in future.

7. What is the long-term impact of Basel III?

In the developed country most loan guarantee is documented. As a result, if one side is unable to fulfil those guarantees terms and condition, another party has very limited things to do. But in Bangladesh, about 60% loans are guaranteed by fixed assets. As a result, Bangladeshi commercial banks have less change of credit default and even if there is a credit default, they can recover it from fixed asset deposit. However, in short-run banks may suffer financially but in long run I think Basel III, will increase banks stability and improve banks risk management framework.

Appendix 8 Sample Interview 3(SME)

Name: Kawsar Ahmed Adil

Age: 29

Business Name: Godhuly Knitting Apparel Ltd.

Position: Owner

Years in business: 4

Employee no: 21

Godhuly Net Apparel Ltd is a newly established company which is in the business for the past four years. Godhuly's manufacturing plants situated in Siddhirgonj, Dhaka. According to Mr Adil, his company gets sub-contract from different large garments company. He explained that he gets sub-contract from garments companies who have to deliver large quantity product in a short time but do not have necessary man or machine power to finish them on time. His clients give him part of the contract jobs which include knitting, dyeing and cutting according to specifications. Godhuly Net Apparel Ltd has 8 netting machine which can produce up to 16 tons a day. The yearly turnover of Godhuly Knitting Apparel Ltd estimated to approximately BDT 2Crore (BDT 20 million). The interview took place in Godhuly Knitting Apparel Ltd.

1. What are your major finance sources?

When I started my business 4 years ago, I start with my personal money which I received from my father. However, last one year my business has been financed by the bank.

2. How often do you seek finance from your finance sources?

All my transaction is done through the bank. My clients pay me through banks and I pay for raw materials through banks. However, I have some client who does small jobs normally pays cash.

2.1 How often you ask loans from the bank?

Well, they are not going to give me loans again and again. I took bank loans once so far and I hardly think they are going to give me another loan until I pay off my current debt. The loan system is they are going to provide you with two types of loans such as cash credit (CC) and term loans. For CC loans I pay interest as I use and term loans I need to pay instalments every month. Normally the bank gives 70% term loans and 30% CC loans.

2.3 How do you withdraw CC loans?

I can either withdraw money using ATM card or cheque.

2.4 Is there any limit of CC loan withdraws?

Actually, there is. You can withdraw 80% of your CC loans anytime, no questions asked. However, for the rest of the 20% depends on your relationship with the bank. If you have a good relationship or good transaction history they might consider further 15%. However, they are going to keep the rest of the 5%.

2.5 How do you pay CC loans interest?

Bank deducts their CC loans interest from my CC balance or I can pay in my next deposit.

3. Can you please tell how your current financial relationship with your bank is? If you need instant money for your business on the top of loans, can you get it from the bank?

Obviously, instant loans from banks depend on your relationship with banks. I have a good relationship with my bank as my father who runs his film production house, my 3 uncle who has their own garments industry all have financial tie with same bank and you know in Bangladesh relationship banking is very important. My local bank manager knows me and my whole family. Recently, bought a piece of land when I suddenly needed BDT 500000. I asked my bank and my bank authorised it in a couple of hours. All they asked me for a grantor for the loan which was my father who had to give a cheque guarantee.

4. Did you receive any credit from your bank for business purpose? If yes when was that? Approximately amount. Bank gave me BDT 9.8 million in term loans which I'm paying back each month and the rest of them are CC loan.

Yes, I did. Bank offered me BDT 2 Crore but I asked my bank to reduce it to 1.5 Crore (BDT 15 million).

4.5 Why did you ask them to reduce your loan amount?

Actually, I didn't need that much and I was scared I might spend them all.

4.6 How much did you initially asked?

I've asked them BDT 1.5 Crore but they offered me BDT 2 Crore because the land I provided as collateral was valued over 3.1 Crore and they offered me BDT 2 Crore. Bank normally gives 70% as a loan of your collateral asset.

5. Can you please tell me when the last time your credit application was rejected if any? and if yes why?

I have applied once and received once.

6. Do you need to provide a collateral deposit for a bank loan?

Yes, I did. As I've mentioned earlier I provided land ownership as collateral for my loan. Which means If I default on my loan repayment, the bank has the right to sell my land to get their money back.

6.1 Can you please explain the loan application process?

First, you need to show documentation on the current situation of your business. You need to provide them with bank solvency, clearance and bank statement. You need to show Vat return, income certificate, trade licence. After submitting those documents, they will look for whether you have any outstanding loans with other banks. This report is called the Credit Information Bureau (CIB) report supplied by Bangladesh Bank. If you have a positive CIB report, bank does collateral valuation and propose a loan amount. However, even if you have negative CIB report, some bank will still offer you a loan.

6.2 How is that possible?

It is possible if you bribe at the right place. If you were reading the newspaper then you would know that many banks have done it the past couple of years.

6.3 How much did your total spend on your loan?

The total estimated cost of my loan was BDT 11 lack (1.1 Million). I've paid surveyor cost, legal cost (both non-refundable whether you receive loans or not), credit rating, insurance for my factory and machinery was estimated to BDT 5lac and reminder of 6 lac I've paid to bank management as a bribe so that they sanction my loan although I had good CIB report as well as high-value collateral.

7. Do you know what is Basel III?

No

8. Bangladeshi commercial bank's start to implement Basel III from 2016 and they have till 2019 to finish the process. If you have applied for credits from the bank in 2016/17, have you noticed any change? i.e. interest rate, increase in the requirement, more documentation, or changes in banks' willingness to grant credit?

As I've taken loan this year, I'm not sure what has changed comparing to the previous year or so on. However, as far I know that business credit rating has been added

recently and your interest rate is based on your business credit rating. I received my business loan on a competitive rate which is 13% plus 1% service charge totalling 14%. I need to pay BDT 2.4lac term loan instalment every month and CC loan works as pay as you use. However, if you miss an instalment it is added to the initial amount whose interest should be paid separately.

8.1 Do you think business credit rating introduced by Bangladesh bank will improve loan application process?

I'm a businessman and I don't understand debit or credit. All I understand the bank is giving me finance hassle-free or not. Let me explain in deep. As you see many banks such as shahjalal Islamic bank, a social Islamic bank is in losses, why do you think is that? Is it because people like me who took loan didn't return? If they didn't return what happened to the collateral deposit? Let me tell you what happened. Bank directors allocated loans to those people who weren't eligible to receive loans and when they received loan, they didn't payback. What did new regulation do to those people? What is the point of introducing new system and regulation if it cannot stop and wrongdoing? Banks directors authorise loan for their family which is couple of time higher comparing to collateral. No one is actually helping small business but they are just using this sector to make money.

9. Any further comment on how this can be improved?

Due to bank directors, fraudulent trading banks are suffering from liquidity problem. Bank don't have money. They take depositors money and invest them as a loan to us. They pay 4% to 6% interest to depositors and earn 13% to 20% interest from us. The balance is their profit. My banks asked me last month to pay them advance loan instalments. My normal loan instalment is BDT 2.4lac but I've paid BDT 3.5 lac in October and BDT 3 lac in November due to banks liquidity problem which was caused by bankdirector's corruptions but the real sufferers are the one like me who is trying to survive in this competitive industry. Therefore, people who did corruption are not suffering but people like us are suffering.

Furthermore, the interest rate is very high. I pay 13% interest plus 1% service charge. As a result, whatever I earn each month, I only see a profit after paying loan instalment and other expenses which is not a big figure.

I think Bangladeshi banking sector has a great future only if we can eliminate corruption and it is only possible if Bangladesh Bank becomes stricter towards commercial banks and introduce higher punishment for bank directors fraudulent trading. Although Bangladesh bank has started to take action against some bank directors for their activities. Only changing regulation and introducing a new system will not save SME's or banks from losses until the central bank keeps strict control over them.

Appendix 9 Basel capital requirement compliance by BCB (2014 to 2017)

List of sampled Bangladeshic commercial banks failed to meet Basel II minimum capital requirement in 2014

List of Banks failed to meet Basel II minimum capital requirement												
Bank Name	Total RWA Asset	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Eligible Capital	Minmum Regulatory Capital	Capital Surplus/Shorages	CAR 8% (Basel II)	Tier 1 Capital to total capital)	Cash Dividen d Paid	Stock Dividen d Paid	Subordinated debt	
State Banks												
Bangladesh Krishi Bank	126791	-5288	3610	-1678	10143	-11821	-1.32%	-4.17%	NA	NA	Nil	
BASIC Bank Limited	92364	-26854	622	-26232	7389	-33621	-28.40%	-29.07%	NA	NA	Nil	
Private Commercial Banks												
Commerce Bank Limited	24284	1236	176	1412	1943	-531	5.81%	5.09%	Nil	Nil	Nil	
ICB Islamic Bank Ltd.	92303	-1018	311	-707	7384	-8091	-0.77%	-1.10%	Nil	Nil	Nil	

List of sampled state commercial banks capital structure in 2014 under Basel II

Figures In BDT Million	Total RWA Assets	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Eligible Capital	Minmum Regulatory Capital (8% Of RWA)	Capital Surplus/Shorages	CAR 8% (Basel II)	Tier 1 Capital to total capital)	Cash Dividend Paid	Stock Dividend Paid	Subordinated debt
Agrani Bank Limited	253260	15520	10920	26440	20261	6179	10.44%	6.13%	NA	NA	Nil
BDBL	53102	9424	3629	13053	5310	7743	24.58%	17.75%	NA	NA	Nil
Bangladesh Krishi Bank	126791	-5288	3610	-1678	10143	-11821	-1.32%	-4.17%	NA	NA	Nil
BASIC Bank Limited	92364	-26854	622	-26232	7389	-33621	-28.40%	-29.07%	NA	NA	Nil
Janata Bank Limited	354201	28579	7889	36468	28336	8132	10.30%	8.07%	NA	NA	Nil
Rupali Bank Limited	138812	10738	3785	14523	11105	3418	10.46%	7.74%	NA	NA	Nil
Sonali Bank Limited	406849	30017	16976	46993	32548	14445	11.55%	7.38%	NA	NA	Nil

List of sampled private commercial banks capital structure in 2014 under Basel II

Figures In BDT Million	Total RWA Assets	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Eligible Capital	Minmum Regulatory Capital (8% of RWA)	Capital Surplus/Shortages	CAR 8% (Basel II)	Tier 1 Capital to total capital)	Cash Dividend Paid	Stock Dividend Paid	Subordinated debt
AB Bank Limited	220865	16561	6238	22799	17669	5130	10.32%	7.50%	Nil	12.50%	2500
Al-Arafah Islami Bank Limited	128212	15620	1732	17352	10257	7095	13.53%	12.18%	14%	Nil	3000
Bank Al Falah	8506	4603	134	4736	680	4056	55.68%	54.11%	Nil	Nil	Nil
Commerce Bank Limited	24284	1236	176	1412	1943	-531	5.81%	5.09%	Nil	Nil	Nil
Bank Asia Limited	157570	14174	3670	17843	12606	5238	11.32%	9.00%	5%	10%	4500
BRAC Bank Limited	139439	17418	3712	21130	11155	9975	15.15%	12.49%	20%	Nil	3000
Citibank N.A	152292	15185	8300	23484	12183	11301	15.42%	9.97%	15%	5%	Nil
Dhaka Bank Limited	137841	12035	3403	15438	11027	4411	11.20%	8.73%	14%	10%	1200
Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	109984	12277	5801	18078	8799	9279	16.44%	11.16%	40%	Nil	4658
Eastern Bank Limited	137038	13958	4163	18121	10963	7158	13.22%	10.19%	20%	Nil	2500
EXIM Bank Limited Ltd	199902	20661	2859	23520	15992	7527	11.77%	10.34%	Nil	10%	Nil
ICB Islamic Bank Ltd.	92303	-1018	311	-707	7384	-8091	-0.77%	-1.10%	Nil	Nil	Nil
IFIC Bank Limited	111578	9695	1613	11308	8926	2382	10.14%	8.69%	Nil	15%	Nil
Islami Bank Bangladesh L	375744	35026	13543	48569	30060	18509	12.93%	9.32%	15%	Nil	3000
Jamuna Bank Ltd	98652	9144	1951	11095	7892	3203	11.25%	9.27%	Nil	19%	Nil
Meghna Bank	9937	4427	99	4526	795	3731	45.55%	44.55%	Nil	Nil	Nil
Mutual Trust Bank Limite	80937	6284	2464	8748	6475	2274	10.81%	7.76%	Nil	20%	1000
NCC Bank	112720	13865	1262	15127	9018	6109	13.42%	12.30%	Nil	10%	Nil
National Bank Limited	249569	24320	4897	29217	19966	9251	11.71%	9.74%	Nil	10%	Nil
One Bank Limited	107718	10176	4334	14510	8617	5893	13.47%	9.45%	12.5%	12.5%	Nil
Premier Bank Limited	87321	5544	2381	7925	6986	939	9.08%	6.35%	Nil	10%	2600
Prime Bank Ltd	214908	22511	4802	27313	17193	10120	12.71%	10.47%	10%	Nil	Nil
Pubali Bank Limited	199633	19895	3540	23435	15971	7464	11.74%	9.97%	10%	Nil	Nil
Shahjalal Bank Limited	93828	11698	1075	12773	7506	5267	13.61%	12.47%	10%	Nil	Nil
Social Islami Bank Ltd	99839	10000	1622	11622	7987	3635	11.64%	10.02%	Nil	10%	Nil
Southeast Bank Limited	221241	19882	7580	27462	17699	9763	12.41%	8.99%	15%	Nil	3000
Standard Bank Limited	98975	9860	1153	11013	7918	3095	11.13%	9.96%	Nil	15%	Nil
UCBL	243254	19265	6426	25691	19460	6231	10.56%	7.92%	10%	20%	2000

List of sampled banks who failed to meet Basel III minimum capital requirement in 2015

	Total RWA Capital	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Eligible Capital	Regulatory Capital (10% of RWA or BDT 4,000 whichever Higher)	Capital Buffer (N/A)	Capital Surplus/ Shortages	CAR (min 10%)	Tier 1 capital to total capital (5.50% min)	Subordinated debt	Dividend Cash	Dividend Bonus
State Bank												
Agrani Bank Limited	264691	17479	7770	25249	26469	N/A	-1220	9.54%	6.6%	Nil	NA	Nil
Bangladesh Krishi Bank	140045	-58096	3971	-54125	14005	N/A	-68130	-38.65%	-41.5%	Nil	NA	Nil
Basic Bank Limited	112748	-9088	575	-8513	11275	N/A	-19787	-7.55%	-8.1%	Nil	NA	Nil
Rupali Bank Limited	149640	9288	3410	12698	14964	N/A	-2266	8.49%	6.2%	Nil	NA	Nil
Privet Banks												
Commerce Bank Limited	26197	1047	136	1183	2620	N/A	-1437	4.52%	4.0%			
ICB Islamic Bank Ltd.	91885	-10438	256	-10183	9189	N/A	-19371	-11.08%	-11.4%	Nil	Nil	Nil
Premier Bank	98729	5693	3303	8996	9873	N/A	-877	9.11%	5.8%	2600	Nil	10

List of sampled state commercial banks capital structure in 2015 under Basel III

Figures In BDT Million

	Total RWA Capital	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Eligible Capital	Regulatory Capital (10% of RWA or BDT 4,000 whichever Higher)	Capital Buffer (N/A)	Capital Surplus/ Shortages	CAR (min 10%)	Tier 1 capital to total capital (5.50% min)	Subordinated debt	Dividend Cash	Dividend Bonus
State Banks												
Agrani Bank Limited	264691	17479	7770	25249	26469	N/A	-1220	9.54%	6.6%	Nil	NA	Nil
BDBL	46842	9135	2935	12070	4684	N/A	7386	25.77%	19.5%	Nil	NA	Nil
Bangladesh Krishi Bank	140045	-58096	3971	-54125	14005	N/A	-68130	-38.65%	-41.5%	Nil	NA	Nil
Basic Bank Limited	112748	-9088	575	-8513	11275	N/A	-19787	-7.55%	-8.1%	Nil	NA	Nil
Rupali Bank Limited	149640	9288	3410	12698	14964	N/A	-2266	8.49%	6.2%	Nil	NA	Nil
Sonali Bank Limited	394319	25357	14387	39744	39432	N/A	312	10.08%	6.4%	Nil	NA	Nil
Janata Bank Limited	365623	29972	7157	37128	36562	N/A	566	10.15%	8.2%	Nil	NA	Nil

List of sampled private commercial banks capital structure in 2015 under Basel III

Private Commercial Banks													
	Total RWA Capital	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Eligible Capital	Regulatory Capital (10% of RWA or BDT 4,000 whichever Higher)	Capital Buffer (N/A)	Capital Surplus/ Shortages	CAR (min 10%)	Tier 1 capital to total capital (5.50% min)	Subordinated debt	Dividend Cash	Dividend Bonus	
AB Bank Limited	255525	20150	8170	28320	25553	N/A	2768	11.08%	7.9%	6500		12.5	
Al-Arafah Islami Bank Limited	139456	18244	4828	23072	13946	N/A	9127	16.54%	13.1%	3000	10	5	
Al-Falah Bank in Bangladesh	9112	4924	119	5042	911	N/A	4131	55.34%	54.0%	Nil			
Commerce Bank Limited	26197	1047	136	1183	2620	N/A	-1437	4.52%	4.0%				
Bank Asia Limited	183249	16400	6437	22837	18325	N/A	4512	12.46%	8.9%	3315	5	10	
BRAC Bank Limited	166628	17114	3260	20374	16663	N/A	3711	12.23%	10.3%	3000	25%	Nil	
Citibank N.A	24095	9552	185	9737	2410	N/A	7328	40.41%	39.6%	3000	22	Nil	
Dhaka Bank Limited	147349	12643	2765	15408	14735	N/A	673	10.46%	8.6%	Nil	6%	10%	
Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	154548	14730	12277	27007	15455	N/A	11552	17.47%	9.5%	4402	40	Nil	
Eastern Bank Limited	143709	14688	5776	20464	14371	N/A	6093	14.24%	10.2%	2500	20	15	
EXIM Bank Limited	234170	23023	5359	28382	23417	N/A	4965	12.12%	9.8%	2500	12%		
First Security Islami Bank Limited	122078	9079	3453	12532	12208	N/A	324	10.27%	7.4%	1882	Nil	10	
ICB Islamic Bank Ltd.	91885	-10438	256	-10183	9189	N/A	-19371	-11.08%	-11.4%	Nil	Nil	Nil	
IFIC Bank Limited	117318	10508	1305	11813	11732	N/A	81	10.07%	9.0%	Nil	Nil	12%	
Islami Bank Bangladesh Ltd	410331	38650	9195	47845	41033	N/A	6812	11.66%	9.4%	3000	20	Nil	
Jamuna Bank Ltd	114827	10773	3852	14625	11483	N/A	3142	12.74%	9.4%	2000	19.5	Nil	
Meghna Bank	18617	4881	186	5067	1862	N/A	3205	27.22%	26.2%	Nil	6%	Nil	
Mutual Trust Bank Limited	102103	7599	4846	12445	10210	N/A	2235	12.19%	7.4%	4875	Nil	20	
National Bank Limited	259358	27223	4041	31264	25936	N/A	5328	12.05%	10.5%	1280	Nil	15	
NCC Bank	122752	15323	1361	16684	12275	N/A	4409	13.59%	12.5%	Nil	Nil	Nil	
One Bank Limited	134305	10744	7331	18075	13431	N/A	4645	13.46%	8.0%	1760	12.5	12.5	
Prime Bank Ltd	229846	22977	6306	29283	22985	N/A	6298	12.74%	10.0%	3000	Nil	10	
Premier Bank	98729	5693	3303	8996	9873	N/A	-877	9.11%	5.8%	2600	Nil	10	
Pubali Bank Limited	210258	21481	3466	24947	21026	N/A	3921	11.86%	10.2%	Nil	12	Nil	
Shahjalal Bank Limited	98793	12254	1101	13355	9879	N/A	3476	13.52%	12.4%	Nil	13	Nil	
Social Islami Bank Ltd	137157	11921	4995	16916	13716	N/A	3200	12.33%	8.7%	3000	15	Nil	
Southeast Bank Limited	247252	21211	7298	28510	24725	N/A	3784	11.53%	8.6%	3000	15%	Nil	
Standard Bank Limited	113650	11044	3202	14246	11365	N/A	2881	12.53%	9.7%	2000	Nil	15	
UCBL	273325	22406	10820	33226	27333	N/A	5894	12.16%	8.2%	6600	20	5	

List of sampled banks who failed to meet Basel III minimum capital requirement in 2016

Figures in Millions	RWA Assets	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Capital	Regulatory Capital (10% of RWA or BDT 4,000 whichever Higher) Surplus/Shortages	Capital Conservation Buffer .625%	CAR + CCB		
							Capital (min Surplus/Shortages 10.625% of RWA)	Tier 1 capital to RWA 5.50%	
Agrani Bank Limited	266995	16915	9856	26771	26700	1669	-1597	10.03%	6.34%
Bangladesh Krishi Bank	135809	-63874	5479	-58395	13581	849	-72825	-43.00%	-47.03%
Basic Bank Limited	112019	-18591	630	-17961	11202	700	-29863	-16.03%	-16.60%
Rupali Bank Limited	176967	8908	2928	11836	17697	1106	-6967	6.69%	5.03%
Sonali Bank Limited	451930	33656	13032	46688	45193	2825	-1330	10.33%	7.45%
Private Commercial Bank									
Commerce Bank Limited	26719	338	122	460	2672	167	-2379	1.72%	1.27%
ICB Islamic Bank Ltd.	93529	-10711	196	-10515	9353	585	-20452	-11.24%	-11.45%

List of sampled state banks capital structure in 2016

Figures+B4:N27 in BDT m	RWA Capital	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Capital	Regulatory Capital (10% of RWA or BDT 4,000 whichever Higher) Surplus/Shortages	Capital Conservation Buffer .625%	CAR + CCB			Subordinated debt	Dividend Cash	Dividend Bonus Share
							Capital (min Surplus/Shortages 10.625% of RWA)	Tier 1 capital to RWA (5.50% min)				
State commercial banks capital structure undr Basel III in 2016												
Agrani Bank Limited	266995	16915	9856	26771	26700	1669	-1597	10.03%	6.34%	Nil	NA	Nil
BDBL	47441	9870	2291	12161	4744	297	7120	25.63%	20.80%	Nil	NA	Nil
Bangladesh Krishi Bank	135809	-63874	5479	-58395	13581	849	-72825	-43.00%	-47.03%	Nil	NA	Nil
Basic Bank Limited	112019	-18591	630	-17961	11202	700	-29863	-16.03%	-16.60%	Nil	NA	Nil
Janata Bank Limited	404088	35760	7430	43190	40409	2526	255	10.69%	8.85%	Nil	NA	Nil
Rupali Bank Limited	176967	8908	2928	11836	17697	1106	-6967	6.69%	5.03%	Nil	NA	Nil
Sonali Bank Limited	451930	33656	13032	46688	45193	2825	-1330	10.33%	7.45%	Nil	NA	Nil

List of sampled commercial banks capital structure under Basel III in 2016

Private commercial banks capital structure under Basel III in 2016												
AB Bank Limited	287204	19806	12063	31869	28720	1795	1354	11.10%	6.90%	6500		12.50%
Al-Arafah Islami Bank Limited	164461	20359	5095	25454	16446	1028	7980	15.48%	12.38%	3000	20%	
Al-Falah Bank in Bangladesh	9627	5288	146	5434	963	60	4411	56.45%	54.93%	Nil		
Commerce Bank Limited	26719	338	122	460	2672	167	-2379	1.72%	1.27%	Nil	Nil	
Bank Asia Limited	199490	16736	8039	24775	19949	1247	3579	12.42%	8.39%	3197	Nil	15%
BRAC Bank Limited	188431	19707	3389	23095	18843	1178	3074	12.26%	10.46%	3000	10%	20%
Citibank N.A	21977	9177	290	9467	2198	137	7132	43.08%	41.76%	3000	24%	Nil
Dhaka Bank Limited	175292	14210	8071	22281	17529	1096	3656	12.71%	8.11%	Nil	10%	5%
Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	162164	16750	6502	23252	16216	1014	6022	14.34%	10.33%	3700	30%	Nil
Eastern Bank Limited	148819	16078	6394	22472	14882	930	6660	15.10%	10.80%	2500	0	5%
EXIM Bank Limited	251259	24024	5694	29718	25126	1570	3022	11.83%	9.56%	2500	12%	Nil
First Security Islami Bank Limited	135249	10152	4065	14217	13525	845	-153	10.51%	7.51%	1382	5%	5%
ICB Islamic Bank Ltd.	93529	-10711	196	-10515	9353	585	-20452	-11.24%	-11.45%	Nil Nil	Nil	
IFC Bank Limited	150528	11609	5318	16928	15053	941	934	11.25%	7.71%	3500	Nil	12%
Islami Bank Bangladesh Ltd	467210	40956	9708	50664	46721	2920	1023	10.84%	8.77%	3000	10%	Nil
Jamuna Bank Ltd	145593	11359	4398	15757	14559	910	288	10.82%	7.80%	Nil	20.50%	Nil
Meghna Bank	23104	5189	251	5440	2310	144	2985	23.55%	22.46%	Nil	3%	Nil
Mutual Trust Bank Limited	118998	8983	4715	13698	11900	744	1054	11.51%	7.55%	4250	Nil	15%
National Bank Limited	283629	32240	5181	37421	28363	1773	7285	13.19%	11.37%	1024	Nil	20
NCC Bank Ltd	147469	16186	1532	17718	14747	922	2049	12.01%	10.98%	Nil	Nil	Nil
One Bank Limited	145350	12432	7561	19993	14535	908	4550	13.76%	8.55%	5320	13%	10%
Premiar Bank	126049	9692	5915	15607	12605	788	2214	12.38%	7.69%	5200	12%	2%
Prime Bank Ltd	254008	23634	7998	31632	25401	1588	4644	12.45%	9.30%	2500	10%	Nil
Pubali Bank Limited	234587	22198	4782	26980	23459	1466	2055	11.50%	9.46%	Nil	5%	8%
Shahjalal Bank Limited	124706	12857	12857	25714	12471	779	12464	20.62%	10.31%	Nil	10%	5%
Social Islami Bank Ltd	166173	13183	6011	19194	16617	1039	1538	11.55%	7.93%	3000	15%	5%
Southeast Bank Limited	280402	21686	12371	34056	28040	1753	4264	12.14%	7.73%	7400	20%	Nil
Standard Bank Limited	118981	10404	3369	13773	11898	744	1131	11.57%	8.74%	2000	5%	5%
UCBL	294398	23027	10495	33522	29440	1840	2242	11.38%	7.82%	6200	15%	Nil

List of sampled bank who failed to meet Basel III minimum capital structure in 2017

Figures in Millions	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Eligible Capital	Regulatory Capital (10% of RWA or BDT 4,000 whichever Higher)	Capital Buffer 1.25%	CAR + Capital CCB(min 11.25% of RWA)	Tier 1 capital to total capital + Conv. Buffer (6% min)	Retained Profits		
State bank										
Agrani Bank Limited	336788	20663	13819	34482	33679	4210	-3407	10.24%	6.14%	-1032
Janata Bank	443422	39819	4777	44596	44342	5543	-5289	10.06%	8.98%	9164
Bangladesh Krishi Bank	142609	-66131	6908	-59223	14261	1783	-75267	-41.53%	-46.37%	-78451
Basic Bank Limited	119712	-16582	749	-15833	11971	1496	-29301	-13.23%	-13.85%	26523
Rupali Bank Limited	199520	9967	3061	13028	19952	2494	-9418	6.53%	5.00%	731
Sonali Bank Limited	460756	37166	10517	47683	46076	5759	-4152	10.35%	8.07%	-1445
Privet Bank										
Commerce Bank Limited	30204	798	127	925	3020	378	-2473	3.06%	2.64%	112
ICB Islamic Bank Ltd.	94905	-11117	140	-10977	9491	1186	-21654	-11.57%	-11.71%	-17731
Southeast Bank Limited	311557	21165	12599	33764	31156	3894	-1286	10.84%	6.79%	2640

List of sampled state banks capital structure in 2017

Figures In BDT Million	RWA Capital Requirement	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Capital	Regulatory Capital (10% of RWA or BDT 4,000 whichever Higher)	Capital Buffer 1.25%	CAR + Capital CCB(min 11.25% of RWA)	Tier 1 capital to total capital + Conv. Buffer (6% min)	Retained Profits	Subordinated Bonds	Dividend cash	Dividend stock	
State Banks													
Agrani Bank Limited	336788	20663	13819	34482	33679	4210	-3407	10.24%	6.14%	-1032	Nil	NA	NA
BDBL	45668	10694	1432	12126	4567	571	6988	26.55%	23.42%	367	Nil	NA	NA
Janata Bank	443422	39819	4777	44596	44342	5543	-5289	10.06%	8.98%	9164	Nil	NA	NA
Bangladesh Krishi Bank	142609	-66131	6908	-59223	14261	1783	-75267	-41.53%	-46.37%	-78451	Nil	NA	NA
Basic Bank Limited	119712	-16582	749	-15833	11971	1496	-29301	-13.23%	-13.85%	26523	Nil	NA	NA
Rupali Bank Limited	199520	9967	3061	13028	19952	2494	-9418	6.53%	5.00%	731	Nil	NA	NA
Sonali Bank Limited	460756	37166	10517	47683	46076	5759	-4152	10.35%	8.07%	-1445	Nil	NA	NA

Private Commercial Banks													
Figures In BDT Million	RWA Capital Requirement	Tier 1 Capital	Tier 2 Capital	Total Capital	Regulatory Capital (10% of RWA or BDT 4,000 whichever Higher)	Capital Buffer 1.25%	Capital Surplus/Shortages	CAR + CCB(min 11.25% of RWA)	Tier 1 capital to total capital + Conv. Buffer (6% min)	Retained Profits	Subordinated Bonds	Dividend cash	Dividend stock
AB Bank Limited	293184	20850	12133	32983	29318	3665	0	11.25%	7.11%	6012	6000	Nil	Nil
Al-Arafah Islami Bank Limited	204457	19615	5488	25103	20446	2556	2102	12.28%	9.59%	2176	3000	15	5
Al-Falah Bank	9810	5536	160	5696	981	123	4592	58.06%	56.43%	1108	Nil	Nil	Nil
Commerce Bank Limited	30204	798	127	925	3020	378	-2473	3.06%	2.64%	112	Nil	Nil	Nil
Bank Asia Limited	221143	18853	14061	32914	22114	2764	8035	14.88%	8.53%	1554	8093	Nil	12.5 S
BRAC Bank Limited	209353	23534	3102	26636	20935	2617	3084	12.72%	11.24%	7992	Nil	10	20
Citibank N.A	26097	9914	413	10327	2610	326	7391	39.57%	37.99%	5260	3000	19	5
Dhaka Bank Limited	182950	14539	7344	21883	18295	2287	1301	11.96%	7.95%	953	3000	Nil	12.5
Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	180138	18617	9798	28415	18014	2252	8149	15.77%	10.33%	5846	6550	30	Nil
Eastern Bank Limited	165441	16943	6358	23301	16544	2068	4689	14.08%	10.24%	3305	2500	20	Nil
EXIM Bank Limited	287420	24852	9962	34814	28742	3593	2479	12.11%	8.65%	2475	6500	12.5	Nil
First Security Islami Bank Limited	163612	11081	8561	19642	16361	2045	1236	12.01%	6.77%	724	5382	Nil	Nil
ICB Islamic Bank Ltd.	94905	-11117	140	-10977	9491	1186	-21654	-11.57%	-11.71%	-17731	Nil	Nil	nil
IFIC Bank Limited	220038	21856	5274	27130	22004	2750	2376	12.33%	9.93%	4623	5274	Nil	12
Islami Bank Bangladesh Ltd	513099	44026	13932	57958	51310	6414	234	11.30%	8.58%	1610	5000	10	Nil
Jamuna Bank Ltd	168130	12188	7721	19909	16813	2102	994	11.84%	7.25%	1346	5000	Nil	22
Meghna Bank	27824	5146	292	5438	2782	348	2308	19.54%	18.49%	2772	Nil	10	Nil
Mutual Trust Bank Limited	136592	9977	8869	18846	13659	1707	3479	13.80%	7.30%	1632	6159	Nil	12.5
National Bank Limited	345758	39806	8567	42173	34576	4322	3275	12.20%	11.51%	3157	2750	Nil	12
NCC Bank Ltd	158051	16431	1763	18194	15805	1976	413	11.51%	10.40%	1151	Nil	Nil	Nil
One Bank Limited	184800	14045	7319	21364	18480	2310	574	11.56%	7.60%	1681	4880	15	5
Premiar Bank	143522	11262	6126	17388	14352	1794	1242	12.12%	7.85%	2030	5400	Nil	15
Prime Bank Ltd	230219	23179	9071	32250	23022	2878	6350	14.01%	10.07%	1079	4880	7	10
Pubali Bank Limited	247245	23216	8758	31974	24725	3091	4159	12.93%	9.39%	4198	5000	Nil	10
Shahjalal Bank Limited	158934	13317	6058	19375	15893	1987	1495	12.19%	8.38%	784	4000	Nil	10
Social Islami Bank Ltd	187743	13187	8538	21725	18774	2347	604	11.57%	7.02%	778	5440	Nil	10
Southeast Bank Limited	311557	21165	12599	33764	31156	3894	-1286	10.84%	6.79%	2640	6800	Nil	15
Standard Bank Limited	143438	13280	7066	20346	14344	1793	4209	14.18%	9.26%	799	5600	5	5
UCBL	305859	23595	13039	36634	30586	3823	2225	11.98%	7.71%	1389	8300	10	Nil

Appendix 10 Historical corporate and SME loan Interest rate

Historical Loan Interest Jan 2014 to Jan 2017										
Banks	Term Loan to Large and Medium Enterprise					Term Loan to Small Enterprise				
	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%
PUBALI	12.50-15.50	15	14	13.00-14.00	12	12.50-15.50	15	14	13.00-14.00	12
UTTARA	15.50-17.00	15.00-16.00	10.50-13.50	10.50-13.50	12.00-13.50	0	15.50-17.00	12.50-15.50	11.00-14.00	12.00-13.50
AB-BANK	12.50-15.50	12.50-15.50	10.50-13.50	10.00-13.00	10.50-13.50	15.50-17.00	13.50-16.50	11.50-14.50	11.00-14.00	11.50-14.50
IFIC	16	13.50-14.00	13	10.00-13.00	9.50-12.50	0	15	15	11.50-14.50	11.50-14.50
ISLAMI	16	16	12.00-15.00	11	11	13.00-15.50	16	12.00-15.00	11	11
NBL	14.50-17.50	14	13	10.00-13.00	10.00-13.00	0	17.00-18.00	15.00-16.00	10.00-13.00	10.00-13.00
UCBL	18.00-16.50	15.00-16.50	15.00-16.50	8.50-11.50	0	13.50-16.50	16.00-18.00	16.00-18.00	10.50-13.50	0
ICB	13.00-16.00	11.50-14.50	11.00-14.00	15.00-16.50	15.00-16.50	16.00-18.00	14.00-17.00	13.00-16.00	16.00-18.00	16.00-18.00
EBL	16	13.50-16.50	10.50-13.50	8.50-11.50	8.50-11.50	15.00-18.00	13.50-16.50	11.50-14.50	9.50-12.50	9.50-12.50
NCCBL	13.50-16.50	12.00-15.00	11.00-14.00	9.00-12.00	9.00-12.00	16	15.00-18.00	14.00-17.00	10.50-13.50	10.50-13.50
DHAKA	16	16	11.00-14.00	8.50-11.50	8.50-11.50	17.00-19.00	16	11.00-14.00	12.50-15.50	11.00-13.50
AL-ARAFAH	16	15	11.00-14.00	11.00-14.00	11.00-14.00	16	15	11.00-14.00	11.00-14.00	11.00-14.00
SIBL	0	0	11.00-14.00	10.00-13.00	11.00-14.00	14.00-15.00	12.00-15.00	12.00-15.00	11.50-14.50	0
DUTCH-BANGLA	14.00-17.00	12.00-15.00	11.00-14.00	9.00-12.00	9.00-12.00	0	13.00-16.00	0	10.00-13.00	10.00-13.00
MERCANTILE	12.50-15.50	12.50-15.50	12.00-15.00	12.00-15.00	12.00-15.00	15.00-18.00	15.00-18.00	14.00-17.00	13.00-16.00	13.00-16.00
ONE BANK	14.00-16.00	12.50-16.50	12.50-15.50	12.00-15.00	12.00-15.00	15.00-18.00	13.50-16.50	15.00-18.00	14.00-17.00	14.00-17.00

Banks	Term Loan to Large and Medium Enterprise					Term Loan to Small Enterprise				
	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%
EXIM	15.00-17.00	12.50-16.50	12.00-15.00	12.00-15.00	12.00-15.00	15.00-17.00	13.50-16.50	13.50-16.50	12.00-15.00	12.00-15.00
PREMIER	14	14	12.00-15.00	10.00-13.00	10.50-13.50	15.00-17.00	14	13.50-16.50	12.50-15.50	11.00-14.00
FIRST SECU	12.50-15.50	12.00-15.00	13	11.00-14.00	10.50-13.50	17	12.00-15.00	14	11.00-14.00	10.50-13.50
STANDARD	0	12.50-16.50	10.50-13.50	13	12.5	12.50-15.50	0	10.50-13.50	13	12.5
TRUST BANK	12.50-15.50	12.50-15.50	11.00-14.00	8.00-11.00	9.00-12.00	0	12.50-15.50	0	8.00-11.00	0
MUTUAL TRUST	0	0	11.00-14.00	9.50-12.50	9.00-12.00	12.50-15.50	0	14.00-17.00	9.50-12.50	9.00-12.00
BANK ASIA	14.00-17.00	14.00-17.00	15	9.00-12.00	9.00-12.00	0	16.50-19.50	20	9.00-12.00	12.00-15.00
BCBL	16	15	14	14	14	15.50-18.50	15.00-18.00	13.00-16.00	14	14
JAMUNA	0	0	0	13	13.5	0	0	0	13	13.5
SHAHJALAL	0	0	0	9.00-12.00	10.00-13.00	16.00-19.00	0	13.00-16.00	12.00-15.00	11.50-14.50
BRAC	13.00-16.00	11.00-14.00	0	10.00-13.00	11.00-14.00	17.00-20.00	20.75-23.75	0	14.00-17.00	14.00-17.00
NRBCBL	15.00-16.00	13.00-16.00	12.00-15.00	10.50-13.50	11.50-14.50	20.75-23.75	13.00-16.00	13.50-16.50	12.50-15.50	12.00-15.00
SBACBL	14.50-17.50	14.00-17.50	12.00-15.00	11.00-14.00	11.00-14.00	14.50-17.50	14.00-17.50	13.00-16.00	12.00-15.00	12.00-15.00
MGBL	13.00-16.00	12.50-15.50	12.50-15.50	12.00-15.00	9.50-12.50	15.00-18.00	15.00-18.00	15.00-18.00	12.00-15.00	11.00-14.00
MDBL	15.00-18.00	13.00-16.00	11.00-14.00	9.50-12.50	9.00-12.00	15	10	13.50-16.50	11.00-14.00	11.50-14.50
NRBGBL	0	0	15.00-16.00	15.00-16.00	15.00-16.00	15.50-18.50	14.00-17.00	15.00-18.00	15.00-18.00	15.00-18.00
FBL	15.50-16.50	15.00-16.00	13.00-15.50	13.00-15.50	13.00-15.50	16.00-16.50	15.00-18.00	13.00-15.50	13.00-15.50	13.00-15.50
MMBL	14.50-15.50	14.50-15.50	14	11.50-14.50	11.50-14.00	14.50-17.50	14.50-17.50	15	14.50-15.00	14.50-15.00
NRBBL		15	12.00-15.00	10.00-13.00	10.00-13.00		15	14.00-17.00	12.00-16.00	12.00-20.00

Appendix 11 Ratio Analysis data

Year	City Bank	Islami Bank	AB Bank	Bank Asia	Dhaka Bank	NCC Bank	BRAC Bank	Premiar Bank	Exim Bank
2012	11.11	7	9.78	11.36	10.81	10.91	12.07	8.11	9.69
2013	12.8	10.87	10.13	12.48	10.18	11.26	11.59	14.88	11.24
2014	11.7	10.37	10.18	12.73	12.05	11.47	11.44	13.05	10.48
2015	11.65	11.53	10.37	12.04	11.95	11.86	12.09	11.05	12.09
2016	15.42	10.56	10.14	12.71	13.18	13.47	14.71	11.32	13.47
2017	14.03	12.16	10.07	12.74	14.24	13.52	12.23	12.42	10.93
2018	13.57	11.39	11.25	12.45	15.1	11.97	12.26	12.42	13.89
2019	14.71	12.07	12.57	14.01	14.09	11.51	12.72	14.89	11.56

Table: Capital to Risk-Weighted Ratio of Banks (%)

Year	City Bank	Islami Bank	AB Bank	Bank Asia	Dhaka Bank	NCC Bank	BRAC Bank	Premiar Bank	Exim Bank
2012	8.31	4.86	8.36	8.25	8.02	9.66	7.43	6.53	7.91
2013	9.62	9.2	8.55	9.64	7.82	10.19	7.46	11.4	9.22
2014	8.98	8.45	8.66	10.14	9.42	10.47	7.76	9.79	9.16
2015	9.04	8.75	8.96	9.73	9.44	10.87	8.44	8.44	8.53
2016	9.97	7.92	8.69	10.48	10.17	12.31	11.94	8.99	8.46
2017	10.08	8.2	8.96	10	10.22	12.41	10.27	8.95	8.46
2018	10.16	7.82	7.71	9.3	10.8	10.93	10.46	8.39	8.72
2019	10.15	7.71	9.84	10.01	10.24	10.25	11.24	8.53	7.6

Table: Tier 1/Core Capital ratio of Banks (%)

Year	City Bank	Islami Bank	AB Bank	Bank Asia	Dhaka Bank	NCC Bank	BRAC Bank	Premiar Bank	Exim Bank
2012	2.03	1.68	2.37	1.97	2.95	2.84	1.42	1.83	3.21
2013	1.74	1.74	0.78	1.82	2.14	2.12	1.28	1.63	2.14
2014	0.59	0.76	0.96	1.14	1.67	1.14	0.31	0.65	1.23
2015	0.62	1.35	1.02	0.75	1.44	0.92	0.73	0.89	1.31
2016	1.25	1.38	0.99	0.94	1.22	1.11	1.02	1.21	1.72
2017	1.67	1.35	0.5	0.85	1.17	0.93	1.08	1.15	1.25
2018	1.55	0.8	0.62	0.81	1.26	1.2	1.79	0.61	1.09
2019	1.32	0.67	0.82	0.38	0.95	0.87	1.81	0.71	0.96

Table: Return on Asset (ROA) of Banks (%)

Year	City Bank	Islami Bank	AB Bank	Bank Asia	Dhaka Bank	NCC Bank	BRAC Bank	Premiar Bank	Exim Bank
2012	16.05	27.92	28.65	17.91	20.07	25.35	17.74	27.33	38.8
2013	11.3	18.45	10.88	19.03	17.5	18.98	17.73	15.36	22.83
2014	4.25	8.73	14.25	12.98	15.01	11.81	5.32	6.96	14.22
2015	4.92	14.95	14.79	7.94	12.33	8.58	10.76	9.99	15.73
2016	9.58	16.31	14.53	9.78	10.49	10.54	11.78	13.16	20.5
2017	14.03	15.54	7.61	8.1	10.84	8.71	12.94	13.56	16.6
2018	19.15	10.21	9.46	8.68	12.91	12.56	20.8	8.12	15.95
2019	14.59	9.18	10.07	4.29	11.14	10.33	20.2	9.72	15.46

Table: Return on Equity (ROE) of Banks (%)

The first-generation Banks

Year	City Bank	Islami Bank	AB Bank		
2012	11.11	7	9.78		
2013	12.8	10.87	10.13	Mean	11.48
2014	11.7	10.37	10.18	Standard Deviation	1.80
2015	11.65	11.53	10.37		
2016	15.42	10.56	10.14	Maximum	15.42
2017	14.03	12.16	10.07		
2018	13.57	11.39	11.25	Minimum	7.00
2019	14.71	12.07	12.57		

Table: Capital to Risk-Weighted Ratio of Banks (%)

Year	City Bank	Islami Bank	AB Bank		
2012	8.31	4.86	8.36		
2013	9.62	9.2	8.55	Mean	8.71
2014	8.98	8.45	8.66	Standard Deviation	1.13
2015	9.04	8.75	8.96		
2016	9.97	7.92	8.69	Maximum	10.16
2017	10.08	8.2	8.96		
2018	10.16	7.82	7.71	Minimum	4.86

2019	10.15	7.71	9.84
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Table: Tier 1/Core Capital ratio of Banks (%)

Year	City Bank	Islami Bank	AB Bank		
2012	2.03	1.68	2.37		
2013	1.74	1.74	0.78	Mean	1.19
2014	0.59	0.76	0.96	Standard Deviation	0.51
2015	0.62	1.35	1.02		
2016	1.25	1.38	0.99		
2017	1.67	1.35	0.5	Maximum	2.37
2018	1.55	0.8	0.62		
2019	1.32	0.67	0.82	Minimum	0.50

Table: Return on Asset (ROA) of Banks (%)

Year	City Bank	Islami Bank	AB Bank		
2012	16.05	27.92	28.65		
2013	11.3	18.45	10.88	Mean	13.56
2014	4.25	8.73	14.25	Standard Deviation	5.97
2015	4.92	14.95	14.79		
2016	9.58	16.31	14.53		
2017	14.03	15.54	7.61	Maximum	28.65
2018	19.15	10.21	9.46		
2019	14.59	9.18	10.07	Minimum	4.25

Table: Return on Equity (ROE) of Banks (%)

The second-generation banks

	Bank Asia	Dhaka Bank	NCC Bank		
2012	11.36	10.81	10.91		
2013	12.48	10.18	11.26	Mean	12.42042
2014	12.73	12.05	11.47		
2015	12.04	11.95	11.86	Standard Deviation	1.217569
2016	12.71	13.18	13.47		
2017	12.74	14.24	13.52	Maximum	15.1
2018	12.45	15.1	11.97		
2019	14.01	14.09	11.51	Minimum	10.18
Table: Capital to Risk Weighted Ratio of Banks (%)					

	Bank Asia	Dhaka Bank	NCC Bank		
2012	8.25	8.02	9.66	Mean	10.03208
2013	9.64	7.82	10.19		
2014	10.14	9.42	10.47	Standard Deviation	1.08906
2015	9.73	9.44	10.87		
2016	10.48	10.17	12.31		
2017	10	10.22	12.41	Maximum	12.41
2018	9.3	10.8	10.93		
2019	10.01	10.24	10.25	Minimum	7.82
Table: Tier 1/Core Capital ratio of Banks (%)					

	Bank Asia	Dhaka Bank	NCC Bank		
2012	1.97	2.95	2.84	Mean	1.357917
2013	1.82	2.14	2.12		
2014	1.14	1.67	1.14	Standard Deviation	0.649394
2015	0.75	1.44	0.92		
2016	0.94	1.22	1.11	Maximum	2.95
2017	0.85	1.17	0.93		
2018	0.81	1.26	1.2	Minimum	0.38
2019	0.38	0.95	0.87		
Table: Return on Asset (ROA) of Banks (%)					

	Bank Asia	Dhaka Bank	NCC Bank		
2012	17.91	20.07	25.35	Mean	12.74417
2013	19.03	17.5	18.98		
2014	12.98	15.01	11.81	Standard Deviation	4.861463
2015	7.94	12.33	8.58		
2016	9.78	10.49	10.54	Maximum	25.35
2017	8.1	10.84	8.71		
2018	8.68	12.91	12.56	Minimum	4.29
2019	4.29	11.14	10.33		

Table: Return on Equity (ROE) of Banks (%)

The third generation of banks

	BRAC Bank	Premiar Bank	Exim Bank		
2012	12.07	8.11	9.69	Mean	12.10833
2013	11.59	14.88	11.24		
2014	11.44	13.05	10.48	Standard Deviation	1.589347
2015	12.09	11.05	12.09		
2016	14.71	11.32	13.47	Maximum	14.89
2017	12.23	12.42	10.93		
2018	12.26	12.42	13.89	Minimum	8.11
2019	12.72	14.89	11.56		

Table: Capital to Risk Weighted Ratio of Banks (%)

	BRAC Bank	Premiar Bank	Exim Bank		
2012	7.43	6.53	7.91		
2013	7.46	11.4	9.22	Mean	8.92
2014	7.76	9.79	9.16		
2015	8.44	8.44	8.53	Standard Deviation	1.342266
2016	11.94	8.99	8.46		
2017	10.27	8.95	8.46	Maximum	11.94
2018	10.46	8.39	8.72		
2019	11.24	8.53	7.6	Minimum	6.53

Table: Tier 1/Core Capital ratio of Banks (%)

	BRAC Bank	Premiar Bank	Exim Bank		
				Mean	1.292917
2012	1.42	1.83	3.21		
2013	1.28	1.63	2.14	Standard Deviation	0.607135
2014	0.31	0.65	1.23		
2015	0.73	0.89	1.31	Maximum	3.21
2016	1.02	1.21	1.72		
2017	1.08	1.15	1.25	Minimum	0.31
2018	1.79	0.61	1.09		
2019	1.81	0.71	0.96		

Table: Return on Asset (ROA) of Banks (%)

	BRAC Bank	Premiar Bank	Exim Bank		
				Mean	15.89833
2012	17.74	27.33	38.8		
2013	17.73	15.36	22.83	Standard Deviation	7.126042
2014	5.32	6.96	14.22		
2015	10.76	9.99	15.73	Maximum	38.8
2016	11.78	13.16	20.5		
2017	12.94	13.56	16.6	Minimum	5.32
2018	20.8	8.12	15.95		
2019	20.2	9.72	15.46		

Table: Return on Equity (ROE) of Banks (%)